

THE UNIVERSITY OF HAWAI‘I AT MĀNOA

Hydrographic Observations At the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution Hawaii Ocean Time-series Site: 2022 - 2023

by

Fernando Carvalho Pacheco¹, Fernando Santiago-Mandujano¹, James Potemra¹,
Albert Plueddemann², Robert Weller², Daniel Fitzgerald¹, and Nan Galbraith²

Friday 27th December, 2024

Data Report - 18

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Table of contents

Table of contents	i
List of figures	iii
List of tables	vii
1 Introduction	1
2 Description of the WHOTS-18 Mooring Cruises	4
2.1 WHOTS-18 Cruise: WHOTS-18 Mooring Deployment	4
2.2 WHOTS-19 Cruise: WHOTS-18 Mooring Recovery	6
3 Description of WHOTS-18 Mooring	8
3.1 Surface Components	8
3.2 Subsurface Instrumentation	9
4 WHOTS (18-19) Cruise Shipboard Observations	14
4.1 Conductivity, Temperature, and Depth (CTD) Profiling	14
4.1.1 Data Acquisition and Processing	15
4.1.2 CTD Sensor Calibration and Corrections	15
4.1.2.1 Pressure	15
4.1.2.2 Temperature/Conductivity	15
4.1.2.3 Dissolved Oxygen	15
4.2 Water Sampling and Analysis	16
4.2.1 Salinity	16
4.3 Thermosalinograph Data Acquisition and Processing	16
4.3.1 WHOTS-18 Cruise	16
4.3.1.1 Temperature Calibration	17
4.3.1.2 Nominal Conductivity Calibration	17
4.3.1.3 Data Processing	17
4.3.1.4 Bottle salinity and CTD Salinity Comparisons	17
4.3.1.5 CTD Temperature Comparisons	18
4.3.2 WHOTS-19 Cruise	18
4.3.2.1 Temperature Calibration	18
4.3.2.2 Nominal Conductivity Calibration	18
4.3.2.3 Data Processing	18
4.3.2.4 Bottle salinity and CTD Salinity Comparisons	19
4.3.2.5 CTD Temperature Comparisons	19
4.4 Shipboard ADCP	19
4.4.1 WHOTS-18 Deployment Cruise	19
4.4.2 WHOTS-19 Deployment Cruise	20
5 Moored Instrument Observations	21
5.1 MicroCAT Data Processing Procedures	21
5.1.1 Internal Clock Check and Missing Samples	22
5.1.2 Pressure Drift Correction and Pressure Variability	22

5.1.3	Temperature Sensor Stability	22
5.1.3.1	Comparisons with VMCM and ADCP temperature sensors	25
5.1.4	Conductivity Calibration	25
5.2	Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler	30
5.2.1	Compass Calibrations	30
5.2.1.1	Pre-Deployment	30
5.2.1.2	Post-Deployment	39
5.2.2	ADCP Configurations	39
5.2.2.1	300 kHz (SN/4891 - 125m)	39
5.2.2.2	600 kHz (SN/1825- 47.5m)	39
5.2.3	ADCP data processing procedures	42
5.2.3.1	ADCP Clock Drift	44
5.2.3.2	Heading Bias	44
5.2.3.3	Speed of sound	44
5.2.3.4	Quality Control	44
5.3	Vector Measuring Current Meter (VMCM)	49
5.4	Global Positioning System Receiver	49
6	Results	55
6.1	CTD Profiling Data	56
6.2	Thermosalinograph Data	56
6.3	MicroCAT Data	69
6.4	Moored ADCP Data	69
6.5	Moored and Shipboard ADCP comparisons	89
6.5.1	WHOTS-18 Deployment Comparison	89
6.5.2	WHOTS-19 Deployment Comparison	90
6.6	Next Generation Vector Measuring Current Meter Data (VMCM)	90
6.7	GPS Data	97
6.8	Mooring Motion	98
7	Appendix: Instrument Configurations and Specifications	100
7.1	WHOTS-18 300 kHz - Serial 4891	100
7.2	WHOTS-18 600 kHz - Serial 1825	103
7.3	WHOTS-18 MicroCAT - Headers	110
	References	185

List of figures

1.1	WHOTS-18 mooring design	2
3.1	WHOTS-18 mooring subsurface instrument deployment information. All times are in UTC	10
5.1	Linearly corrected pressures from MicroCATs between 7 and 155 m during WHOTS-18 deployment. The horizontal dashed line is the sensor's nominal pressure, based on deployed depth. The text on the left (right) side of the figure indicates the mean (standard deviation) of the difference between each instrument's pressure and nominal pressure.	23
5.2	The temperature difference between MicroCAT SN 7212 at 1 m, and near-surface temperature sensors SN 7212 (top panel), 7213 (second panel), 7214 (third panel), and 7215 (bottom panel), during the WHOTS-18 deployment. The light blue line is a 24-hour running mean of the differences.	24
5.3	The temperature difference between the 7-m MicroCAT and the 10-m VMCM (upper panel); between the 15-m MicroCAT and the 10-m VMCM (middle panel); and between the 7-m and the 15-m MicroCATs (lower panel) during the WHOTS-18 deployment. The light blue line is a 24-hour running mean of the differences.	26
5.4	The temperature difference between the 25-m MicroCAT and the 30-m VMCM (upper panel); between the 30-m MicroCAT and the 40-m VMCM (middle panel); and between the 25-m and the 40-m MicroCATs (lower panel) during the WHOTS-18 deployment. The light blue line is a 24-hour running mean of the differences.	27
5.5	The temperature difference between the 45-m MicroCAT and the 47.5-m ADCP (upper panel) (The ADCP stopped collecting data on 2023/2/10); between the 50-m MicroCAT and the 47.5-m ADCP (middle panel); and between the 45-m and the 50-m MicroCATs (lower panel) during the WHOTS-18 deployment. The light blue line is a 24-hour running mean of the differences.	28
5.6	The temperature difference between the 120-m MicroCAT and the 125-m ADCP (upper panel) (the ADCP stopped collecting data on 2023/1/24); between the 135-m MicroCAT and the 125-m ADCP (middle panel); and between the 120-m and the 135-m MicroCATs (lower panel) during the WHOTS-18 deployment. The light blue line is a 24-hour running mean of the differences.	29
5.7	Temperature differences (top panel) and salinity differences (bottom panel) between MicroCATs #12241 and #11391 during WHOTS-18. The blue (red) lines are the differences before (after) correcting the data following the text's procedures.	31
5.8	Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs from 1 to 7 meters during WHOTS-18.	32
5.9	Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs from 15 to 25 meters during WHOTS-18	33
5.10	Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs from 40 to 50 meters during WHOTS-18	34
5.11	Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs from 55 to 75 meters during WHOTS-18.	35
5.12	Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs from 85 to 105 meters during WHOTS-18.	36
5.13	Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs from 120 to 155 meters during WHOTS-18.	37
5.14	Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs at 4710 meters during WHOTS-18.	38

5.15	Results of the pre-cruise compass calibration, conducted on June 28, 2022, for ADCP SN 4891 at the University of Hawai'i at Manoa. Unfortunately, a post-cruise compass calibration could not be performed due to corrosion of the bulkhead connectors following the cruise.	40
5.16	Results of the pre-cruise compass calibration, conducted on June 28, 2022, for ADCP SN 1825 at the University of Hawai'i at Manoa. Unfortunately, a post-cruise compass calibration could not be performed due to corrosion of the bulkhead connectors following the cruise.	41
5.17	temperature record from the 300 khz adcp during whots-18 mooring (top panel). the bottom panel shows the beginning and end of the record, with the green vertical line representing the in-water time during deployment and out-of-water recovery time. the red line represents the anchor release and acoustic release trigger for deployment and recovery, respectively.	42
5.18	Same as Fig. 5.17, but for the 600 kHz ADCP.	43
5.19	Sound speed profile (top panel) during the deployment of the WHOTS-18 mooring from 2 dbar CTD data taken during regular HOT cruises and CTD profiles taken during the WHOTS-18 and -19 deployment cruises (individual casts marked with a red diamond). The bottom left panels show the sound velocity at a depth of the ADCP's (47.5 m and 125 m), with the mean sound velocity indicated with a dashed black line. The lower right panels show the temperature and salinity at each ADCP depth for the time series, with the mean temperatures indicated with blue lines and mean salinity indicated with red lines.	45
5.20	Eastward velocity component for the 300 kHz (top panel) and the 600 kHz (bottom panel) ADCPs are showing the incoherence between depth bins 1 (red), 2 (green), and 3 (blue).	46
5.21	Histogram of the vertical velocity of the 300 kHz ADCP for raw data (top panel) and enlarged for clarity (upper middle panel), and partial quality controlled data (lower middle panel) and enlarged for clarity (bottom).	47
5.22	Same as Fig. 5.21, but for 600kHz ADCP.	48
5.23	A comparison of 30 m VMCM and ADCP U velocity for WHOTS-18. The top panel shows 24-hour moving averages of VMCM zonal (U) velocity at 30 m depth (red) and ADCP U velocity from the nearest depth bin to 30 m. The middle panel shows the U velocity difference, and the bottom panel shows the percentage of ADCP data within the moving average not flagged by quality control methods.	50
5.24	Same as in Fig. 5.23 but for the meridional (V) velocity component.	51
5.25	Same as in Fig. 5.23 but for the 10 m VMCM.	52
5.26	Same as Fig. 5.25, but for the meridional (V) velocity component.	53
6.1	[Upper left panel] Profiles of CTD temperature, salinity, and potential density ($\sigma\theta$) as a function of pressure, including discrete bottle salinity samples (when available) for station 20 cast 1 during the WHOTS-18 cruise. [Upper right panel] Profiles of CTD salinity as a function of potential temperature, including discrete bottle salinity samples (when available) for station 20 cast 1 during the WHOTS-18 cruise. [Lower left panel] Same as in the upper left panel, but for station 50 cast 1. [Lower right panel] Same as in the upper right panel, but station 50 cast 1.	57
6.2	[Upper panels] Same as in Fig. 6.1, but for station 50, cast 2. [Lower panels] Same as Fig. 6.1, but for station 50, cast 3.	58
6.3	[Upper panels] Same as in Fig. 6.1, but for station 50, cast 4. [Lower panels] Same as in Fig. 6.1, but for station 52 cast 1.	59
6.4	[Upper panels] Same as in Fig. 6.1, but for station 52, cast 2. [Lower panels] Same as in Fig. 6.1, but for station 52, cast 3.	60
6.5	[Upper panels] Same as in Fig. 6.1, but for station 52, cast 4.	61
6.6	[Upper left panel] Profiles of CTD temperature, salinity, and potential density ($\sigma\theta$) as a function of pressure, including discrete bottle salinity samples (when available) for station 20 cast 1 during the WHOTS-19 cruise. [Upper right panel] Profiles of CTD salinity as a function of potential temperature, including discrete bottle salinity samples (when available) for station 20 cast 1 during the WHOTS-19 cruise. [Lower left panel] Same as in the upper left panel, but for station 52 cast 1. [Lower right panel] Same as in the upper right panel, but station 52 cast 1.	62
6.7	Upper panels] Same as in Fig. 6.6, but for station 52, cast 1.[Lower panels] Same as in Fig. 6.6, but for station 52, cast 3.	63
6.8	Upper panels] Same as in Fig. 6.6, but for station 52, cast 4.	64

6.9	Final processed temperature (upper panel), salinity (middle panel), and potential density ($\sigma\theta$) (lower panel) data from the continuous underway system onboard the R/V Hi'ialakai during the WHOTS-18 cruise. Temperature and salinity taken from 6-dbar CTD data (circles) and salinity bottle sample data (crosses) are superimposed. The dashed vertical red line indicates the period of occupation of Station ALOHA and the WHOTS site.	65
6.10	Timeseries of latitude (upper panel), longitude (middle panel), and ship's speed (lower panel) during the WHOTS-18 cruise.	66
6.11	Final processed temperature (upper panel), salinity (middle panel), and potential density ($\sigma\theta$) (lower panel) data from the continuous underway system onboard the R/V Oscar Sette during the WHOTS-19 cruise. Temperature and salinity were taken from 6-dbar CTD data (circles), and salinity bottle sample data (crosses) are superimposed. The dashed vertical red line indicates the period of occupation of Station ALOHA and the WHOTS site.	67
6.12	Timeseries of latitude (upper panel), longitude (middle panel), and ship's speed (lower panel) during the WHOTS-19 cruise.	68
6.13	Temperatures from MicroCATs during WHOTS-18 deployment at 1.5, 7, 15, and 25m.	70
6.14	Same as in Fig. 6.13, but at 40, 45, 50, and 55m.	71
6.15	Same as in Fig. 6.13, but at 65, 75, 85, and 95m.	72
6.16	Same as in Fig. 6.13, but at 105, 120, 135, and 155m.	73
6.17	Salinities from MicroCATs during WHOTS-18 deployment at 1.5, 7, 15, and 25m	74
6.18	Same as in Fig. 6.17, but at 40, 45, 50 and 55m.	75
6.19	Same as in Fig. 6.17, but at 65, 75, 85, and 95 m	76
6.20	Same as in Fig. 6.17, but at 105, 120, 135, and 155 m.	77
6.21	Potential densities ($\sigma\theta$) from MicroCATs during WHOTS-18 deployment at 1.5, 7, 15, and 25m.	78
6.22	Same as in Fig. 6.21, but at 40, 45, 50, and 55m.	79
6.23	Same as in Fig. 6.21, but at 65, 75, 85, and 95m.	80
6.24	Same as in Fig. 6.21, but at 105, 120, 135, and 155 m.	81
6.25	Contour plots of temperature (upper panel) and salinity (lower panel) versus depth from SeaCATs/MicroCATs during WHOTS-1 through WHOTS-18 deployments. The shaded areas indicate missing data. The diamonds along the right axis indicate the depths of the instrument.	82
6.26	Contour plots of potential density ($\sigma\theta$), versus depth from SeaCATs/MicroCATs during WHOTS-1 through WHOTS-18 deployments. The shaded areas indicate missing data. The diamonds along the right axis in the upper figure indicate the depths of the instrument.	83
6.27	Contour plots of salinity versus $\sigma\theta$ from SeaCATs/MicroCATs during WHOTS-1 through WHOTS-18 deployments.	84
6.28	Potential temperature (upper panel) and salinity (lower panel) time-series from the ALOHA Cabled Observatory (ACO) sensors and the WHOTS-18 MicroCATs 11391 and 12241.	85
6.29	Contour plot of east velocity component (ms^{-1}) versus depth and time from the moored ADCPs from the WHOTS-1 through -18 deployments (upper panel). Contour plot of north velocity component (ms^{-1}) (middle panel). Contour plot of vertical velocity component (ms^{-1})(lower panel).	86
6.30	Contour plot of east velocity component (ms^{-1}) versus depth and time from the moored ADCP WHOTS-18 (upper panel). Contour plot of north velocity component (ms^{-1}) (middle panel). Contour plot of vertical velocity component (ms^{-1})(lower panel).	87
6.31	Staggered time-series of east velocity component (ms^{-1}) for each bin of the 600 kHz (upper panel) and 300 kHz (lower panel) moored ADCPs during WHOTS-18. The time-series are offset upwards by $0.5 ms^{-1}$; each bin's depth is on the right.	88
6.32	Same as Fig. 6.31 but for north velocity component	88
6.33	Same as Fig. 6.31 but for north velocity component but for vertical velocity component.	89
6.34	The contour of zonal currents (ms^{-1}) from the Ship Oscar Sette Ocean Surveyor narrowband 75 kHz shipboard ADCP (upper panel), and the moored 300 kHz ADCP from the WHOTS-18 mooring (bottom panel) as a function of time and depth, during the WHOTS-18 cruise. Times when the CTD rosette was in the water are identified between solid and dashed black lines.	91
6.35	The contour of meridional currents (ms^{-1}) from the Ship Oscar Sette Ocean Surveyor narrowband 75 kHz shipboard ADCP (upper panel), and the moored 300 kHz ADCP from the WHOTS-18 mooring (bottom panel) as a function of time and depth, during the WHOTS-18 cruise. Times when the CTD rosette was in the water are identified between solid and dashed black lines.	92
6.36	The contour of zonal currents (ms^{-1}) from the Ship Oscar Sette Ocean Surveyor narrowband 75 kHz shipboard ADCP as a function of time and depth, during the WHOTS-19 cruise. Times when the CTD rosette was in the water are identified between solid and dashed black lines.	93

6.37	Contours of meridional currents (ms^{-1}) from the Ship Oscar Sette Ocean Surveyor narrowband 75 kHz shipboard ADCP as a function of time and depth, during the WHOTS-19 cruise. Times when the CTD/rosette was in the water are identified between the solid and dashed black lines.	93
6.38	Mean current profiles during shipboard ADCP (cyan: zonal, magenta: meridional) versus moored 300 kHz ADCP (blue: zonal, red: meridional) intercomparisons from HOT-316 through HOT-329. Moored minus shipboard ADCP differences shown in dotted lines (blue: zonal, red: meridional) . .	94
6.39	Mean current profiles during shipboard ADCP (cyan: zonal, magenta: meridional) versus moored 600 kHz ADCP (blue: zonal, red: meridional) intercomparisons from HOT-316 through HOT-329. Moored minus shipboard ADCP differences shown in dotted lines (blue: zonal, red: meridional) . .	95
6.40	Horizontal velocity data (ms^{-1}) during WHOTS-18 from the VMCMs at 10 m depth (first and second panel) and at 30 m depth (third and fourth panel)	96
6.41	GPS Latitude (upper panel) and longitude (lower panel) time series from the WHOTS-18 deployment.	97
6.42	The power spectrum of latitude (upper panel) and longitude (lower panel) for the WHOTS-18. . .	98
6.43	Scatter plots of ADCP tilt and distance of the buoy to its anchor for the 300 kHz (left panel) and the 600 kHz ADCP deployments (right panel, blue circles). The red line is a quadratic fit to the median tilt calculated every 0.2 km distance bins.	99

List of tables

2.1	Scientific personnel on Ship Oscar Sette during the WHOTS-18 deployment cruise.	4
2.2	CTD stations occupied during the WHOTS-18 cruise (Datetime is in mm/dd/yyyy hh:mm)	5
2.3	Configuration of the Ocean Surveyor 75kHz ADCP on board the Ship Oscar Sette during the WHOTS-18 cruise	5
2.4	Scientific personnel on Ship Oscar Sette during the WHOTS-19 deployment cruise.	6
2.5	CTD stations during the WHOTS-19 cruise (WHOTS-18 mooring recovery). Datetime is in UTC (mm/dd/yy hh:mm).	6
2.6	Configuration of the Ocean Surveyor 75kHz ADCP on board the Ship Oscar Sette during the WHOTS-19 cruise	7
3.1	WHOTS-18 MicroCAT and SBE-56 Temperature Sensor Information.	9
3.2	WHOTS-18 mooring C-T and ADCP Instruments recovery information. All times are in UTC (mm/dd/yy hh:mm:ss). Sea-Bird 37 Serial Number (SN).	11
3.3	WHOTS-18 mooring ADCP deployment and configuration information. All times are in UTC (mm/dd/yy hh:mm:ss).	12
3.4	WHOTS-18 mooring ADCP recovery information. All times are in UTC (mm/dd/yy hh:mm:ss).	12
4.1	The precision of salinity measurements of secondary lab standards.	16
4.2	ADCP record times (UTC mm/dd/yy hh:mm:ss) for the Narrow Band 75 kHz ADCP during the WHOTS-18 cruise	19
4.3	ADCP record times (UTC mm/dd/yy hh:mm:ss) for the Narrow Band 75 kHz ADCP during the WHOTS-19 cruise	20
5.1	WHOTS-18 MicroCAT temperature sensor calibration dates and sensor drift during deployments; <i>SN = Sea-Bird Serial Number; PDC = Pre-Deployment Calibration; PRC = Post-Recovery Calibration; TSA = Temperature Sensor's Annual Drift during WHOTS-18 ; N. depth = Nominal deployment depth</i>	21
5.2	Pressure bias of MicroCATs with pressure sensors for WHOTS-18. <i>SN = Sea-bird Serial Number; BBD = Bias Before Deployment (dbar); BAR = Bias After Recovery (dbar)</i>	22
5.3	Specifications of the ADCP's used for the WHOTS-18 mooring.	30
5.4	Results from the WHOTS-18 pre-deployment 300 kHz ADCP compass field calibration procedure. <i>SCE = Single Cycle Error (°); DCE = Double Cycle Error (°); LD_SCE = Largest Double + Single Cycle Error (°); RMS_RE = RMS of 3rd Order and Higher + Random Error (°); OE = Overall Error (°); PM_STD = Pitch, Mean and St. Deviation (°); RM_STD = Roll, Mean and St. Dev. (°)</i>	39
5.5	Results from the WHOTS-18 pre-deployment 600 kHz ADCP compass field calibration procedure. See acronyms on Table 5.4	39
5.6	ADCP record times (UTC mm/dd/yyyy, hh:mm:ss) during WHOTS-18 deployment	42
5.7	Record times (UTC mm/dd/yy hh:mm) for the VMCMs at 10 m and 30 m during the WHOTS-18 deployment	49
5.8	GPS record times (UTC mm/dd/yy hh:mm) during WHOTS-18	54

In 2003, Robert Weller (Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution [WHOI]), Albert Plueddemann (WHOI), and Roger Lukas (The University of Hawaii [UH]) proposed to establish a long-term surface mooring at the Hawaii Ocean Time-series (HOT) Station ALOHA ($22^{\circ}45'N$, $158^{\circ}W$) to provide sustained, high-quality air-sea fluxes and the associated upper ocean response as a coordinated part of the HOT program, and as an element of the global array of ocean reference stations supported by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's (NOAA) Office of Climate Observation.

With support from the NOAA and the National Science Foundation (NSF), the WHOI HOT Site (WHOTS) surface mooring has been maintained at Station ALOHA since August 2004. This project aims to record long-term, high-quality air-sea fluxes as a coordinated part of the HOT program and contribute to the goals of observing heat, freshwater, and chemical fluxes at a site representative of the oligotrophic North Pacific Ocean. The approach is to maintain a surface mooring outfitted for meteorological and oceanographic measurements at a site near Station ALOHA by successive mooring turnarounds. These observations will be used to investigate air-sea interaction processes related to climate variability.

The original mooring system is described in the mooring deployment/recovery cruise reports [Plueddemann *et al.*, 2006, Whelan *et al.*, 2007, Whelan *et al.*, 2008, Whelan *et al.*, 2010, Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2022, Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2024]. Briefly, a Surlyn foam surface buoy is equipped with meteorological instrumentation, including two complete Air-Sea Interaction Meteorological (ASIMET) systems, measuring air and sea surface temperatures, relative humidity, barometric pressure, wind speed and direction, incoming shortwave and long wave radiation, and precipitation [Hosom *et al.*, 1995, Colbo and Weller, 2009]. Complete surface meteorological measurements are recorded every minute, as required to compute air-sea fluxes of heat, freshwater, and momentum. Each ASIMET system also transmits hourly averages of the surface meteorological variables via the Argos satellite system. The mooring line is instrumented to collect time series of upper ocean temperature, velocity, and salinity coincident with the surface forcing record. This mooring includes conductivity, salinity and temperature recorders, two Vector Measuring Current Meters (VMCMs), and two Acoustic Doppler current profilers (ADCPs). See the WHOTS-18 mooring diagram in the Fig. 1.1.

The subsurface instrumentation is located to resolve the temporal variations of shear and stratification in the upper pycnocline to support the study of mixed layer entrainment. Experience with moored profiler measurements near Hawaii suggests that Richardson number estimates over 10 m scales are adequate. Salinity is essential to the stratification, as salt-stratified barrier layers are observed at HOT and in the region [Kara *et al.*, 2000]. Hence, we use Sea-Bird SeaCATs and MicroCATs with vertical separation ranging from 5 to 20 m to measure temperature and salinity. We use two ADCPs made by Teledyne RD Instruments to obtain current profiles across the entrainment zone and in the mixed layer zone. Both ADCPs are in an upward-looking configuration, one is at 125 m, using 4 m bins, and the other is at 47.5 m using 2 m bins. To provide near-surface velocity (where ADCP estimates are less reliable), we deploy two Vector Measuring Current Meters (VMCMs). The nominal mooring design is a balance between resolving extremes versus the typical annual cycling of the mixed layer [Plueddemann *et al.*, 2006, Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2007]. A pair of Sea-Bird SeaCATs (SBE-16) or MicroCATs (SBE-37) have been included since the WHOTS-9 deployment (June 2012) to measure near-bottom temperature and salinity.

The WHOTS-18 mooring was deployed on July 24, 2022 (WHOTS-18 cruise) and was recovered on June 19, 2023 (WHOTS-19 cruise). The cruises were aboard the R/V Oscar Elton Settle. The WHOTS-19 mooring was deployed

WHOTS 18 PO Mooring

2.7 m Surlyn Foam Buoy with
(2) IMET systems (1 Sonic WND) with Iridium Telemetry,
XEOS Melo, Xeos Rover (2), SBE 39 AT, Lascar AT/RH
VAISALA WXT 530, NOAA PMEL PCO2, SAMI, SBE 16,
MAX. DIA. BUOY WATCH CIRCLE = 4.4 N.Miles
Position: 22 46 N, 157 54 W

Fig. 1.1: WHOTS-18 mooring design

on June 17, 2023, during the [WHOTS-19 cruise](#) and was recovered on June 06, 2024.

This report documents and describes the oceanographic observations made on the WHOTS-18 mooring for nearly eleven months and from shipboard measurements during the two cruises when the mooring was deployed and recovered. Sections [II](#) and [III](#) include a detailed description of the cruises and the mooring, respectively. Sampling and processing procedures of the hydrographic casts, thermosalinograph, and shipboard ADCP data collected during these cruises are described in Section [IV](#). Section [V](#) includes the processing procedures for the data collected by the moored instruments: [MicroCATs](#), [Moored ADCPs](#) and [VMCM](#). Plots of the resulting data and preliminary analysis are presented in Section [VI](#).

Description of the WHOTS-18 Mooring Cruises

2.1 WHOTS-18 Cruise: WHOTS-18 Mooring Deployment

The Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution Upper Ocean Processes Group (WHOI/UOP) , with the UH group's assistance, conducted the 18 deployment of the WHOTS mooring on board the Oscar Elton Settle during the WHOTS-18 cruise between July 22 and July 27, 2022. The WHOTS-18 mooring was deployed at Station 52 on July 24, 2022, 02:17 UTC at 22 40.002'N, 157 56.793'W, and the WHOTS-17 mooring were recovered on July 25, 2022. The scientific personnel that participated during the cruise are listed in [Table 2.1](#).

Table 2.1: Scientific personnel on Ship Oscar Sette during the WHOTS-18 deployment cruise.

Name	Title or Function	Affiliation
Plueddeman, Albert	Chief Scientist	WHOI
Graham, Raymond	Research Associate	WHOI
Llanos, Nico	Senior Engineering Assistant	WHOI
Fitzgerald, Dan	Marine Electronics Technician	UH
Harris, James	Student Assistant	UH
Maloney, Kelsey	Scientific Research Volunteer	UH
Howins, Noah	Undergraduate Volunteer	UH
Penunuri, Alexander	Graduate Student	CU
Conner, Kyle	Graduate Student	UH
Rohrer, Tully	Research Associate	UH

The UH group conducted shipboard oceanographic observations during the cruise. A complete description of these operations can be found in [[Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2022](#)].

A Sea-Bird CTD (conductivity, temperature, and depth) system was used measure T, S, and O₂ profiles during CTD casts. The time, location, and maximum CTD pressure for each profile are listed in [Table 2.2](#). Nine CTD casts were conducted during the WHOTS-18 cruise. CTD profile data were collected at Station 50 (near the WHOTS-17 buoy) and Station 52 (near the WHOTS-18 buoy). A test cast was conducted at Station 20 offshore of Makaha, HI, to an approximate depth of 1501 m to test three acoustic releases (two to be used in the WHOTS-18 mooring and one backup) were attached to the rosette frame for function testing. Four CTD yo-yo casts were conducted to obtain profiles for comparison with subsurface instruments on the WHOTS-18 mooring after deployment, and four yo-yo casts were performed for comparison with the WHOTS-17 mooring before recovery. The yo-yo casts were started about 0.25 nm from the buoys with varying drift during each cast, and consisted of 5 up-down cycles between near the surface and 203 to 210 m. The first set of T, C and O₂ sensors displayed bad data during various casts, apparently due to problems with the cable termination, but the second sensors set displayed good data.

Between 3 and 4 water samples were taken from all casts, except from Station 52 casts 2, 3 and 4, in which the pylon failed to communicate with the CTD. These samples were analyzed for salinity at UH and used to calibrate the CTD conductivity sensors.

Table 2.2: CTD stations occupied during the WHOTS-18 cruise
 (Datetime is in mm/dd/yyyy hh:mm)

Station/cast	Date	In-water Time	Location	Maximum pressure (dbar)
20/1	7/23/2022	04:30	21°28.286'N, 158°21.342'W	1501
50/1	7/24/2022	16:04	22°46.021'N, 157°56.186'W	208
50/2	7/24/2022	20:14	22°46.224'N, 157°56.091'W	208
50/3	7/24/2022	23:57	22°46.006'N, 157°56.014'W	204
50/4	7/25/2022	04:06	22°46.068'N, 157°56.001'W	210
52/1	7/26/2022	16:13	22°39.682'N, 157°59.152'W	203
52/2	7/26/2022	20:06	22°39.836'N, 157°59.066'W	203
52/3	7/27/2022	00:10	22°40.087'N, 157°59.123'W	206
52/4	7/27/2022	04:13	22°40.192'N, 157°59.041'W	203

Also, continuous ADCP and near-surface thermosalinograph data were obtained while underway.

The R/V Oscar Elton Settle was equipped with a TRDI Ocean Surveyor 75 kHz ADCP, set to function in broadband and narrowband configurations. The configuration information is shown in Table 2.3. The ADCP used input from a SAMOS gyrometer and Furuno GP 150, a GPS receiver, to establish the ship's heading and attitude.

Table 2.3: Configuration of the Ocean Surveyor 75kHz ADCP on board the Ship Oscar Sette during the WHOTS-18 cruise

Parameters	OS75BB	OS75NB
Sample interval (s)	300	300
Number of bins	80	55
Bin Length (m)	8	16
Transducer depth (m)	5	5
Blanking length (m)	8	8

Near-surface temperature and salinity data during the WHOTS-18 cruise were acquired from the thermosalinograph (TSG) system installed on the NOAA Ship Oscar Sette. The sensors were sampling water from the continuous seawater system running through the ship, and were comprised of one thermosalinograph model SBE-21 (SN 3168) and a micro-thermosalinograph 17 model SBE-45 (SN 0290), both with (internal) temperature and conductivity sensors located in the ship's chemistry lab, about 70 m from the hull intake; and an SBE-38 (SN266) external temperature sensor located at the entrance of the water intake. All instruments recorded data every second. The water intake is located at the bow of the ship, forward from the starboard side bow thruster at a depth of 3m. The system has a flow meter in the chemistry lab, showing a flow rate of about 1.1 liter/minute during the cruise. Only the SBE-45 has a debubbler. Salinity water samples were taken every 8 hours from the exhaust in the Chemistry lab using 0.25 liter glass bottles, measured in the UH lab and used to correct for any drift in the thermosalinograph conductivities.

2.2 WHOTS-19 Cruise: WHOTS-18 Mooring Recovery

The WHOI/UOP Group conducted the mooring turnaround operations during the WHOTS-19 cruise between June 15, and June 22, 2023. The WHOTS-19 mooring was deployed at Station 50 on June 17, 2023, 02:59 UTC at 22 46.002°N, 157 53.768°W, and the WHOTS-18 mooring was recovered on June 19, 2023, 17:49 UTC. The scientific personnel that participated during the cruise are listed in [Table 2.4](#).

Table 2.4: Scientific personnel on Ship Oscar Sette during the WHOTS-19 deployment cruise.

Name	Title or function	Affiliation
Plueddeman, Albert	Chief Scientist	WHOI
Bigorre, Sebastian	Research Specialist	WHOI
Graham, Raymond	Senior Engineering Assistant	WHOI
Llanos, Eduardo	Senior Engineering Assistant	WHOI
Santiago-Mandujano, Fernando	Research Associate	UH
Fitzgerald, Dan	Marine Electronics Technician	UH
Rohrer, Tully	Research Associate	UH
Maloney, Kelsey	Scientific Research Volunteer	UH
Adkison, Camille	Graduate Student	UH
Dale, Elizabeth	Technician	WHOI

The UH group conducted the shipboard oceanographic observations during the cruise. A complete description of these operations is available in the WHOTS-19 cruise report [[Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2024](#)]

A Sea-Bird CTD system was used to measure T, S, and O₂ profiles during CTD casts. The time, location, and maximum CTD pressure for each profile are listed in [Table 2.5](#).

Five CTD casts were conducted during the WHOTS-19 cruise from June 16 through June 19. CTD profile data were collected at Station 20 (in transit to the WHOTS mooring) and Station 52 (near the WHOTS-18 buoy). The cast at Station 20 was ~1500 m deep, and three acoustic releases (two to be used in the WHOTS-19 mooring and one backup) were attached to the rosette frame for function testing. Four CTD yo-yo casts were conducted to obtain profiles for comparison with subsurface instruments from WHOTS-18 mooring before recovery. The yo-yo casts started at about 0.25 nm from the buoys with varying drifts during each cast, and they consisted of 5 updown cycles near the surface and 200 to 215 m. CTD modulo errors started appearing during casts 3 and 4, indicating problems in communication between the CTD and the deck box. The number of modulo errors considerably increased at the start of casts conducted near the WHOTS-19 mooring, and those casts were aborted. The errors persisted after re-terminating the CTD wire connection and even after replacing the CTD with our spare CTD. We suspect the problem was in the CTD wire or the slip-rings. We were not able to conduct CTD casts near the WHOTS-19 mooring because of this problem.

Between 2 and 4 water samples were taken from all casts. These samples were analyzed for salinity at UH and used to calibrate the CTD conductivity sensors.

Table 2.5: CTD stations during the WHOTS-19 cruise (WHOTS-18 mooring recovery). Datetime is in UTC (mm/dd/yy hh:mm).

Station/cast	Date	In-water Time	Location	Maximum pressure (dbar)
20/1	6/16/2023	07:01	21°28.052'N, 158°21.087'W	1489
52/1	6/18/2023	16:05	22°40.680'N, 157°58.892'W	215
52/2	6/18/2023	20:02	22°40.888'N, 157°58.803'W	203
52/3	6/19/2023	00:05	22°40.707'N, 157°58.954'W	202
52/4	6/19/2023	05:22	22°41.226'N, 157°58.574'W	200

Also, continuous ADCP and near-surface thermosalinograph data were obtained while underway.

The NOAA Ship Oscar Sette was equipped with a TRDI Ocean Surveyor 75 kHz ADCP, set to function in broadband and narrowband configurations. The configuration information is shown in [Table 2.6](#). The ADCP used input from a SAMOS gyrometer and Furuno GP 170, a GPS receiver, to establish the ship's heading and attitude.

Table 2.6: Configuration of the Ocean Surveyor 75kHz ADCP on board the Ship Oscar Sette during the WHOTS-19 cruise

Parameters	OS75BB	OS75NB
Sample interval (s)	300	300
Number of bins	80	55
Bin Length (m)	8	16
Transducer depth (m)	5	5
Blanking length (m)	8	8

Near-surface temperature and salinity data during the WHOTS-19 cruise were acquired from the thermosalinograph (TSG) system installed on the NOAA Ship Oscar Sette. The sensors were sampling water from the continuous seawater system running through the ship, and were comprised of one thermosalinograph model SBE-21 (SN 3168) and a micro-thermosalinograph model SBE-45 (SN 0290), both with (internal) temperature and conductivity sensors located in the ship's chemistry lab, about 70 m from the hull intake; and an SBE-38 (SN 212) external temperature sensor located at the entrance of the water intake. All instruments recorded data every 17 second. The water intake is located at the ship's bow, forward from the starboard side bow thruster at a depth of 3 m. The system has a flow meter in the chemistry lab, showing a flow rate of about 1.1 liter/minute during the cruise. Only the SBE-45 has a debubbler. Salinity water samples were taken every 8 hours from the exhaust in the Chemistry lab using 0.25 liter glass bottles, measured in the UH lab and used to correct for any drift in the thermosalinograph conductivities.

Description of WHOTS-18 Mooring

The WHOTS-18 mooring, deployed on July 24, 2022, from R/V Oscar Elton Settle, was outfitted with two complete sets of Air-Sea Interaction Meteorological (ASIMET) sensors on the buoy and underneath subsurface instruments from 7 to 155 m depth, and near the bottom. See [Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2022, Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2024] for a complete description of the buoy. The WHOTS-18 was recovered on June 19-20 2023.

The buoy used during the WHOTS-18 deployment cruise was equipped with a variety of surface and subsurface instruments to ensure comprehensive data collection across multiple environmental parameters.

3.1 Surface Components

- **Two Loggers** (System 1 and System 2) with IDs 7 and 8.
- **Two Iridium Satellite Systems** for communication, with IMEI numbers 30023406326740 and 300234063345500.
- **Two Relative Humidity and Air Temperature (HRH) Sensors**, IDs 704 and 749, mounted at 230 cm and 233 cm above the deck.
- **Two Barometric Pressure Recorders (BPR)**, IDs 211 and 501, mounted at heights of 237 cm and 238 cm.
- **Two Wind Sensors (WND)**, IDs 221 and 343, mounted at 265 cm and 264 cm, respectively, from RM Young.
- **Two Precipitation Sensors (PRC)**, IDs 215 and 216, mounted at 253 cm and 254 cm.
- **Longwave Radiation Sensors (LWR)**, IDs 209 and 210, mounted at 280 cm.
- **Shortwave Radiation Sensors (SWR)**, IDs 504 and 209, also mounted at 280 cm.
- **Sea Surface Temperature (SST) Sensors**, IDs 1834 and 1841, located at -155 cm.
- **A Xeos Melo GPS** with IMEI 300034012129060.
- **Two Xeos Rover GPS Units** with IDs 787 and 859, and IMEI numbers 300434063359170 and 300434063297420.
- **A Vaisala WXT-530 Multi-variable Sensor** (ID 201) measuring temperature, humidity, pressure, wind, and precipitation, mounted at 267 cm.
- **A Sea-Bird SBE39AT Temperature Sensor** (ID 5272), mounted at 233 cm.
- **A Lascar Sensor** (ID 18), mounted at 197 cm.

3.2 Subsurface Instrumentation

- A pCO₂ System (ID 23), employing an equilibration tube, by Battelle MAPCO₂, mounted at 155 cm.
- A CTD Sensor (ID 7202), mounted at 155 cm, using an SBE-16.
- An Oxygen Sensor (ID 1780), mounted at 155 cm.
- A Fluorometer (ID 2676), mounted at 155 cm.
- A SAMI-2 pH Sensor (ID 82), mounted at 155 cm.
- A Xeos Kilo Transmitter at 160 cm, with IMEI 300234067205440.
- An Airmar Stand-alone Sensor (ID 274), mounted at 233 cm.

Five internally logging Sea-Bird SBE-56 temperature sensors were bolted to the buoy hull's underside, measuring sea surface temperature (SST). The SBE-56 sensors measured SST every 60 seconds at different depths ranging between 80-110cm below the buoy deck. Two SBE-37 MicroCATs were at 1.55m measuring at every 300s (See [Table 3.1](#)).

Table 3.1: WHOTS-18 MicroCAT and SBE-56 Temperature Sensor Information.

Instrument	SN	Depth (m)	Sample Interval (sec)
SBE-56	6411	0.80	60
SBE-56	7413	0.80	60
SBE-56	7414	0.95	60
SBE-56	7415	0.80	60
SBE-56	7412	0.80	60
MicroCAT	1834	1.55	300
MicroCAT	1841	1.50	300

Instrumentation provided by UH for the WHOTS-18 mooring included 18 SBE-37 Microcats, and two upward-looking RDI Workhorse ADCPs, transmitting in 300 kHz and 600 kHz, respectively. The Microcats all measured temperature and conductivity, with eight of them measuring pressure. All MicroCATs were deployed with antifoulant capsules. In addition to the buoy instrumentation, WHOI provided two Vector Measuring Current Meters (VMCMs), two deep Microcats (SBE-37) installed near the bottom of the mooring, and all required subsurface mooring hardware. In addition, a 69 kHz Vemco acoustic receiver was included in the mooring to detect the presence of sharks tagged with acoustic transmitters

The [Fig. 3.1](#) provides a listing of the WHOTS-18 subsurface instrumentation at their nominal depths on the mooring, along with serial numbers, sampling rates, and other pertinent information. A cold water spike was induced to the UH MicroCATs before deployment ([Fig. 3.1](#)) and after recovery [Table 3.2](#) by placing an ice pack in contact with their temperature sensor to check for any drift in their internal clock. To produce a spike in the ADCP data, each instrument's transducer was rubbed gently by hand for 20 seconds ([Table 3.3](#), and [Table 3.4](#)).

SN	Instrument	Depth (m)	Pressure SN	Sample Interval (sec)	Start Logging Date	Cold Spike Begin	Cold Spike End	Time in Water
3617	MicroCAT	7	N/A	180	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:30:00	07/23/22 19:37:00
33	VMCM	10	N/A	60	07/17/2022 22:25:00	07/23/2022 19:34:00*	N/A	07/23/22 19:35:00
6893	MicroCAT	15	N/A	60	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:30:00	07/23/22 19:33:00
6894	MicroCAT	25	N/A	60	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:30:00	07/23/22 19:29:00
135915	Acoustic Receiver **	25	N/A	N/A	07/01/2022 19:00:00	N/A	N/A	07/23/22 19:29:00
42	VMCM	30	N/A	60	07/17/2022 21:52:00	07/23/2022 19:24:00*	N/A	07/23/22 19:26:00
6895	MicroCAT	35	N/A	60	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:30:00	07/23/22 19:22:00
6896	MicroCAT	40	N/A	60	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:30:00	07/23/22 19:17:00
6887	MicroCAT	45	2651319	75	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:30:00	07/23/22 19:12:00
1825	600 kHz ADCP	47.5	N/A	600	07/23/2022 00:40:00	07/23/2022 00:40:00	See Table 3.3	07/23/22 20:13:00
6897	MicroCAT	50	N/A	60	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:30:00	07/23/22 20:16:00
6888	MicroCAT	55	N/A	60	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:30:00	07/23/22 20:20:00
6899	MicroCAT	65	N/A	60	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:30:00	07/23/22 20:17:00
3616	MicroCAT	75	N/A	180	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:30:00	07/23/22 20:15:00
3634	MicroCAT	85	N/A	180	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:30:00	07/23/22 20:20:00
3670	MicroCAT	95	5701	240	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:30:00	07/23/22 20:23:00
6885	MicroCAT	105	N/A	180	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:30:00	07/23/22 21:28:00
6890	MicroCAT	120	2651322	75	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:30:00	07/23/22 21:08:00
4891	300 kHz ADCP	125	N/A	600	07/23/2022 00:40:00	07/23/2022 00:40:00	See Table 3.3	07/23/22 21:33:00
6888	MicroCAT	135	3418745	75	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:30:00	07/23/22 21:40:00
6891	MicroCAT	155	2651323	75	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/23/2022 00:30:00	07/23/22 21:38:00
12241	MicroCAT	39 m off	2153123	300	07/23/2022 23:59:00	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/24/2022 00:01:49	07/24/22 00:01:49
11391	MicroCAT	39 m off	2146837	300	07/23/2022 23:59:00	07/23/2022 00:00:00	07/24/2022 00:01:49	07/24/22 00:01:49

Fig. 3.1: WHOTS-18 mooring subsurface instrument deployment information. All times are in UTC

Table 3.2: WHOTS-18 mooring C-T and ADCP Instruments recovery information. All times are in UTC (mm/dd/yy hh:mm:ss). Sea-Bird 37 Serial Number (SN).

Depth (m)	Sea-Bird Serial #	Time out of water	Time of Spike	Time of End Spike	Time Logging Stopped	Samples Logged	Data Quality
7	3617	06/20/23 03:54:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:43:00	06/21/23 15:10:40	72872	Good
15	6893	06/20/23 03:58:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:43:00	06/21/23 18:36:00	358223	Good
25	6894	06/20/23 04:02:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:43:00	06/21/23 19:18:00	358181	Good
35	6895	06/20/23 04:27:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:43:00	N/A	0	No data
40	6896	06/20/23 04:25:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:43:00	06/21/23 20:52:30	358087	Good
45	6887	06/20/23 02:20:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:43:00	06/21/23 20:32:00	174638	Good
47.5	ADCP 1825	06/16/23 02:16:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:43:00	02/10/23	28858	Failed on 02/10/23
50	6897	06/20/23 02:20:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:43:00	06/21/23 16:33:00	358346	Good
55	6898	06/20/23 02:14:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:43:00	06/21/23 18:53:10	479208	Good
65	6899	06/20/23 02:10:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:43:00	06/21/23 18:54:10	358346	Good
75	3618	06/20/23 02:11:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:43:00	06/21/23 22:24:30	159809	Good
85	3634	06/20/23 02:10:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:43:00	06/21/23 05:21:20	159951	Good
95	3670	06/20/23 02:08:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:43:00	06/21/23 19:31:50	119813	Good
105	6889	06/20/23 02:07:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:43:00	06/21/23 02:59:20	383760	Good
120	6890	06/20/23 02:04:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:43:00	06/20/23 22:58:30	383567	Good
125	ADCP 4891	06/20/23 02:00:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:43:00	01/24/23	26654	Failed on 01/24/23
135	6888	06/20/23 02:03:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:43:00	06/21/23 06:05:40	383945	Good
155	6891	06/20/23 01:56:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:43:00	06/21/23 08:44:20	175204	Large C-offset on 11/15/22
39 mab	12241	06/19/23 21:35:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:40:00	06/21/23 16:42:00	96129	Good
39 mab	11391	06/19/23 21:35:00	06/20/23 06:08:00	06/20/23 06:40:00	06/21/23 18:33:45	96127	Good

Table 3.3: WHOTS-18 mooring ADCP deployment and configuration information. All times are in UTC (mm/dd/yy hh:mm:ss).

-	ADCP S/N 1825	ADCP S/N 4891
Frequency (kHz)	600	300
Number of Depth Cells	25	30
Depth Cell Size (m)	2 m	4 m
Pings per Ensemble	80	40
Time per Ensemble (min)	10 min	10 min
Time per Ping (sec)	2 sec	4 sec
Time of First Ping	07/23/22, 00:40:00	07/22/22, 23:59:30
Transducer 1 Spike Time	07/23/22, 00:41:00	07/23/22, 00:20:00
Transducer 2 Spike Time	07/23/22, 00:41:15	07/23/22, 00:20:15
Transducer 3 Spike Time	07/23/22, 00:41:30	07/23/22, 00:20:30
Transducer 4 Spike Time	07/23/22, 00:41:45	07/23/22, 00:20:45
Ice Spike Time Begin	07/23/22, 00:50:00	07/23/22, 00:50:00
Ice Spike Time End	07/23/22, 01:20:00	07/23/22, 01:20:00
Time in Water	07/23/22, 20:13:00	07/23/22, 20:23:00
Depth (m)	47.5 m	125 m

Table 3.4: WHOTS-18 mooring ADCP recovery information. All times are in UTC (mm/dd/yy hh:mm:ss).

-	ADCP S/N 1825	ADCP S/N 4891
Frequency (kHz)	600	300
Number of Depth Cells	25	30
Depth Cell Size (m)	2 m	4 m
Pings per Ensemble	80	40
Time per Ensemble (min)	10 min	10 min
Time in Water	07/23/22, 20:13:00	07/23/22, 21:33:00
Time out of Water	06/20/23, 02:16:00	06/20/23, 02:00:00
Depth (m)	47.5 m	125 m

Both the 300 kHz ADCP at 125 m and the 600 kHz ADCP at 47.5 m were found not pinging upon recovery, with data indicating they stopped recording on January 24, 2023, and February 10, 2023, respectively. In both cases, the likely cause of failure was power loss due to corrosion of the bulkhead connectors. The data recorded before the failures were of good quality, although the 600 kHz ADCP had some near-surface side-lobe interference.

The RDI 300 kHz Workhorse Sentinel ADCP, SN 4891, was deployed at 125 m with transducers facing upwards with an additional external battery pack. This instrument was set to ping at 4-second intervals for 160 seconds every 10 minutes, and the burst sampling was designed to minimize aliasing by occasional large ocean swell orbital motions. The bin size was set for 4 m. The first ensemble was on 07/22/2012 at 23:45:49, and the last was on 02/10/2023 at 10:33:12 (see more [Table 3.3](#), [Table 3.4](#), and [WHOTS-18 300 kHz - Serial 4891](#) for more configuration). This instrument also measured temperature.

The RDI 600 kHz Workhorse Sentinel ADCP, SN 1825, was deployed at 47.5 m with transducers facing upwards with an additional external battery pack. The instrument was set to ping at 2-second intervals for 160 seconds every 10 minutes, and the burst sampling was designed to minimize aliasing by occasional large ocean swell orbital motions. The bin size was set for 2 m. The first ensemble was on 07/22/2022 at 23:48:56, and the last was on 01/24/2022 at 16:16:39 (see [Table 3.3](#), [Table 3.4](#), and [WHOTS-18 600 kHz - Serial 1825](#) for more configuration). This instrument also measured temperature.

The two VMCMs, SN 2042 and 2032, were deployed at 30 m and 10 m depth, respectively. The instruments were prepared for deployment by the WHOI/UOP group and set to sample at 1-minute interval. These instruments also measured temperature.

All WHOTS-18 instruments were successfully recovered; recovery information for the C-T instruments is shown in [Table 3.2](#). Most of the instruments had some degree of biofouling, with the most substantial fouling near the surface. The fouling extended down to the ADCP at 125 m, although it was minor at that level.

All MicroCATs except one were in good condition and had their antifoulant capsules. The MicroCAT SN 3617 at 7 m was recovered with a bent conductivity sensor guard

After recovery and before stopping recording, a bag of ice was placed in contact with each MicroCAT temperature sensor, to produce a spike in the data as a reference point to check the instrument's clock. The data from all instruments were downloaded at UH. [Table 3.2](#) has an initial evaluation of the data quality; more details are in [MicroCAT Data Processing Procedures](#), and [MicroCAT Data](#).

WHOTS (18-19) Cruise Shipboard Observations

The hydrographic profile observations made during the WHOTS cruises were obtained with a Sea-Bird CTD package with dual temperature, salinity, and oxygen sensors. This CTD was installed on a rosette-sampler with 5 L Niskin sampling bottles for calibration water samples. Furthermore, the ship Oscar Sette came equipped with a thermosalinograph system that provided a continuous depiction of the near-surface layer's temperature and salinity. Horizontal currents over the depth range of 30-700 m were measured from the shipboard 75 kHz Ocean Surveyor (OS75) ADCP (narrowband) with a vertical resolution of 16m for the WHOTS-18 and WHOTS-19 cruises. Broadband mode for the OS75 provided additional current data over the range upper 200 m with a vertical resolution of 8m.

Data gaps occurred when the system was shut down temporarily during communications with the acoustic releases used for the moorings during both cruises. Periods of missing data between 300 and 450 m in the broadband ADCP were apparent due to the lack of scattering material in the water.

4.1 Conductivity, Temperature, and Depth (CTD) Profiling

Continuous measurements of temperature, conductivity, dissolved oxygen, and pressure were made with the UH Sea-Bird SBE-9/11Plus CTD underwater units #1487 and #1506 during WHOTS-18 and WHOTS-19 cruises respectively. The CTD was equipped with an internal Digiquartz pressure sensor and pairs of external temperature, conductivity, and oxygen sensors.

Each temperature-conductivity sensor pair used a Sea-Bird TC duct, which circulated seawater through independent pump and plumbing installations. The CTD configuration also included two oxygen sensors, installed in the plumbing for each sensor set. In both cruises, the CTD was mounted in a vertical position in the lower part of a rosette sampler, with the sensors' water intakes located at the bottom of the rosette.

The package was deployed on a conducting cable, which allowed for real-time data acquisition and display. The deployment procedure consisted of lowering the package to approximately 10 dbar and waiting until the CTD pumps started operating. The CTD was then raised until the sensors were close to the surface to begin the CTD cast. The time and position of each cast were obtained via a GPS connection to the CTD deck box. Four salinity samples were taken on each cast for calibration of the conductivity sensors.

4.1.1 Data Acquisition and Processing

CTD data were acquired at the instrument's highest sampling rate of 24 samples per second. Digital data were stored on a laptop computer, and, for redundancy, the analog signal was recorded on a separate computer using a sound card and Audacity (TM) software. Backups of CTD data were made onto USB storage cards.

The raw CTD data were quality controlled and screened for spikes described in the WHOTS Data Report 1 [Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2007]. Data alignment, averaging, correction, and reporting were done as described in [Tupas *et al.*, 1993]. Spikes in the data occur when the CTD samples the disturbed water of its wake. Therefore, the downcast samples were rejected when the CTD was moving upward or when its acceleration exceeded 0.5 m s⁻² in magnitude. The data were subsequently averaged into 2-dbar pressure bins after calibrating the CTD conductivity with the bottle salinities.

The data were additionally screened by comparing the T-C sensor pairs. These differences permitted the identification of problems with the sensors. The data from only one T-C pair, whichever was deemed most reliable, is reported here. Only data from the downcast are reported, as wake effects from the rosette commonly contaminate upcast data.

Temperature is reported on the ITS-90 scale. Salinity and all derived units were calculated using the UNESCO (1981) routines; salinity is reported in the Practical Salinity(SA) scale (PSS-78). Oxygen is reported in $\mu\text{mol/kg}$.

4.1.2 CTD Sensor Calibration and Corrections

4.1.2.1 Pressure

The pressure calibration strategy for CTD pressure transducers #153702 and #154451 used during WHOTS-18 and WHOTS-19 cruises respectively employed a high-quality quartz pressure transducer as a transfer standard. Periodic recalibrations of this lab standard were performed with a primary pressure standard. The only corrections applied to the CTD pressures were a constant offset determined when the CTD first enters the water on each cast. Also, a span correction determined from bench tests on the sensor against the transfer standard was applied. These procedures and corrections are thoroughly documented in the HOT-2022 data report [Fujieki *et al.*, 2024].

4.1.2.2 Temperature/Conductivity

Sea-Bird SBE-3-Plus temperature and SBE 4C conductivity transducers were used during WHOTS-18 and -19 cruises. These sensors' history and performance have been monitored during HOT cruises, and calibrations and drift corrections applied during WHOTS cruises are thoroughly documented in the HOT-2022 data report [Fujieki *et al.*, 2024].

4.1.2.3 Dissolved Oxygen

Sea-Bird SBE-43 oxygen sensors were used during the WHOTS-18 and -19 cruises. There were no oxygen samples taken during the cruise to calibrate the CTD sensors. The WHOTS-18 oxygen data were calibrated using calibration coefficients obtained during the HOT-305 cruise, as this was the only available option since these sensors had not been used previously. The HOT cruise CTD empirical calibration was performed using oxygen water samples and the procedure from [Owens and Millard, 1985]. See [Tupas *et al.*, 1996] for details on these calibrations procedures. The oxygen data from WHOTS-19 were calibrated using calibration coefficients obtained during the HOT-343 cruise conducted on 15-22 August 2023, after the WHOTS-19 cruise, which used the same oxygen sensor.

4.2 Water Sampling and Analysis

4.2.1 Salinity

Salinity samples were collected by a rosette sampler during CTD casts at selected depths during WHOTS-18 and -19, and then sub-sampled in 250 ml glass bottles. The top of each bottle and thimble were thoroughly dried before being tightly capped to prevent water from being trapped between the cap or thimble and the bottle’s mouth. It has been observed that residual water trapped in this way increases its salinity due to evaporation, and it can leak into the sample when the bottle is opened for measuring. Samples from each cruise were measured after the cruise in the UH laboratory using a Guildline Autosol 8400B SN 73647 for WHOTS-18 and WHOTS-19. International Association for Physical Sciences of the Ocean (IAPSO) standard seawater samples were measured to standardize the Autosol, and samples from a large batch of “secondary standard” (substandard) seawater were measured after every 24-48 samples to detect drift in the Autosol. Standard deviations of the secondary standard measurements were less than ± 0.001 for WHOTS-18 and -19 cruises [Table 4.1](#).

The substandard water was collected by a rosette sampler from 1020 m at station ALOHA during HOT cruises and drained into a 50-liter Nalgene plastic carboy. In the laboratory, the water was then thoroughly mixed in a glass carboy for 20 minutes by manually shaking, rolling, and tilting the carboy vigorously, after which a 2-inch protective layer of white oil was added on top to deter evaporation. The substandard water was allowed to stand for approximately three days before it was used and was stored in the same temperature-controlled room as the Autosol, protecting it from the light with black plastic bags to inhibit biological growth. Substandard seawater batch #72 was prepared on April 11-13, 2022, and it was used for WHOTS-18. The batch #74 was prepared on July 17-19, 2023, and it was used for WHOTS-19.

Samples from WHOTS-18 were measured on August 4, 2022, while samples from WHOTS-19 were measured on August 29, 2023. [Table 4.1](#) presents the precision measurements of the secondary sub-standards. For more details about the salinity measurements, please refer to [WHOTS-18 Salinity Measurements](#) and [WHOTS-19 Salinity Measurements](#).

Table 4.1: The precision of salinity measurements of secondary lab standards.

Cruise	Mean Salinity +/- SD	# Samples	Substandard Batch	IAPSO Batch
WHOTS-18	34.4930 \pm 0.0005	3	72	P164
WHOTS-19	34.4954 \pm 0.0004	5	74	P166

4.3 Thermosalinograph Data Acquisition and Processing

4.3.1 WHOTS-18 Cruise

Near-surface temperature and salinity data during the WHOTS-18 cruise were acquired from the thermosalinograph (TSG) system installed on the NOAA Ship Oscar Sette. The sensors were sampling water from the continuous seawater system running through the ship. They comprised one thermosalinograph model SBE-21 (SN 3168) and a micro-thermosalinograph model SBE-45 (SN 0290), both with (internal) temperature and conductivity sensors located in the ship’s chemistry lab, about 70 m from the hull intake; and an SBE-38 (SN 266) external temperature sensor located at the entrance of the water intake. All instruments recorded data every second. The water intake is located at the ship’s bow, forward from the starboard side bow thruster at a depth of 3 m. The system has a flow meter in the chemistry lab, showing a flow rate of about 1.1 liters/minute during the cruise. Only the SBE-45 has a debubbler. Salinity water samples were taken every 8 hours from the exhaust in the Chemistry lab using 0.25-liter glass bottles, to be measured in the UH lab to correct any drift in the thermosalinograph conductivities.

4.3.1.1 Temperature Calibration

External temperature data from the SBE-38 sensor (last calibrated at Sea-Bird on December 7, 2020) were used to measure the seawater temperature. These data were compared to the data collected during CTD casts.

4.3.1.2 Nominal Conductivity Calibration

Data from the SBE-45 conductivity and temperature sensors were used to calculate the intake seawater salinity. These sensors were last calibrated at Sea-Bird on December 7, 2020. All conductivity data from the thermosalinograph were nominally calibrated with coefficients from this calibration. However, all the final salinity data reported here were calibrated against bottle data, as explained below.

4.3.1.3 Data Processing

Daily files containing navigation data recorded every second were concatenated with the thermosalinograph data. The thermosalinograph data were then screened for gross errors, with upper and lower bounds of 18°C and 35°C for temperature and 3 and 6 Siemens/m for conductivity. There were 28 points outside the valid temperature range and no points outside the valid conductivity range.

A 5-point running median filter was used to detect one- or two-point temperature and conductivity glitches in the thermosalinograph data. Glitches in temperature and conductivity detected by the 5-point median filter were immediately replaced by the median. Threshold values of 0.3°C for temperature and 0.1 Siemens/m for conductivity were used for the median filter. After running the filter, there were 332 internal temperature, 391 external temperature, and 40 conductivity points replaced with the median.

A 3-point triangular running mean filter was used to smooth the temperature and conductivity data after passing the glitch detection.

The thermosalinograph aboard the Ship Oscar Sette was set to record data every second. Data were visually scanned to flag spikes likely caused by contamination due to the introduction of bubbles to the flow-through system during transits or rough conditions. Of 456,895 data points, 86,670 conductivity data points were flagged as bad.

4.3.1.4 Bottle salinity and CTD Salinity Comparisons

The thermosalinograph salinity was calibrated by comparing it to bottle salinity samples drawn from a water intake next to the thermosalinograph every 8 hours throughout the cruise. Of the twenty thermosalinograph bottles sampled, bottle #8 was identified as a conductivity outlier and was discarded from the analysis. Samples were analyzed as described in [Water Sampling and Analysis](#). The comparison was made in conductivity to eliminate the effects of temperature. The conductivity of each bottle sample was computed using the salinity of the bottle, thermosalinograph temperature, and a pressure of 10 dbar, which includes the pressure of the flow-through system's pump.

Salinity samples were drawn from the flow-through system, located less than 0.5 m from the SBE-45. Consequently, there should be virtually no delay between when the water passes through the thermosalinograph and sampled. A 90-second average centered on the sample draw time was chosen for processing purposes.

In order to make the comparison in conductivity units, the CTD conductivity was calculated using the 4 dbar downcast CTD salinity, the internal thermosalinograph temperature, and a pump pressure of 10 dbar. There were nine CTD casts conducted during WHOTS-18 while the thermosalinograph was running. Casts 4 and 8 were removed from the analysis as temperature and conductivity outliers.

A cubic spline was fit to the time series of the differences between the bottle and TSG conductivity, and a correction was obtained for the TSG conductivities. Salinity was calculated using these corrected conductivities, the thermosalinograph temperatures, and 10 dbar pressure. After applying corrections, the mean difference between the bottle and thermosalinograph salinities was -0.0001 psu with a standard deviation of 0.0033 psu. The mean CTD - thermosalinograph difference was -0.0011 psu with a standard deviation of 0.0040 psu.

4.3.1.5 CTD Temperature Comparisons

There were 9 CTD casts conducted during WHOTS-18, one of which was a test cast offshore Honolulu (Station 20) and four at Station 52 (WHOTS-18), and four at Station 50 (WHOTS-17), respectively. The 3 dbar downcast CTD temperature data from those casts were used to compare with the thermosalinograph data at the time of the casts. This comparison gives an estimate of the quality of the thermosalinograph measurements.

Of the nine casts, casts #4 and 8 were identified as temperature outliers after comparing them against the thermosalinograph data and removed from the analysis. The mean difference between the CTD and the internal temperature sensor was -0.1274°C , with a standard deviation of $\pm 0.0448^{\circ}\text{C}$.

4.3.2 WHOTS-19 Cruise

Near-surface temperature and salinity data during the WHOTS-19 cruise were acquired from the thermosalinograph (TSG) system installed on the NOAA Ship Oscar Sette. The sensors were sampling water from the continuous seawater system running through the ship, and comprised one thermosalinograph model SBE-21 (SN 3168) and a micro-thermosalinograph model SBE-45 (SN 0290), both with (internal) temperature and conductivity sensors located in the ship's chemistry lab, about 70 m from the hull intake; and an SBE-38 (SN 212) external temperature sensor located at the entrance of the water intake. All instruments recorded data every second. The water intake is located at the bow of the ship, forward from the starboard side bow thruster at a depth of 3 m. The system has a flow meter in the chemistry lab, showing a flow rate of about 1.1 liter/minute during the cruise. Only the SBE-45 has a debubbler. Salinity water samples were taken every 8 hours from the exhaust in the Chemistry lab using 0.25 liter glass bottles, to be measured in the UH lab to correct for any drift in the thermosalinograph conductivities.

4.3.2.1 Temperature Calibration

External temperature data from the SBE-38 sensor (last calibrated at Sea-Bird on December 8, 2022) were used to measure the seawater temperature. These data were compared to the data collected during CTD casts.

4.3.2.2 Nominal Conductivity Calibration

Data from the SBE-45 conductivity and temperature sensors were used to calculate the intake seawater salinity. These sensors were last calibrated at Sea-Bird on November 11, 2020. All conductivity data from the thermosalinograph were nominally calibrated with coefficients from this calibration. However, all the final salinity data reported here were calibrated against bottle data, as explained below.

4.3.2.3 Data Processing

Daily files containing navigation data recorded every second were concatenated with the thermosalinograph data. The thermosalinograph data were then screened for gross errors, with upper and lower bounds of 18°C and 35°C for temperature and 3 and 6 Siemens m^{-1} for conductivity. There were 0 points outside the valid temperature range and no points outside the valid conductivity range.

A 5-point running median filter was used to detect one- or two-point temperature and conductivity glitches in the thermosalinograph data. Glitches in temperature and conductivity detected by the 5-point median filter were immediately replaced by the median. Threshold values of 0.3°C for temperature and 0.1 Siemens m^{-1} for conductivity were used for the median filter. After running the filter, there were 0 internal temperature, 0 external temperature, and 5 conductivity points replaced by the median. A 3-point triangular running mean filter was used to smooth the temperature and conductivity data after passing the glitch detection.

The thermosalinograph aboard the Ship Oscar Sette was set to record data every second. Both thermosalinographs exhibited a number of conductivity and temperature glitches due to air going into the plumbing.

Data were visually scanned to flag spikes likely caused by contamination due to the introduction of bubbles to the flow-through system during transits or rough conditions. Of 534647 data points, 11014 conductivity data points were flagged as bad.

4.3.2.4 Bottle salinity and CTD Salinity Comparisons

The thermosalinograph salinity was calibrated by comparing it to bottle salinity samples drawn from a water intake next to the thermosalinograph every 8 hours throughout the cruise. Of the twenty thermosalinograph bottles sampled, no bottles were identified as a conductivity outlier. Samples were analyzed as described in [Water Sampling and Analysis](#). The comparison was made in conductivity to eliminate the effects of temperature. The conductivity of each bottle sample was computed using the salinity of the bottle, thermosalinograph temperature, and a pressure of 10 dbar, which includes the pressure of the flow-through system’s pump.

Salinity samples were drawn from the flow-through system, located less than 0.5 m from the SBE-45. Consequently, there should be virtually no delay between when the water passes through the thermosalinograph and sampled. A 90-second average centered on the sample draw time was chosen for processing purposes.

In order to make the comparison in conductivity units, the CTD conductivity was calculated using the 4 dbar downcast CTD salinity, the internal thermosalinograph temperature, and a pump pressure of 10 dbar. There were five CTD casts conducted during WHOTS-19 while the thermosalinograph was running. No casts were removed from the analysis as temperature and conductivity outliers.

A cubic spline was fit to the time series of the differences between the bottle and TSG conductivity, and a correction was obtained for the TSG conductivities. Salinity was calculated using these corrected conductivities, the thermosalinograph temperatures, and ten dbar pressure. After applying corrections, the mean difference between the bottle and thermosalinograph salinities was less than 1 mpsu with a standard deviation of 0.0044 psu. The mean CTD - thermosalinograph difference was 0.0077 psu with a standard deviation of 0.0150 psu.

4.3.2.5 CTD Temperature Comparisons

There were five CTD casts conducted during WHOTS-19, one of which was a test cast offshore Honolulu (Station 20), and four at Station 52 (WHOTS-19). The 3 dbar downcast CTD temperature data from those casts were used to compare with the thermosalinograph data at the time of the casts. This comparison gives an estimate of the quality of the thermosalinograph measurements. Of the five casts, none was identified as temperature outliers after comparing it against the thermosalinograph data and removed from the analysis. The mean difference between the CTD and the internal temperature sensor was -0.2114 °C, with a standard deviation of ± 0.0183 °C.

4.4 Shipboard ADCP

4.4.1 WHOTS-18 Deployment Cruise

Currents were measured for the cruise duration over the depth range of 30-700 m with a 75 kHz RDI Ocean Surveyor (OS75) ADCP working in narrowband mode with a vertical resolution of 16 m and broadband mode with a vertical resolution of 8 m. The system yielded good data [[Santiago-Mandujano et al., 2022](#)] during operations near the WHOTS-17 and WHOTS-18 moorings. The broadband system only recorded good data in the upper 200 m. The times of the datasets from the OS75 kHz are shown in [Table 4.2](#).

Table 4.2: ADCP record times (UTC mm/dd/yy hh:mm:ss) for the Narrow Band 75 kHz ADCP during the WHOTS-18 cruise

WHOTS-18	OS75nb	OS75bb
File starting time	07/22/22 23:24:47	07/22/22 23:24:47
File ending time	07/27/22 20:59:44	07/27/22 29:59:44

4.4.2 WHOTS-19 Deployment Cruise

Currents were measured for the duration of the cruise over the depth range of 30-700 m with a 75 kHz RDI Ocean Surveyor (OS75) ADCP working in narrowband mode with a vertical resolution of 16 m, and in broadband mode with vertical resolution of 8 m. The system yielded good data (see [Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2024]) during operations near the WHOTS-18 and WHOTS-19 moorings. The broadband system only recorded good data in the upper 200 m. The times of the datasets from the OS75 kHz are shown in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: ADCP record times (UTC mm/dd/yy hh:mm:ss) for the Narrow Band 75 kHz ADCP during the WHOTS-19 cruise

WHOTS-19	OS75nb	OS75bb
File starting time	06/16/23 02:12:16	06/16/23 02:12:16
File ending time	06/22/23 18:17:13	06/22/23 18:17:13

Moored Instrument Observations

5.1 MicroCAT Data Processing Procedures

Each moored MicroCAT temperature, conductivity, and pressure (when installed) was calibrated at Sea-Bird before their deployment and after their recovery on the dates shown in [Table 5.1](#). The internally-recorded data from each instrument were downloaded on board the ship after the mooring recovery. The nominally-calibrated data were plotted for a visual assessment of the data quality. The data processing included checking the internal clock data against external event times, pressure sensor drifts correction, temperature sensor stability, and conductivity calibration against CTD data from casts conducted near the mooring during HOT and WHOTS cruises. The detailed processing procedures are described in this section. Individual configurations for the MicroCATs on the WHOTS-18 mooring are detailed in [WHOTS-18 MicroCAT - Headers](#).

Table 5.1: WHOTS-18 MicroCAT temperature sensor calibration dates and sensor drift during deployments; *SN* = *Sea-Bird Serial Number*; *PDC* = *Pre-Deployment Calibration*; *PRC* = *Post-Recovery Calibration*; *TSA* = *Temperature Sensor's Annual Drift during WHOTS-18* ; *N. depth* = *Nominal deployment depth*

N. depth (m)	SN	PDC	PRC	TSA (mdegC)
7	3617	17-Nov-21	09-Aug-23	-0.10
15	6893	13-Nov-21	06-Sep-23	0.34
25	6894	04-Nov-21	09-Aug-23	-0.99
40	6896	24-Nov-21	08-Aug-23	-0.15
45	6887	19-Nov-21	15-Aug-23	0.03
50	6897	04-Nov-21	09-Aug-23	-1.20
55	6898	02-Dec-21	08-Aug-23	-0.35
65	6899	13-Nov-21	08-Aug-23	-0.16
75	3618	04-Nov-21	06-Sep-23	-1.07
85	3634	13-Nov-21	06-Sep-23	-0.21
95	3670	19-Nov-21	06-Sep-23	1.46
105	6889	10-Nov-21	09-Aug-23	0.95
120	6890	19-Nov-21	09-Aug-23	-0.49
135	6888	19-Nov-21	15-Aug-23	0.04
155	6891	19-Nov-21	09-Aug-23	0.33
4710	11391	10-Mar-22	22-Oct-23	0.15
4710	12241	25-Feb-22	24-Oct-23	0.07

5.1.1 Internal Clock Check and Missing Samples

Before the WHOTS-18 mooring deployment and after its recovery (before the data logging was stopped), the MicroCATs temperature sensors were placed in contact with an ice pack to create a spike in the data, to check for any problems with their internal clocks, and for possible missing samples (Table 3.2). The cold spikes deployment were detected by a sudden decrease in temperature. For all the instruments, the clock time of this event matched the time of the spike (within the sampling interval of each instrument) correctly. No missing samples were detected for any of the devices.

5.1.2 Pressure Drift Correction and Pressure Variability

Some MicroCATs used in the moorings were outfitted with pressure sensors (Table 3.2). Biases were detected in the pressure sensors by comparing the on-deck pressure readings (which should be zero for standard atmospheric pressure at sea level of 1029 mbar) before deployment and after recovery. Table 5.2 shows the magnitude of the bias for each of the sensors before and after deployment. To correct this offset, a linear fit between the initial and final on-deck pressure offset as a function of time was obtained and subtracted from each sensor. Fig. 5.1 shows the linearly corrected pressures measured by the MicroCATs located above 200 m during the WHOTS-18 deployment. For all these sensors, the mean difference from the nominal instrument pressure (based on the deployed depth) was less than 0.6 dbar. The standard deviation of the pressure for the duration of the record was less than 1 dbar for all sensors, with the deeper sensors showing a slightly larger standard deviation. The range of variability for all sensors was about ± 3 dbar.

The causes of pressure variability can be several, including density variations in the water column above the instrument; horizontal dynamic pressure (not only due to the currents but also due to the motion of the mooring); mooring position [Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2007].

Table 5.2: Pressure bias of MicroCATs with pressure sensors for WHOTS-18. SN = Sea-bird Serial Number; BBD = Bias Before Deployment (dbar); BAR = Bias After Recovery (dbar)

Depth (m)	SN	BBD(dbar)	BAR(dbar)
45	6887	0.00	-0.19
95	3670	-1.28	-1.80
105	6889	0.02	-0.12
120	6890	0.02	-0.05
135	6888	-0.07	-0.17
155	6891	-0.02	-0.09
4710	11391	0.65	1.87
4710	12241	0.47	1.10

5.1.3 Temperature Sensor Stability

The MicroCAT temperature sensors were calibrated at Sea-Bird before and after each deployment, and their annual drift evaluations based on these calibrations are shown in Table 5.1. These values turned out to be insignificant (not higher than 0.002 °C) for all sensors. Comparisons between the MicroCAT and CTD data from casts conducted near the mooring during HOT cruises confirmed that the rest of the moored instruments' temperature drift was insignificant. The temperatures from the two MicroCATs (SN 11391 and SN 12241) deployed near the bottom were drift corrected. Fig. 5.7 (upper panel) shows the temperature differences between both instruments before and after the correction. After the correction, the temperature differences were in the ± 0.001 °C range.

Temperature comparisons between one of the WHOTS-18 near-surface MicroCAT (SN 1834) and the four SBE-56 surface temperature sensors in the buoy hull Table 3.1 are shown in Fig. 5.2. All the SBE-56 instruments returned full records, and none of them show any obvious bias compared to the Microcat measurements.

In addition to the Sea-Bird temperature sensors, there were additional temperature sensors in the VMCMs (at 10 and 30 m) and in the ADCPs (at 47.5 m and 125 m). Comparisons with the temperatures from adjacent MicroCATs were conducted to evaluate the temperatures from those sensors.

Fig. 5.1: Linearly corrected pressures from MicroCATs between 7 and 155 m during WHOTS-18 deployment. The horizontal dashed line is the sensor’s nominal pressure, based on deployed depth. The text on the left (right) side of the figure indicates the mean (standard deviation) of the difference between each instrument’s pressure and nominal pressure.

Fig. 5.2: The temperature difference between MicroCAT SN 7212 at 1 m, and near-surface temperature sensors SN 7212 (top panel), 7213 (second panel), 7214 (third panel), and 7215 (bottom panel), during the WHOTS-18 deployment. The light blue line is a 24-hour running mean of the differences.

5.1.3.1 Comparisons with VMCM and ADCP temperature sensors

The upper panel of Fig. 5.3 shows the difference between the 10-m VMCM and the 7-m MicroCAT temperatures during WHOTS-18, after adding a 0.0239°C offset correction to the VMCM. The offset was the mean difference between the uncorrected VMCM and the 7-m MicroCAT data. Also shown for comparison in the middle panel of the figure are the corrected VMCM temperature differences from the 15 m MicroCAT. The lower panel shows the temperature fluctuations in the differences between the 7 and 15-m MicroCATs, which seem to be around zero.

Temperature differences between the 30-m VMCM and the temperatures from adjacent MicroCATs at 25 and 35-m during WHOTS-18 are shown in Fig. 5.4 after adding a 0.0192°C offset correction to the VMCM. The offset was the mean difference between the uncorrected VMCM and the 25-m MicroCAT data. For comparison, the differences between the MicroCATs temperatures are also shown in the lower panel.

Temperature differences between the 47.5-m ADCP and the temperatures from adjacent MicroCATs at 45 and 50-m during WHOTS-18 are shown in Fig. 5.5. The ADCP failed and stopped collecting data on February 10, 2023 (see *Description of WHOTS-18 Mooring*). For comparison, the differences between the MicroCATs temperatures are also shown in the lower panel.

Temperature differences between the 125-m ADCP and the temperatures from adjacent MicroCATs at 120 and 135-m during WHOTS-18 are shown in Fig. 5.6. The ADCP failed and stopped collecting data on January 24, 2023 (see *Description of WHOTS-18 Mooring*). For comparison, the differences between the MicroCATs temperatures are also shown in the lower panel. It is difficult to assess the quality of the ADCP temperature from these comparisons. These sensors were located at the top of the thermocline, where we expect to find substantial temperature differences between adjacent sensors. However, an indication of the ADCP temperatures' quality is given in the upper panel plot, which shows temperatures fluctuating closely around zero.

5.1.4 Conductivity Calibration

The results of the Sea-Bird post-recovery conductivity calibrations indicated that some MicroCAT conductivity sensors experienced relatively large offsets from their pre-deployment calibration. These were qualitatively confirmed by comparing the mooring data against CTD data from casts conducted between 200 m and 5 km from the mooring during HOT cruises. The conductivity offsets are not apparent, and there may have been multiple causes (see [Freitag *et al.*, 1999] for a similar experience with conductivity cells during COARE). For some instruments, the offset was negative, caused perhaps by biofouling of the conductivity cell. In contrast, for others, the offset was positive, for reasons still unknown. A visual inspection of the instruments after recovery did not show any apparent signs of biofouling. There were no cell scourings reported in the post-recovery reviews at Sea-Bird.

Corrections of the MicroCATs conductivity data were conducted by comparing them against CTD data from profiles and yo-yo casts conducted near the mooring during HOT cruises and during deployment/recovery cruises. Casts led between 200 and 1000 m from the mooring were given extra weight in the correction compared to those conducted between 1 and 5 km away. Casts more than 5 km away from the mooring were not used. Given that the CTD casts are conducted at least 200 m from the mooring, CTD and MicroCAT data's alignment was done in density rather than in-depth. For cases where the alignment in density was not possible due to large conductivity offsets (causing unrealistic mooring density values), the alignment was done in temperature space. A cubic least-squares fit (LSF) to the CTD-MicroCAT differences against time was applied as a first approximation, and the corresponding correction was applied.

Some sensors had large offsets and noticeable variability that could not be explained by a cubic LSF (see below). For these sensors, a stepwise correction was applied to match the data to the available CTD cast data and then to use the differences between consecutive sensors to determine when the sensor started to drift. For instance, during periods of weak stratification, the conductivity difference between neighboring sensors A, B, and C could reach near-zero values, in particular for instruments near the surface, which are the ones most prone to suffer conductivity offsets. A sudden conductivity offset observed during this period between sensors A and B, but not between sensors A and C could indicate the beginning of an offset for sensor B.

Given that the most in-depth instruments on the mooring are less likely to be affected by biofouling and consequent sudden conductivity drift, the deep instruments served as an excellent reference to find any possible malfunction in the shallower ones. Therefore, the conductivity from the deepest instruments was corrected first, and the correction was continued sequentially upwards toward the shallower ones.

Fig. 5.3: The temperature difference between the 7-m MicroCAT and the 10-m VMCM (upper panel); between the 15-m MicroCAT and the 10-m VMCM (middle panel); and between the 7-m and the 15-m MicroCATs (lower panel) during the WHOTS-18 deployment. The light blue line is a 24-hour running mean of the differences.

Fig. 5.4: The temperature difference between the 25-m MicroCAT and the 30-m VMCM (upper panel); between the 30-m MicroCAT and the 40-m VMCM (middle panel); and between the 25-m and the 40-m MicroCATs (lower panel) during the WHOTS-18 deployment. The light blue line is a 24-hour running mean of the differences.

Fig. 5.5: The temperature difference between the 45-m MicroCAT and the 47.5-m ADCP (upper panel) (The ADCP stopped collecting data on 2023/2/10); between the 50-m MicroCAT and the 47.5-m ADCP (middle panel); and between the 45-m and the 50-m MicroCATs (lower panel) during the WHOTS-18 deployment. The light blue line is a 24-hour running mean of the differences.

Fig. 5.6: The temperature difference between the 120-m MicroCAT and the 125-m ADCP (upper panel) (the ADCP stopped collecting data on 2023/1/24); between the 135-m MicroCAT and the 125-m ADCP (middle panel); and between the 120-m and the 135-m MicroCATs (lower panel) during the WHOTS-18 deployment. The light blue line is a 24-hour running mean of the differences.

As a quality control to the conductivity corrections, the buoyancy frequency between neighboring instruments was calculated using finite differences. Over- or under-corrected conductivities yielded instabilities in the water column (negative buoyancy frequency) that were easy to detect and were not real when lasting for several days. Based on this, the conductivity correction of the corresponding sensors was revised.

Correction of the deep and the near-bottom MicroCATs' conductivities were done following similar procedures than for the shallow instruments, by comparing them against CTD data from near-bottom profiles conducted during HOT cruises (Fig. 5.7, bottom panel). After correction, the salinity differences between both instruments were in the ± 0.001 range.

Another characteristic of the offsets in the conductivity sensors is that their development is not always linear in time. Their behavior can be highly variable [Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2007]. The corrections applied to each of the conductivity sensors during WHOTS-18 are shown in Fig. 5.8 through Fig. 5.14. Most of the instruments had a drift of less than 0.02 Siemens/m for the duration of the deployment, corrected with a linear, cubic least-squares or stepwise fit. The instrument at 155 m had a large offset (0.5 Siemens/m) on November 15, 2022. Some of the instruments deployed above 120 m showed a negative drift starting a few months before the end of their record, apparently due to the anti-foulant expiration.

5.2 Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler

Two TRDI broadband Workhorse Sentinel ADCP's were deployed on the WHOTS-18 mooring. A 600 kHz ADCP was deployed at 47.5 m depth in the upward-looking configuration, and a 300 kHz ADCP was deployed at 125 m, also in the upward-looking configuration. The instruments were installed in aluminum frames and an external battery module to provide sufficient power for the intended period of deployment. The four ADCP beams were angled at 20° from the vertical line of the instrument. The 300 kHz ADCP was set to profile across 30 range cells of 4 m with the first bin centered at 6.23m from the transducer. The 600 kHz ADCP was set to profile across 25 range cells of 4 m with the first bin centered at 3.11m from the transducer. The specifications of the instrument are shown in Table 5.3.

Table 5.3: Specifications of the ADCP's used for the WHOTS-18 mooring.

Frequency (kHz)	Instrument	Model	Serial Number
300	TRDI Workhorse Sentinel	WHS300-I-UG86	4891
600	TRDI Workhorse Sentinel	WHS600-I	1825

5.2.1 Compass Calibrations

5.2.1.1 Pre-Deployment

Before the WHOTS-18 deployment, field calibration of the internal ADCP compass was performed at the University of Hawaii at Manoa on June 28, 2022 for 300 kHz and the 600 kHz instruments. Each instrument was mounted in the deployment cage with the external battery module and was located away from potential sources of magnetic field disturbances. The ADCP was mounted to a turntable, aligned with the magnetic north using a surveyor's compass. Using the built-in RDI calibration procedure, the instrument was tilted in one direction between 10 and 20 degrees and then rotated through 360 degrees at less than 5° per second. The ADCP was then tilted in a different direction, and a second rotation was made. Based on the results from the first two rotations, calibration parameters are temporarily loaded, and the instrument, tilted in a third direction, is rotated once more to check the calibration. Results from each pre-deployment field calibration are shown in Table 5.4 and Table 5.5 (Fig. 5.15 and Fig. 5.16).

Fig. 5.7: Temperature differences (top panel) and salinity differences (bottom panel) between MicroCATs #12241 and #11391 during WHOTS-18. The blue (red) lines are the differences before (after) correcting the data following the text's procedures.

Fig. 5.8: Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs from 1 to 7 meters during WHOTS-18.

Fig. 5.9: Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs from 15 to 25 meters during WHOTS-18

Fig. 5.10: Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs from 40 to 50 meters during WHOTS-18

Fig. 5.11: Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs from 55 to 75 meters during WHOTS-18.

Fig. 5.12: Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs from 85 to 105 meters during WHOTS-18.

Fig. 5.13: Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs from 120 to 155 meters during WHOTS-18

Fig. 5.14: Conductivity sensor corrections for MicroCATs at 4710 meters during WHOTS-18.

Table 5.4: Results from the WHOTS-18 pre-deployment 300 kHz ADCP compass field calibration procedure. *SCE* = *Single Cycle Error* (°); *DCE* = *Double Cycle Error* (°); *LD_SCE* = *Largest Double + Single Cycle Error* (°); *RMS_RE* = *RMS of 3rd Order and Higher + Random Error* (°); *OE* = *Overall Error* (°); *PM_STD* = *Pitch, Mean and St. Deviation* (°); *RM_STD* = *Roll, Mean and St. Dev.* (°)

(SN 4891)	SCE	DCE	LD_SCE	RMS_RE	OE	PM_STD	RM_STD
Before	4.24	0.69	4.93	0.19	4.14	0.12 ±0.60	17.00 ±0.58
After	0.13	0.15	0.28	0.32	0.24	0.02 ±0.60	1.99 ±0.84

Table 5.5: Results from the WHOTS-18 pre-deployment 600 kHz ADCP compass field calibration procedure. See acronyms on Table 5.4

(SN 1825)	SCE	DCE	LD_SCE	RMS_RE	OE	PM_STD	RM_STD
Before	4.22	0.20	4.42	0.11	4.25	13.32 ±0.57	-0.79 ±0.57
After	0.16	0.05	0.21	0.07	0.18	-1.41 ±0.53	-0.18 ±0.51

5.2.1.2 Post-Deployment

After the WHOTS-18 mooring was recovered, neither ADCP was able to ping, and the power pins on the bulkhead connectors were found to be corroded. Both units failed to communicate with a PC, so they were sent back for factory repair. The service report indicated that the issue was not with the instrument electronics, but rather with the corroded connectors. Unfortunately a post-cruise compass calibration could not be performed.

5.2.2 ADCP Configurations

Individual configurations for the two ADCP's on the WHOTS-18 mooring are detailed in [WHOTS-18 300 kHz - Serial 4891](#), and [WHOTS-18 600 kHz - Serial 1825](#). The salient differences for each of the ADCP's are summarized below.

5.2.2.1 300 kHz (SN/4891 - 125m)

The ADCP, set to a beam frequency of 300 kHz, was configured in a burst sampling mode consisting of 40 pings per ensemble to resolve low-frequency wave orbital motions. The interval between each ping was 4 seconds, so the ensemble length was 160 seconds. The interval between ensembles was 10 minutes. Data were recorded in earth coordinates, with a heading bias of 9.54° E due to magnetic declination. False targets, usually fish, were screened by setting the threshold maximum to 70 counts. Velocity data were rejected if the difference in echo intensity among the four beams exceeded this threshold.

5.2.2.2 600 kHz (SN/1825- 47.5m)

The ADCP, set to a beam frequency of 600 kHz, was configured in a burst sampling mode consisting of 80 pings per ensemble. The interval between each ping was 2 seconds, so the ensemble length was also 160 seconds. The interval between ensembles was 10 minutes. Data were recorded in earth coordinates with a heading bias of 9.54° E. The threshold maximum was also set to 70 counts. Velocity data were rejected if the difference in echo intensity among the four beams exceeded this threshold.

Fig. 5.15: Results of the pre-cruise compass calibration, conducted on June 28, 2022, for ADCP SN 4891 at the University of Hawai'i at Manoa. Unfortunately, a post-cruise compass calibration could not be performed due to corrosion of the bulkhead connectors following the cruise.

Fig. 5.16: Results of the pre-cruise compass calibration, conducted on June 28, 2022, for ADCP SN 1825 at the University of Hawai'i at Manoa. Unfortunately, a post-cruise compass calibration could not be performed due to corrosion of the bulkhead connectors following the cruise.

5.2.3 ADCP data processing procedures

Binary files output from the ADCP were read and converted to MATLAB™ binary files using scripts developed by [Eric Firing's ADCP lab](#). The beginning of the raw data files was truncated to a time after the mooring anchor was released to allow time for the anchor to reach the seabed and for the mooring motions that follow the anchor's impact on the seafloor to dissipate. The pitch, roll, and ADCP temperature were examined to pick reasonable times that ensured good data quality without unnecessarily discarding too much data (Fig. 5.17, Fig. 5.18). Truncation at the end of the data files was chosen to be the ensemble before the acoustic release signal was sent to avoid contamination due to the instrument's ascent. The times of the first ensemble from the raw data, deployments, and recovery time, along with the truncated records of both deployments, are shown in Table 5.6.

Fig. 5.17: temperature record from the 300 kHz adcp during whots-18 mooring (top panel). the bottom panel shows the beginning and end of the record, with the green vertical line representing the in-water time during deployment and out-of-water recovery time. the red line represents the anchor release and acoustic release trigger for deployment and recovery, respectively.

Table 5.6: ADCP record times (UTC mm/dd/yyyy, hh:mm:ss) during WHOTS-18 deployment

Activities	300 kHz	600 kHz
Raw file start	07/22/2022, 23:48:56	07/22/2022, 23:45:49
Raw file end	01/24/2023, 16:16:39	02/10/2023, 10:33:12
ADCP In water	07/23/2022, 21:33:00	07/23/2022, 20:13:00
Anchor over	07/24/2022, 02:17:00	07/24/2022, 02:17:00
Anchor release fired	06/19/2023, 17:49:00	06/19/2023, 17:49:00
ADCP on deck	06/20/2023, 02:00:00	06/20/2023, 02:16:00

Fig. 5.18: Same as Fig. 5.17, but for the 600 kHz ADCP.

5.2.3.1 ADCP Clock Drift

Upon recovery, a spike is normally produced in the ADCP data by gently rubbing each instrument's transducer by hand for 20 seconds (see [Table 3.4](#)) to compare the ADCP clocks with the ship's time server. Unfortunately, the clock on both ADCPs could not be evaluated because the instrument stopped working before recovery. Past deployments of the ADCP's suggest a 3-minute difference is not unusual. No drift corrections were made. However, this drift may be significant if the data are used for time-dependent analysis, such as tidal or spectrum analysis. A drift correction needs to be applied in those cases.

5.2.3.2 Heading Bias

As mentioned in the ADCP configuration section, the data were recorded in the earth coordinates. A heading bias, the angle between magnetic north and true north, can be included in the setup to obtain output data in true-earth coordinates. Magnetic variation was obtained from the [National Geophysical Data Center 'Geomag' calculator](#). A constant value is acceptable for a yearlong deployment because the change in declination is small, approximately $-0.02^{\circ}\text{year}^{-1}$ at the WHOTS location. A heading bias of 9.54° was entered in the setup of the WHOTS-18 ADCP's.

5.2.3.3 Speed of sound

Due to the constant proportionality between the Doppler shift and water speed, the speed of sound needs only be measured at the transducer head [[Firing, 1991](#)]. The sound speed used by the ADCP is calculated using a constant value of salinity (35) and the temperature recorded by the transducer temperature sensor of the ADCP. Using CTD profiles close to the mooring during HOT cruises, HOT-338 to 342, and from the WHOTS deployment/recovery cruises, the mean salinity at 125 dbar was 35.19 while the mean salinity at 47.5 dbar was 35.11. The mean ADCP temperature at 125 dbar was 22.11°C and 25.08°C at 47.5dbar ([Fig. 5.17](#), [Fig. 5.18](#), and [Fig. 5.19](#)). The mean sound velocity at 47.5 and 125 dbar was 1535.49ms^{-1} and 1529.42ms^{-1} , respectively.

5.2.3.4 Quality Control

Quality control of the ADCP data involved the thorough examination of the velocity, instrument orientation, and diagnostic fields to develop the basis of the QC flagging procedures. Details of the methods used can be found in the WHOTS Data Report 1 [[Santiago-Mandujano et al., 2007](#)]. The following QC procedures were applied to the WHOTS-18 deployment of ADCP data.

1. The first bin (closest to the transducer) is sometimes corrupted due to what is known as ringing. A period of time is needed for the sound energy produced during a transducer's transmit pulse to dissipate before the ADCP can adequately receive the returned echoes. This "blanking interval" is used to prevent useless data from being recorded. If it is too short, signal returns can be contaminated by the lingering noise from the transducer. The blanking interval is expressed as a distance. The default value of 1.76 m was used for the 300 kHz ADCP, whereas an interval of 0.88 m was used for the 600 kHz ADCP. As a result, bin one was flagged and replaced with *Not a Number (NaN)* in the quality-controlled dataset ([Fig. 5.20](#)).
2. For an upward-looking ADCP with a beam angle of 20° within range of the sea surface, the upper 6% of the depth range is contaminated with sidelobe interference [[Teledyne RD Instruments, 2011](#)]. This contamination results from the much stronger signal reflection from the sea surface than from scatters, overwhelming the sidelobe suppression of the transducer. Data quality is quantified using echo intensity, a measure of the backscattered echo's strength for each depth cell. With distance from the transducer sensor, echo intensity is expected to decrease. Sharp increases in echo intensity indicate contamination from surface reflection. Most of the data within the upper four bins ($\sim 14\%$ of the vertical range) were flagged. These top four bins range from about 15 m up to the sea surface.
3. The Janus configuration of four beams (along with instrument orientation) is used to resolve currents into their component earth-referenced velocities, providing a second estimate of the vertical velocity. The scaled difference between these estimates is defined as the error velocity, and it is useful for assessing data quality. Error velocities with an absolute magnitude more significant than 0.15ms^{-1} (value comparable to the standard deviation of observed horizontal velocities) were flagged and removed.
4. An indication of data quality for each ensemble is given by the "percent good" data indicator, which accompanies each beam for each bin. The use of the percent good indicator is determined by the coordinate

Sound Speed Profile (m/s) during WHOTS-18 Deployment 27-Jul-2022 to 17-Jun-2023 from HOT Stn 52 CTD casts and CTD casts during WHOTS-18/19 cruises

Fig. 5.19: Sound speed profile (top panel) during the deployment of the WHOTS-18 mooring from 2 dbar CTD data taken during regular HOT cruises and CTD profiles taken during the WHOTS-18 and -19 deployment cruises (individual casts marked with a red diamond). The bottom left panels show the sound velocity at a depth of the ADCP's (47.5 m and 125 m), with the mean sound velocity indicated with a dashed black line. The lower right panels show the temperature and salinity at each ADCP depth for the time series, with the mean temperatures indicated with blue lines and mean salinity indicated with red lines.

Fig. 5.20: Eastward velocity component for the 300 kHz (top panel) and the 600 kHz (bottom panel) ADCPs are showing the incoherence between depth bins 1 (red), 2 (green), and 3 (blue).

transformation mode used during the data collection. For profiles transformed into earth coordinates, the percent good field shows the percentage of pings that could be used to create the earth coordinate velocities. The percent good fields show the percentage of data made using 4 and 3 beam solutions in each depth cell within an ensemble and the percentage that was rejected due to failing one of the criteria set during the instrument setup (see *WHOTS-18 300 kHz - Serial 4891*). Data were flagged when data in each depth cell within an ensemble made from 3 or 4 beam solutions was 20% or less.

5. Data were rejected using correlation magnitude, which is the pulse-to-pulse correlation (in ping returns) for each depth cell. Correlation magnitude represents how the shape of the received signal corresponds to the outgoing signal for each ping. If at least three of the beams exhibited a correlation magnitude more significant than 64 counts for a given bin, the profile could be transformed into earth coordinates. Low correlation magnitudes may indicate sudden changes in particle density or sudden changes in ADCP tilt. More research is needed at this time into relationships between ADCP tilt and correlation magnitude. If any beam had a correlation magnitude of 20 counts or less, that data point was flagged.
6. Histograms of raw vertical velocity data and partially cleaned data from the ADCP (Fig. 5.21 and Fig. 5.22) and the WHOTS Data Report 1 [Santiago-Mandujano *et al.*, 2007] showed vertical velocities larger than expected, some exceeding 1ms^{-1} . Recall that the instruments' burst sampling (4-second intervals for the 300 kHz and 2-second intervals for the 600 kHz, for 160 seconds every 10 minutes) was designed to minimize aliasing by occasional large ocean swell orbital motions *Description of WHOTS-18 Mooring*, and therefore are not the source of these speeds in the data. These significant vertical speeds are possibly fish swimming in the beams based on the histograms of the partially cleaned data; depth cells with an absolute value of vertical velocity greater than 0.3ms^{-1} were flagged.

Fig. 5.21: Histogram of the vertical velocity of the 300 kHz ADCP for raw data (top panel) and enlarged for clarity (upper middle panel), and partial quality controlled data (lower middle panel) and enlarged for clarity (bottom).

7. A quality control routine known as ‘edgers’ identifies outliers in surface bins using a five-point median

Fig. 5.22: Same as Fig. 5.21, but for 600kHz ADCP.

differencing method. The median velocity from surface bins was calculated for each ensemble, and then a five-point running median of the surface bin median was calculated. This last median was then compared to individual velocity observations in the surface bins, and those differing by greater than 0.48ms^{-1} were flagged.

8. A 5-pole low pass Butterworth filter with a cutoff frequency of $0.25\frac{\text{cycles}}{\text{hour}}$ was used upon the time-series' length to isolate low-frequency flow for each bin independently. The low-frequency flow is then subtracted, giving a time series of high-frequency velocity component fluctuations for each bin. Data points were considered outliers when their values exceeded four standard deviations from the mean (for each bin) and were removed.
9. A median residual filter used a 7-point (70 minutes) median differencing method to define velocity fluctuations. A 7-point running median is calculated for each bin independently, and the result is subtracted out, giving time series of variations relative to the running median. Outliers higher than four standard deviations from the mean of the 7 points are flagged and removed for each bin.
10. Meticulous verification of all the quality control routines was performed through visual inspections of the quality-controlled velocity data. Two methods were utilized; time-series of u and v components for multiple bins were evaluated, and individual vertical profiles. The time-series methodology involved inspecting u and v components separately, five bins at a time, over 600 ensembles (100 hours). Any instance showing one bin behaving erratically from the other four bins was investigated further. If it seemed that there could be no reasonable rationale for the erratic points from the identified bin, the points were flagged. The intent of the inspection of vertical profiles of u and v components was to find entire profiles that were not aligned with neighboring profiles. Thirty u and v profiles were stacked at a time and were visually inspected for any anomalous data.

5.3 Vector Measuring Current Meter (VMCM)

Vector measuring current meters (VMCM) were deployed on the WHOTS-18 mooring at depths of 10 m and 30 m, serial numbers SN 2032 and 2042, respectively. VMCM data were processed by the WHOI/UOP group, and the record times are shown in [Table 5.7](#).

Table 5.7: Record times (UTC mm/dd/yy hh:mm) for the VMCMs at 10 m and 30 m during the WHOTS-18 deployment

Time Over	VMCM (SN 2042)	VMCM (SN 2032)
Deployment	07/23/22 19:26	07/23/22 19:35
Recovery	06/20/23 02:31	06/20/23 03:56

Daily (24 hours) moving averages of quality controlled 600 kHz ADCP data are compared to VMCM data interpolated to the ADCP ensemble times in the top panels of [Fig. 5.23](#) through [Fig. 5.26](#), and the difference is shown in the middle panels. The absolute value of the mean difference plus or minus one standard deviation is shown at the top of the middle panel. Velocities are not compared if greater than 80% of the ADCP data within a 24-hour average was flagged. The absolute value of mean differences for all deployments and both velocity components varied between 1.8 and 3.3cms^{-1} , with standard deviations between 1.3 and 2.6cms^{-1} . The VMCM data does not appear to degrade over time for any deployment. Propeller fouling would dampen measured VMCM velocity magnitudes, but a decrease in VMCM velocity magnitude than ADCP velocity magnitude with time is not observed.

5.4 Global Positioning System Receiver

Xeos Global Positioning System receiver (Melo-IMEI:300034012129060) and (Rover-IMEI:300434063359170) were attached to the buoy's tower top during the WHOTS-18 deployment ([Description of WHOTS-18 Mooring](#)). Data returns from the receiver were high ([Table 5.8](#)).

Fig. 5.23: A comparison of 30 m VMCM and ADCP U velocity for WHOTS-18. The top panel shows 24-hour moving averages of VMCM zonal (U) velocity at 30 m depth (red) and ADCP U velocity from the nearest depth bin to 30 m. The middle panel shows the U velocity difference, and the bottom panel shows the percentage of ADCP data within the moving average not flagged by quality control methods.

Fig. 5.24: Same as in Fig. 5.23 but for the meridional (V) velocity component.

Fig. 5.25: Same as in Fig. 5.23 but for the 10 m VMCM.

Fig. 5.26: Same as Fig. 5.25, but for the meridional (V) velocity component.

Table 5.8: GPS record times (UTC mm/dd/yy hh:mm) during WHOTS-18

Raw file	Xeos GPS (Melo)	Xeos GPS (Rover)
Start Time	07/24/22 03:09	05/18/22 00:01
End Time	06/19/23 04:39	06/19/23 00:02

During the WHOTS-18 cruise (WHOTS-18 mooring deployment, 24 July 2022), a high-pressure ridge far north of the Hawaiian Islands maintained a tight enough pressure gradient down across the region to produce moderate local trades, increasing by the end of the cruise. There was no measurable precipitation during the deployment or recovery times. Conditions during the WHOTS-18 deployment were favorable, with light ENE winds during the deployment. There were clear skies and no precipitation in the region, and small short-period wind waves.

Currents were nearly 1 kt to the west in the upper 200 m. This westward flow seemed to be associated with a high sea level north of Station ALOHA. A combination of internal semidiurnal and diurnal tides, along with near-inertial oscillations, were noticeable especially in vertical shear.

CTD casts conducted near the WHOTS-18 buoy (Station 52) after deployment (Fig. 6.3, Fig. 6.4, Fig. 6.5) displayed a subsurface salinity maximum between 60 and 80 dbar and a mixed layer 60 to 80 dbar deep.

During the WHOTS-19 cruise (WHOTS-18 mooring recovery, 19 June 2023), a high-pressure ridge far north of the Hawaiian Islands maintained a tight enough pressure gradient down across the region to produce moderate local trades, increasing by the end of the cruise. There was no measurable precipitation during the deployment or recovery times. Conditions during the WHOTS-19 deployment on June 16-17 were favorable. There were 15-16 kt winds from the east during the deployment and a westward current of nearly 0.5 kt near the surface. There were clear skies and no precipitation in the region, and there were small short-period wind waves.

Currents were predominantly to the northwest in the upper 200 m. This westward flow seemed to be associated with a high sea level north of Station ALOHA. A combination of internal semidiurnal and diurnal tides, along with near-inertial oscillations, were noticeable, especially in vertical shear.

CTD casts conducted near the WHOTS-18 buoy (Station 52) before recovery (Fig. 6.6, Fig. 6.7, Fig. 6.8) displayed a subsurface salinity maximum between 130 and 150 dbar and a mixed layer of about 40 dbar deep.

The temperature MicroCAT records during the WHOTS-18 deployment (Fig. 6.13 through Fig. 6.15) show noticeable seasonal variability in the upper 100 m. A temperature increase in January-February 2023 was evident in all the instruments. The salinity records (Fig. 6.17 through Fig. 6.19) do not show an apparent seasonal cycle, but a sudden drop in salinity was recorded in January 2023, with values mostly below 35 in the upper 40 m for the rest of the deployment. Another salinity drop was recorded by all the instruments after June 2023, reaching 34.5 values in the upper 95 m.

Fig. 6.25 through Fig. 6.27 show contours of the WHOTS-18 MicroCAT data in context with data from the previous 17 deployments. The seasonal cycle is evident in the temperature record, with record temperatures (higher than 26°C) in the summer of 2004, and again in 2014, 2015, 2017, 2019, and 2020. Salinities in the subsurface salinity maximum were relatively low during the first 6 years of the record, only to increase drastically after 2008 through 2015, with some lower salinity episodes in mid-2011 and early 2012. The salinity maximum extended to near the surface in early 2010, 2011, late 2012-early 2013, and February-March 2013. Salinities in the salinity minimum decreased after 2015, showing low salinities above 100 m in 2016, 2017, 2018, and reaching record low values (34.4) in July-August 2019 and July-September 2020. The salinities started to increase after 2021, reaching 35.4 values at the salinity maximum, and extending to the surface in October and November-December 2022. When plotted in $\sigma\theta$ coordinates (Fig. 6.27), the salinity maximum seems to be centered roughly between 24 and 24.5 $\sigma\theta$.

Records from the WHOTS-18 MicroCATs (Fig. 6.28) deployed near the bottom of the mooring (4710 m) detected temperature and salinity changes related to episodic ‘cold events’ apparently caused by bottom water moving between abyssal basins [Lukas *et al.*, 2001]. These events are being monitored by instruments at the ALOHA Cabled Observatory (ACO) [Howe *et al.*, 2011], a deep water observatory located at the bottom of Station ALOHA (about 6 nautical miles north from the WHOTS-18 anchor), since June 2011. Fig. 6.28 shows temperature and salinity records from the WHOTS-18 MicroCATs superimposed on the ACO data. The MicroCAT data agreed with the temperature decrease and the salinity variability registered by ACO instruments during a cold event in August 2022, and during minor events in October 2022 and late February 2023.

Fig. 6.31 through Fig. 6.33 shows the time series of the zonal, meridional, and vertical currents recorded with the moored ADCPs during the WHOTS-18 deployment. Fig. 6.29 shows the ADCP current components’ contours in context with data from the previous deployments. Despite the gaps in the data, an apparent variability is seen in the zonal and meridional currents, apparently caused by passing eddies. There have been periods of intermittent positive or negative zonal currents on top of this variability, for instance, during 2007-2008. The contours of the vertical current component show a transition in the magnitude of the contours near 47 m, indicating that the 300 kHz ADCP located at 126 m moves more vertically than the 600 kHz ADCP located at 47.5 m.

A comparison between the moored ADCP data and the shipboard ADCP data obtained during the WHOTS-18 cruise is shown in Fig. 6.34, and Fig. 6.35. A similar comparison during the WHOTS-19 cruise was not possible because both moored ADCPs stopped working before the mooring was recovered. The shipboard ADCP data during the WHOTS-19 cruise are shown in Fig. 6.36 and Fig. 6.37. Some differences were seen during the WHOTS-18 cruise comparisons, especially in the zonal component, maybe due to the mooring motion, which was not removed from the data. Comparisons between the available shipboard ADCP from HOT-339 to -342 cruises and the mooring data are shown in Fig. 6.38 through Fig. 6.39.

The Xeos-GPS receiver registered the WHOTS-18 buoy motion, and its positions are plotted in Fig. 6.41. The buoy remained predominantly around its intended deployment location, with noticeable variability both in latitude and longitude, particularly during the periods from November 2022 to March 2023. The power spectrum of these data Fig. 6.43 shows significant energy at the diurnal (K1) and semidiurnal (M2) tidal frequencies, indicating that tidal forces were a major driver of the buoy’s movement. Combining the buoy motion with the tilt (a combination of pitch and roll) from the ADCP data (Fig. 6.43) showed that the tilt increased as the buoy’s distance from the anchor increased. This was expected since the inclination of the cable increases as the buoy moves farther from the anchor.

6.1 CTD Profiling Data

Profiles of temperature, salinity, and potential density ($\sigma\theta$) from the casts obtained during the WHOTS-18 deployment cruise are presented in Fig. 6.1 through Fig. 6.5, together with the results of bottle determination of salinity. Fig. 6.6 through Fig. 6.8 shows the results of the CTD profiles during the WHOTS-19 cruise.

6.2 Thermosalinograph Data

Underway measurements of near-surface temperature and salinity from the thermosalinograph (TSG) system on board the R/V Oscar Sette cruise are presented in Fig. 6.9 and navigational data is shown in Fig. 6.10 for the WHOTS-18 cruise. TSG and navigational data during the WHOTS-19 cruise, on board the R/V Oscar Sette, are presented in Fig. 6.11 and Fig. 6.12, respectively.

Fig. 6.1: [Upper left panel] Profiles of CTD temperature, salinity, and potential density (σ_θ) as a function of pressure, including discrete bottle salinity samples (when available) for station 20 cast 1 during the WHOTS-18 cruise. [Upper right panel] Profiles of CTD salinity as a function of potential temperature, including discrete bottle salinity samples (when available) for station 20 cast 1 during the WHOTS-18 cruise. [Lower left panel] Same as in the upper left panel, but for station 50 cast 1. [Lower right panel] Same as in the upper right panel, but station 50 cast 1.

Fig. 6.2: [Upper panels] Same as in Fig. 6.1, but for station 50, cast 2. [Lower panels] Same as Fig. 6.1, but for station 50, cast 3.

Fig. 6.3: [Upper panels] Same as in Fig. 6.1, but for station 50, cast 4. [Lower panels] Same as in Fig. 6.1, but for station 52 cast 1.

Fig. 6.4: [Upper panels] Same as in Fig. 6.1, but for station 52, cast 2. [Lower panels] Same as in Fig. 6.1, but for station 52, cast 3.

Fig. 6.5: [Upper panels] Same as in Fig. 6.1, but for station 52, cast 4.

Fig. 6.6: [Upper left panel] Profiles of CTD temperature, salinity, and potential density (σ_θ) as a function of pressure, including discrete bottle salinity samples (when available) for station 20 cast 1 during the WHOTS-19 cruise. [Upper right panel] Profiles of CTD salinity as a function of potential temperature, including discrete bottle salinity samples (when available) for station 20 cast 1 during the WHOTS-19 cruise. [Lower left panel] Same as in the upper left panel, but for station 52 cast 1. [Lower right panel] Same as in the upper right panel, but station 52 cast 1.

Fig. 6.7: Upper panels] Same as in Fig. 6.6, but for station 52, cast 1. [Lower panels] Same as in Fig. 6.6, but for station 52, cast 3.

Fig. 6.8: Upper panels] Same as in Fig. 6.6, but for station 52, cast 4.

Fig. 6.9: Final processed temperature (upper panel), salinity (middle panel), and potential density (σ_θ) (lower panel) data from the continuous underway system onboard the R/V Hi'ialakai during the WHOTS-18 cruise. Temperature and salinity taken from 6-dbar CTD data (circles) and salinity bottle sample data (crosses) are superimposed. The dashed vertical red line indicates the period of occupation of Station ALOHA and the WHOTS site.

Fig. 6.10: Timeseries of latitude (upper panel), longitude (middle panel), and ship's speed (lower panel) during the WHOTS-18 cruise.

Fig. 6.11: Final processed temperature (upper panel), salinity (middle panel), and potential density (σ_θ) (lower panel) data from the continuous underway system onboard the R/V Oscar Sette during the WHOTS-19 cruise. Temperature and salinity were taken from 6-dbar CTD data (circles), and salinity bottle sample data (crosses) are superimposed. The dashed vertical red line indicates the period of occupation of Station ALOHA and the WHOTS site.

Fig. 6.12: Timeseries of latitude (upper panel), longitude (middle panel), and ship's speed (lower panel) during the WHOTS-19 cruise.

6.3 MicroCAT Data

The temperatures measured by MicroCATs during the mooring deployment for WHOTS-18 are presented in Fig. 6.13 through Fig. 6.16 for each of the depths where the instruments were located. The salinities are plotted in Fig. 6.17 through Fig. 6.20. The potential densities ($\sigma\theta$) are plotted in Fig. 6.21 through Fig. 6.24.

Contoured plots of temperature and salinity as a function of depth for the deployments WHOTS-1 through -18 are presented in Fig. 6.25, and contoured plots of potential density ($\sigma\theta$) as a function of depth are in Fig. 6.26, and of salinity as a function of $\sigma\theta$ are in Fig. 6.27.

The potential temperature (θ) and salinity measured by the deep MicroCATs during the mooring deployment are shown in Fig. 6.28. Also shown in the plot are the θ and salinity data obtained with a MicroCAT (SBE-37) installed in the ALOHA Cabled Observatory, about six nautical miles north from the WHOTS-18 anchor. The instrument is located 2 m above the bottom.

6.4 Moored ADCP Data

The contour plots presented in Fig. 6.29 illustrate the temporal evolution of the smoothed horizontal (zonal and meridional components) and vertical velocity as a function of depth for the WHOTS mooring deployments from WHOTS 1 through WHOTS 18. The zonal velocity shows seasonal variability, with alternating eastward and westward flows often observed down to 100 meters. Notable changes are evident particularly during the deployments from 2010 to 2012 and from 2018 to 2020, where shifts in both magnitude and direction are prominent. The meridional component displays considerable variability in northward and southward flow, with the most significant changes occurring between 2011 and 2013. The vertical velocity component remains weaker overall, but increased variability is noticeable during the 2011 to 2013 period and again from 2018 onward.

These observations highlight key periods of variability and provide insights into the evolving current structure throughout the WHOTS deployments. The years 2011-2013 and 2018-2020 stand out as periods with significant changes in both horizontal and vertical velocity patterns.

The vertical velocity component is relatively weak compared to the horizontal components, indicating minimal large-scale vertical movement. However, slight positive and negative velocities during specific periods suggest internal wave activity or localized vertical mixing events.

The plots in Fig. 6.30 detail the WHOTS-18 ADCP velocity measurements from mid-2022 through early 2023. The zonal velocity exhibits a predominantly westward flow throughout the deployment, with occasional eastward anomalies observed in the late summer and early winter months. These patterns align with seasonal wind forcing and possibly localized wind-driven upwelling events. The meridional velocity reveals alternating periods of northward and southward movement, suggesting the influence of mesoscale eddies and regional circulation patterns that drive variability along the meridional axis. In particular, significant northward transport was observed during late 2022, which transitioned to a southward direction in early 2023.

The vertical velocity component is relatively weak compared to the horizontal components, indicating minimal large-scale vertical movement, consistent with the stratified nature of the upper ocean at these depths. However, slight positive and negative velocities during specific periods suggest internal wave activity or localized vertical mixing events.

These plots collectively help us understand the dynamics of the ocean at the WHOTS-18 site, highlighting the importance of the combined influence of local wind forcing, mesoscale eddy activity, and internal waves in shaping the observed current structure.

A staggered time-series of smoothed horizontal and vertical velocities are shown in Fig. 6.31 through Fig. 6.33. Smoothing was performed by applying a daily running mean to the data and then interpolating it on an hourly grid.

Contours of east and north velocity components from the Ship Oscar Sette Ocean Surveyor broadband 75 kHz shipboard ADCP, and the moored 300 kHz ADCP from the WHOTS-18 deployment as a function of time and depth, during the WHOTS-18 cruise, are shown in Fig. 6.34 and Fig. 6.35.

Fig. 6.13: Temperatures from MicroCATs during WHOTS-18 deployment at 1.5, 7, 15, and 25m.

Fig. 6.14: Same as in Fig. 6.13, but at 40, 45, 50, and 55m.

Fig. 6.15: Same as in Fig. 6.13, but at 65, 75, 85, and 95m.

Fig. 6.16: Same as in Fig. 6.13, but a 105, 120, 135, and 155m.

Fig. 6.17: Salinities from MicroCATs during WHOTS-18 deployment at 1.5, 7, 15, and 25m

Fig. 6.18: Same as in Fig. 6.17, but at 40, 45, 50 and 55m.

Fig. 6.19: Same as in Fig. 6.17, but at 65, 75, 85, and 95 m

Fig. 6.20: Same as in Fig. 6.17, but at 105, 120, 135, and 155 m.

Fig. 6.21: Potential densities (σ_θ) from MicroCATs during WHOTS-18 deployment at 1.5, 7, 15, and 25m.

Fig. 6.22: Same as in Fig. 6.21, but at 40, 45, 50, and 55m.

Fig. 6.23: Same as in Fig. 6.21, but at 65, 75, 85, and 95m.

Fig. 6.24: Same as in Fig. 6.21, but at 105, 120, 135, and 155 m.

FS-M 29-Jan-2024, 13:14
 /home/helu/export/aina1/whots/analysis/w1_18cont.m

Fig. 6.25: Contour plots of temperature (upper panel) and salinity (lower panel) versus depth from SeaCATs/MicroCATs during WHOTS-1 through WHOTS-18 deployments. The shaded areas indicate missing data. The diamonds along the right axis indicate the depths of the instrument.

FS-M 29-Jan-2024, 13:14
/home/helu/export/aina1/whots/analysis/w1_18cont.m

Fig. 6.26: Contour plots of potential density (σ_θ), versus depth from SeaCATs/MicroCATs during WHOTS-1 through WHOTS-18 deployments. The shaded areas indicate missing data. The diamonds along the right axis in the upper figure indicate the depths of the instrument.

FS-M 29-Jan-2024, 13:15
 /home/helu/export/aina1/whots/analysis/w1_18cont.m

Fig. 6.27: Contour plots of salinity versus σ_θ from SeaCATs/MicroCATs during WHOTS-1 through WHOTS-18 deployments.

Fig. 6.28: Potential temperature (upper panel) and salinity (lower panel) time-series from the ALOHA Cabled Observatory (ACO) sensors and the WHOTS-18 MicroCATs 11391 and 12241.

Fig. 6.29: Contour plot of east velocity component (ms^{-1}) versus depth and time from the moored ADCPs from the WHOTS-1 through -18 deployments (upper panel). Contour plot of north velocity component (ms^{-1}) (middle panel). Contour plot of vertical velocity component (ms^{-1})(lower panel).

Fig. 6.30: Contour plot of east velocity component (ms^{-1}) versus depth and time from the moored ADCP WHOTS-18 (upper panel). Contour plot of north velocity component (ms^{-1}) (middle panel). Contour plot of vertical velocity component (ms^{-1})(lower panel).

Fig. 6.31: Staggered time-series of east velocity component (ms^{-1}) for each bin of the 600 kHz (upper panel) and 300 kHz (lower panel) moored ADCPs during WHOTS-18. The time-series are offset upwards by $0.5 ms^{-1}$; each bin's depth is on the right.

Fig. 6.32: Same as Fig. 6.31 but for north velocity component

Fig. 6.33: Same as Fig. 6.31 but for north velocity component but for vertical velocity component.

6.5 Moored and Shipboard ADCP comparisons

The contour plots in Fig. 6.34, and Fig. 6.35 present a comparison of the zonal and meridional current components captured by both the shipboard 75 kHz ADCP from the Oscar Sette and the moored 300 kHz ADCP at the WHOTS-18 mooring site. These plots provide insights into the consistency and discrepancies between shipboard and moored ADCP measurements throughout the WHOTS-18 cruise. Similar moored ADCP comparisons with the WHOTS-19 cruise shipboard ADCP (Fig. 6.36, and Fig. 6.37) were not possible because the moored ADCPs stopped working before the mooring was recovered.

6.5.1 WHOTS-18 Deployment Comparison

For the WHOTS-18 cruise (as shown in Fig. 6.34 and Fig. 6.35), the shipboard ADCP data from the Oscar Sette and the moored ADCP data reveal certain distinctions between zonal and meridional velocities at similar depths. Notably, the zonal current data show consistent eastward and westward oscillations between both ADCPs, though the magnitude appears more pronounced in the shipboard ADCP, particularly around late July 2022. These differences may be influenced by the positioning of the moored ADCP relative to the ship's track and its response to localized eddies or current variations.

The meridional current comparison (as presented in Fig. 6.35) also displays variations between the two datasets. The moored ADCP, being positioned at a fixed depth, captures consistent northward and southward patterns, whereas the shipboard ADCP data exhibit more fluctuation at shallower depths, potentially linked to local surface current variability during the cruise. The variability is especially pronounced around late July 2022, which aligns with the timing of increased dynamic activity also observed in the zonal component.

6.5.2 WHOTS-19 Deployment Comparison

WHOTS-19 cruise shipboard ADCP zonal and meridional currents are shown in [Fig. 6.36](#) and [Fig. 6.37](#). The zonal current reveals a predominantly westward flow throughout the deployment period, with occasional eastward pulses, particularly around day 168 and day 169. The eastward flow on day 168 is concentrated mainly between 40 to 100 m. Other eastward flows appear prominently at different times during the deployment.

The meridional current displays alternating northward and southward flows, which are more variable compared to the zonal currents. Between day 168 and day 169, there is a transition from predominantly southward flow to mixed northward and southward patterns, particularly in the upper 70 meters. Below 70 meters, the variability in meridional flow becomes less pronounced, with smoother transitions between northward and southward flows.

As mentioned above, the 300 kHz and the 600 kHz moored ADCP experienced operational failures, and we couldn't make a direct comparison between the Shipboard ADCP and Moored ADCP data for the WHOTS-19 deployment cruise. The 300 kHz instrument stopped recording on January 24, 2023, and the 600 kHz instrument stopped on February 10, 2023, likely due to power loss caused by bulkhead corrosion. As a result, only the shipboard ADCP data is available for the WHOTS-19 cruise analysis, limiting the ability to cross-verify these measurements with the moored instruments.

Comparisons between quality-controlled moored ADCPs during the WHOTS-18 deployment and available shipboard ADCP obtained during regular HOT cruises 338 to 342, and during the mooring deployment (WHOTS-18) and recovery (WHOTS-19) cruises are shown in [Fig. 6.38](#) for the 300 kHz ADCP. Median and mean velocity profiles were computed when HOT CTD casts were being conducted near the WHOTS mooring specifically intended to calibrate moored instrumentation (see [Conductivity Calibration](#)). The HOT shipboard profiles were taken when the ship was stationary, within 1 km of the mooring, and within 4 hours before the start and 4 hours after the end of the CTD cast conducted near the WHOTS mooring.

The HOT cruises conducted on the R/V Kilo Moana from HOT-338 to HOT-342 utilized various acoustic instruments for data collection. The TRDI Ocean Surveyor 38 kHz (OS38BB) was operated in broadband mode with a 12-meter bin size and 5-minute ensemble intervals, although data in broadband mode was not available for HOT-340 and HOT-341. Additionally, the cruises used the TRDI Ocean Surveyor 38 kHz in narrowband mode (OS38NB), with a 24-meter bin size and 5-minute ensemble. Furthermore, the Teledyne Workhorse 300 kHz, with a 2-meter bin size and 2-minute ensemble intervals, was employed throughout all the cruises.

Comparisons between the moored 300 kHz ADCP and the shipboard ADCP were available from HOT-339 to HOT-342, as shown in [Fig. 6.38](#). Data from other HOT-338 was excluded due to a lack of comparable measurements. Comparisons between the moored 600 kHz ADCP and the shipboard ADCP are presented in [Fig. 6.39](#).

6.6 Next Generation Vector Measuring Current Meter Data (VMCM)

Time-series of daily mean horizontal velocity components for the VMCM current meters deployed during WHOTS-18 at 10 m and 30 m depths are presented in [Fig. 6.40](#). The plots show the zonal and meridional velocity components for each depth, highlighting the variability in both east-west and north-south flows.

At 10 m depth, the zonal speed shows a notable oscillatory pattern, with peaks reaching up to 0.4 m/s in both eastward and westward directions. The meridional component at 10 m similarly exhibits variability, with alternating northward and southward flows, although the magnitude generally remains below 0.4 m/s. At 30 m depth, the zonal and meridional velocities exhibit similar oscillatory behavior, though the magnitude of the oscillations is slightly reduced compared to the 10 m depth. The zonal component continues to display alternating eastward and westward flows, with slightly dampened peaks compared to the surface. The meridional component also shows consistent fluctuations, with amplitudes generally below 0.4 m/s, indicating the persistence of dynamic current structures even at 30 m depth.

Fig. 6.34: The contour of zonal currents (ms^{-1}) from the Ship Oscar Sette Ocean Surveyor narrowband 75 kHz shipboard ADCP (upper panel), and the moored 300 kHz ADCP from the WHOTS-18 mooring (bottom panel) as a function of time and depth, during the WHOTS-18 cruise. Times when the CTD rosette was in the water are identified between solid and dashed black lines.

Fig. 6.35: The contour of meridional currents ($m s^{-1}$) from the Ship Oscar Sette Ocean Surveyor narrowband 75 kHz shipboard ADCP (upper panel), and the moored 300 kHz ADCP from the WHOTS-18 mooring (bottom panel) as a function of time and depth, during the WHOTS-18 cruise. Times when the CTD rosette was in the water are identified between solid and dashed black lines.

Fig. 6.36: The contour of zonal currents (ms^{-1}) from the Ship Oscar Sette Ocean Surveyor narrowband 75 kHz shipboard ADCP as a function of time and depth, during the WHOTS-19 cruise. Times when the CTD rosette was in the water are identified between solid and dashed black lines.

Fig. 6.37: Contours of meridional currents (ms^{-1}) from the Ship Oscar Sette Ocean Surveyor narrowband 75 kHz shipboard ADCP as a function of time and depth, during the WHOTS-19 cruise. Times when the CTD/rosette was in the water are identified between the solid and dashed black lines.

Fig. 6.38: Mean current profiles during shipboard ADCP (cyan: zonal, magenta: meridional) versus moored 300 kHz ADCP (blue: zonal, red: meridional) intercomparisons from HOT-316 through HOT-329. Moored minus shipboard ADCP differences shown in dotted lines (blue: zonal, red: meridional)

Fig. 6.39: Mean current profiles during shipboard ADCP (cyan: zonal, magenta: meridional) versus moored 600 kHz ADCP (blue: zonal, red: meridional) intercomparisons from HOT-316 through HOT-329. Moored minus shipboard ADCP differences shown in dotted lines (blue: zonal, red: meridional)

Fig. 6.40: Horizontal velocity data ($m s^{-1}$) during WHOTS-18 from the VMCMs at 10 m depth (first and second panel) and at 30 m depth (third and fourth panel)

6.7 GPS Data

Time-series of latitude and longitude of the WHOTS-18 buoy from GPS data are presented in Fig. 6.41. The plots illustrate the variability in the buoy's position over time, from late July 2022 to June 2023, providing insights into the movement and stability of the buoy during the deployment.

The latitude time-series (upper panel) shows fluctuations around a central value of approximately 22.66°N , with variations ranging between 22.64°N and 22.68°N . These deviations indicate lateral movement of the buoy, potentially caused by surface currents, wind forcing, and wave action. Notable peaks in latitude variability are observed around November 2022 and March 2023, suggesting periods of increased displacement due to dynamic oceanic or atmospheric conditions.

The longitude time-series (lower panel) depicts similar variability, with values fluctuating around 157.95°W , ranging from approximately 157.92°W to 157.98°W . The longitudinal deviations mirror the behavior seen in the latitude plot, indicating that the buoy experienced both east-west and north-south drift throughout the deployment. The increased variability in longitude, particularly around November 2022 and March 2023, aligns with the latitude observations, suggesting consistent periods of elevated buoy movement.

Fig. 6.41: GPS Latitude (upper panel) and longitude (lower panel) time series from the WHOTS-18 deployment.

Spectra of the latitude and longitude time-series from the WHOTS-18 buoy are presented in Fig. 6.42. These power spectra provide insights into the dominant frequencies of movement and help identify the temporal scales of variability affecting the buoy's position.

The power spectrum of the latitude time-series (upper panel) shows a decreasing trend in energy from low to high frequencies, indicating that most of the variability in the buoy's latitude occurs over longer timescales. The notable peaks around the frequencies marked as K1 and M2 suggest the influence of tidal components. The K1

tidal frequency corresponds to diurnal tidal cycles, while the M2 frequency is indicative of semidiurnal tides. These features highlight the impact of tidal forces on the buoy's latitudinal movement.

Similarly, the power spectrum of the longitude time-series (lower panel) also shows dominant energy at lower frequencies, reflecting the longer-term variability in the buoy's east-west displacement. Peaks at the K1 and M2 frequencies are also present, suggesting that the buoy's longitudinal movement is affected by similar tidal components as the latitude. The general trend of decreasing energy at higher frequencies suggests that high-frequency processes, such as wind or short-period waves, contribute less to the overall movement compared to lower-frequency tidal and mesoscale processes.

Overall, the spectral analysis reveals that the buoy's movement is largely driven by tidal forces, with significant contributions from both diurnal and semidiurnal components.

Fig. 6.42: The power spectrum of latitude (upper panel) and longitude (lower panel) for the WHOTS-18.

6.8 Mooring Motion

The position of the mooring with respect to its anchor was determined from GPS positions, supplemented by additional information provided by the ADCP data on pitch, roll, and heading. This section presents an analysis of the mooring's motion and its relationship to the tilt recorded by the ADCP instruments.

Fig. 6.43 shows scatter plots of the ADCP tilt (a combination of pitch and roll) against the buoy's distance from its anchor, derived from GPS positions, for both the 300 kHz and 600 kHz ADCPs during WHOTS-18. The red line in each plot represents a quadratic fit to the median tilt, calculated in 0.2 km distance bins. The plots demonstrate that as the distance of the buoy from the anchor increased, the tilt of the ADCP also increased.

This increase in tilt is consistent with the mooring line's deviation from its vertical position as the anchor pulled on it due to environmental forces such as currents, wind, and waves. The deviation causes the mooring line to tilt, which in turn affects the attached instruments, resulting in greater tilting of the ADCPs as the buoy moves farther from the anchor. This phenomenon highlights the dynamic interaction between the mooring and its environment, which can impact the measurements taken by the instruments.

It is also important to note that both the 300 kHz and 600 kHz moored ADCPs experienced operational interruptions. The 300 kHz instrument stopped recording on January 24, 2023, and the 600 kHz instrument stopped on February 10, 2023, likely due to power loss caused by bulkhead corrosion. Despite this, the scatter plot for both ADCPs still provides valuable insight into the relationship between tilt and distance before the failure occurred. The correlation coefficients ($R = 0.57$ for the 300 kHz ADCP and $R = 0.60$ for the 600 kHz ADCP) indicate a moderate positive relationship between the distance from the anchor and the tilt, demonstrating that the farther the buoy drifted, the more significant the ADCP tilt became.

Fig. 6.43: Scatter plots of ADCP tilt and distance of the buoy to its anchor for the 300 kHz (left panel) and the 600 kHz ADCP deployments (right panel, blue circles). The red line is a quadratic fit to the median tilt calculated every 0.2 km distance bins.

Appendix: Instrument Configurations and Specifications

7.1 WHOTS-18 300 kHz - Serial 4891

```
[BREAK Wakeup A]
WorkHorse Broadband ADCP Version 50.40
Teledyne RD Instruments (c) 1996-2010
All Rights Reserved.
>ps0
Instrument S/N: 4891
    Frequency: 307200 HZ
Configuration: 4 BEAM, JANUS
    Match Layer: 10
    Beam Angle: 20 DEGREES
    Beam Pattern: CONVEX
    Orientation: UP
    Sensor(s): HEADING TILT 1 TILT 2 TEMPERATURE
Temp Sens Offset: -0.23 degrees C

    CPU Firmware: 50.40 [0]
    Boot Code Ver: Required: 1.16 Actual: 1.16
    DEMOD #1 Ver: ad48, Type: 1f
    DEMOD #2 Ver: ad48, Type: 1f
    PWRTIMG Ver: 85d3, Type: 5

Board Serial Number Data:
    E2 00 00 03 7C 0B 00 09 REC727-1000-04E
    63 00 00 03 87 A5 E4 09 CPU727-2000-00J
    99 00 00 03 83 DB 8F 09 PI0727-3000-04C
    09 00 00 03 40 91 CF 09 DSP727-2001-04G
>ts 22/07/22,23:05:45
>r?
Available Commands:

RE ----- Recorder Erase
RF ----- Recorder Space used/free (bytes)
RN WHT16 ----- Set Deployment Name
RR ----- Recorder diRectory
RY ----- Upload Recorder Files to Host
R? ----- Display Recorder Commands
```

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```
>rf
RF = 69664768,186687488 --- Rec space used (bytes), free (bytes)

>rr
Recorder Directory:
Volume serial number for device #1 is 206f-6241

  WHT16000 000          69664768 07-06-21  2:52:36p r a [  2]

  Bytes used on device #1 = 69664768
Total capacity   = 256352256 bytes
Total bytes used = 69664768 bytes in 1 files
Total bytes free = 186687488 bytes

>re
Must use 'RE ErAsE' or 're ErAsE' to erase recorder!

Recorder not erased.

>RE ErAsE erasing...
Recorder erased.

>rr
Recorder Directory:
Volume serial number for device #1 is 206f-6241

  No files found.

  Bytes used on device #1 = 0
Total capacity   = 256352256 bytes
Total bytes used =          0 bytes in 0 files
Total bytes free = 256352256 bytes

>rrwht16
Recorder Directory:
Volume serial number for device #1 is 206f-6241

  No files found.

  Bytes used on device #1 = 0
Total capacity   = 256352256 bytes
Total bytes used =          0 bytes in 0 files
Total bytes free = 256352256 bytes

>cf11101
>ps0
  Instrument S/N: 4891
    Frequency: 307200 HZ
  Configuration: 4 BEAM, JANUS
    Match Layer: 10
    Beam Angle: 20 DEGREES
  Beam Pattern: CONVEX
  Orientation: UP
    Sensor(s): HEADING TILT 1 TILT 2 TEMPERATURE
Temp Sens Offset: -0.23 degrees C
```

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```

CPU Firmware: 50.40 [0]
Boot Code Ver: Required: 1.16 Actual: 1.16
DEMOM #1 Ver: ad48, Type: 1f
DEMOM #2 Ver: ad48, Type: 1f
PWRTIMG Ver: 85d3, Type: 5

Board Serial Number Data:
E2 00 00 03 7C 0B 00 09 REC727-1000-04E
63 00 00 03 87 A5 E4 09 CPU727-2000-00J
99 00 00 03 83 DB 8F 09 PI0727-3000-04C
09 00 00 03 40 91 CF 09 DSP727-2001-04G
>cf11101
>ea0
>eb0954
>ed1250
>es35
>ex11111
>ez1111101
>wa70
>wb0
>wd111100000
>wf176
>wn30
>wp40
>wv175
>wl2,6
>ws0400
>te00:10:00.00
>tp00:04:00
>tg20220722,23:59:59
>PS0
Instrument S/N: 4891
Frequency: 307200 HZ
Configuration: 4 BEAM, JANUS
Match Layer: 10
Beam Angle: 20 DEGREES
Beam Pattern: CONVEX
Orientation: UP
Sensor(s): HEADING TILT 1 TILT 2 TEMPERATURE
Temp Sens Offset: -0.23 degrees C

CPU Firmware: 50.40 [0]
Boot Code Ver: Required: 1.16 Actual: 1.16
DEMOM #1 Ver: ad48, Type: 1f
DEMOM #2 Ver: ad48, Type: 1f
PWRTIMG Ver: 85d3, Type: 5

Board Serial Number Data:
E2 00 00 03 7C 0B 00 09 REC727-1000-04E
63 00 00 03 87 A5 E4 09 CPU727-2000-00J
99 00 00 03 83 DB 8F 09 PI0727-3000-04C
09 00 00 03 40 91 CF 09 DSP727-2001-04G
>CK
[Parameters saved as USER defaults]
>

```

7.2 WHOTS-18 600 kHz - Serial 1825

```

[BREAK Wakeup A]
WorkHorse Broadband ADCP Version 51.40
Teledyne RD Instruments (c) 1996-2010
All Rights Reserved.
>
>TS 60/07/22,22:47:44
>?
Available Menus:
DEPLOY? ----- Deployment Commands
SYSTEM? ----- System Control, Data Recovery and Testing Commands

>SYSTEM
System Control, Data Recovery and Testing Commands:
AC ----- Output Active Fluxgate & Tilt Calibration data
AF ----- Field calibrate to remove hard/soft iron error
AR ----- Restore factory fluxgate calibration data
AX ----- Examine compass performance
AZ ----- Zero pressure reading

CB = 411 ----- Serial Port Control (Baud; Par; Stop)
CP # ----- Polled Mode (0 = NORMAL, 1 = POLLED)
CZ ----- Power Down Instrument

FC ----- Clear Fault Log
FD ----- Display Fault Log

OL ----- Display Features List

PA ----- Pre-Deployment Tests
PC1 ----- Beam Continuity
PC2 ----- Sensor Data
PS0 ----- System Configuration
PS3 ----- Transformation Matrices

RR ----- Recorder Directory
RF ----- Recorder Space used/free (bytes)
RY ----- Upload Recorder Files to Host

>ol
                                FEATURES
-----
Feature                               Installed
-----
BT-HA (High Accuracy 0.4%)            Yes
Water Profile                          Yes
High Resolution Water Modes           No
LADCP/Surface Track/WM15              No
Wave Gauge Acquisition                No
Shallow Bottom Mode                   No
High Rate Pinging                     No
Narrow Bandwidth only (WB1)           No
BT-RA (Reduced Accuracy 1.15%)       No

See your technical manual or contact TRDI for information on how to

```

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```

install additional capability in your WorkHorse.

>p50 ERR 010: UNRECOGNIZED COMMAND
>ps0
  Instrument S/N: 1825
    Frequency: 614400 HZ
  Configuration: 4 BEAM, JANUS
    Match Layer: 10
    Beam Angle: 20 DEGREES
  Beam Pattern: CONVEX
  Orientation: UP
    Sensor(s): HEADING TILT 1 TILT 2 DEPTH TEMPERATURE PRESSURE
Pressure Sens Coefficients:
    c3 = +1.762294E-13
    c2 = +3.330826E-08
    c1 = +1.389532E-01
  Offset = -4.652679E+00

Temp Sens Offset: -0.13 degrees C

  CPU Firmware: 51.40 [0]
  Boot Code Ver: Required: 1.16 Actual: 1.16
  DEMOD #1 Ver: ad48, Type: 1f
  DEMOD #2 Ver: ad48, Type: 1f
  PWRTIMG Ver: 85d3, Type: 5

Board Serial Number Data:
  E4 00 00 02 00 20 C0 09 DSP727-2001-03F
  OD 00 00 02 48 A7 98 09 REC727-1000-03A
  7E 00 00 02 00 4D 0B 09 PI0727-3000-03C
  97 00 00 02 00 3F BB 09 CPU727-2000-00H

>rrwht16
Recorder Directory:
Volume serial number for device #1 is 206f-6241

WHT16000 000          0 09-27-19  0:56:50a r a [  0]
WHT16001 000          0 09-27-19  2:24:58a r a [  0]
WHT16002 000      10348242 01-21-20  9:10:02p r a [  2]
WHT16003 000      11118 01-22-20  0:09:40a r a [ 2529]
WHT16004 000      53628 01-22-20  1:55:24p r a [ 2532]
WHT16005 000      17658 01-22-20  6:31:06p r a [ 2546]
WHT16006 000      7848 01-22-20  8:37:04p r a [ 2551]
WHT16007 000      654 01-22-20  8:53:56p r a [ 2553]
WHT16008 000      7194 01-22-20 10:49:20p r a [ 2554]
WHT16009 000      3924 04-17-20  1:01:30p r a [ 2556]
WHT16010 000          0 04-17-20  1:59:10p r a [  0]
WHT16011 000      654 04-17-20  2:44:32p r a [ 2557]
WHT16012 000      1962 04-17-20  3:33:42p r a [ 2558]
WHT16013 000      3270 04-17-20  4:47:48p r a [ 2559]
WHT16014 000          0 04-17-20  5:16:56p r a [  0]
WHT16015 000      1308 04-17-20  6:19:26p r a [ 2560]
WHT16016 000      654 04-17-20  6:51:58p r a [ 2561]
WHT16017 000      2616 04-17-20  7:40:22p r a [ 2562]
WHT16018 000      6540 04-17-20 10:00:42p r a [ 2563]

Bytes used on device #1 = 10467270

```

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```

Total capacity = 256352256 bytes
Total bytes used = 10467270 bytes in 19 files
Total bytes free = 245854208 bytes

>cf11101
>ea0
>eb0954
>?
Available Menus:
DEPLOY? ----- Deployment Commands
SYSTEM? ----- System Control, Data Recovery and Testing Commands

>deploy
Deployment Commands:
BP = 000 ----- Bottom Track Pings per Ensemble

CF = 11101 ----- Flow Ctrl (EnsCyc;PngCyc;Binry;Ser;Rec)
CK ----- Keep Parameters as USER Defaults
CR # ----- Retrieve Parameters (0 = USER, 1 = FACTORY)
CS ----- Start Deployment

EA = +00000 ----- Heading Alignment (1/100 deg)
EB = +00954 ----- Heading Bias (1/100 deg)
ED = 00475 ----- Transducer Depth (0 - 65535 dm)
ES = 35 ----- Salinity (0-40 pp thousand)
EX = 11111 ----- Coord Transform (Xform: Type,Tilts,3 Bm,Map)
EZ = 1111101 ----- Sensor Source (C,D,H,P,R,S,T)

RE ----- Recorder ErAsE
RN ----- Set Deployment Name

TE = 00:10:00.00 ----- Time per Ensemble (hrs:min:sec.sec/100)
TF = **/**/**,**:***:*** --- Time of First Ping (yr/mon/day,hour:min:sec)
TP = 00:02.00 ----- Time per Ping (min:sec.sec/100)
TS = 60/07/22,22:50:30 --- Time Set (yr/mon/day,hour:min:sec)

WD = 111 100 000 ----- Data Out (Vel,Cor,Amp; PG,St,P0; P1,P2,P3)
WF = 0088 ----- Blank After Transmit (cm)
WN = 025 ----- Number of depth cells (1-128)
WP = 00080 ----- Pings per Ensemble (0-16384)
WS = 0200 ----- Depth Cell Size (cm)
WV = 175 ----- Mode 1 Ambiguity Vel (cm/s radial)

>RE
Must use 'RE ErAsE' or 're ErAsE' to erase recorder!

Recorder not erased.

>RE ErAsE erasing...
Recorder erased.

>rrwht16
Recorder Directory:
Volume serial number for device #1 is 206f-6241

No files found.

```

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```

Bytes used on device #1 = 0
Total capacity   = 256352256 bytes
Total bytes used =           0 bytes in 0 files
Total bytes free = 256352256 bytes

>cf11101
>ea0
>eb0954
>ed0475
>es35
>ex11111
>ez1111101
>wa70
>wb0
>wd111100000
>wf0088
>wl2,6
>wp80
>ws0200
>wn25
>wv175
>te:00:10:00.00
>tp00:02:00
>tg20220722,23:59:59ERR: TF date/time is more than a year!
  ERR: Bad command parameters!Out of range!
>?
Available Menus:
DEPLOY? ----- Deployment Commands
SYSTEM? ----- System Control, Data Recovery and Testing Commands

>SYSTEM
System Control, Data Recovery and Testing Commands:
AC ----- Output Active Fluxgate & Tilt Calibration data
AF ----- Field calibrate to remove hard/soft iron error
AR ----- Restore factory fluxgate calibration data
AX ----- Examine compass performance
AZ ----- Zero pressure reading

CB = 411 ----- Serial Port Control (Baud; Par; Stop)
CP # ----- Polled Mode (0 = NORMAL, 1 = POLLED)
CZ ----- Power Down Instrument

FC ----- Clear Fault Log
FD ----- Display Fault Log

OL ----- Display Features List

PA ----- Pre-Deployment Tests
PC1 ----- Beam Continuity
PC2 ----- Sensor Data
PS0 ----- System Configuration
PS3 ----- Transformation Matrices

RR ----- Recorder Directory
RF ----- Recorder Space used/free (bytes)

```

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```

RY ----- Upload Recorder Files to Host

>PS0
Instrument S/N: 1825
  Frequency: 614400 HZ
Configuration: 4 BEAM, JANUS
  Match Layer: 10
  Beam Angle: 20 DEGREES
Beam Pattern: CONVEX
Orientation: UP
  Sensor(s): HEADING TILT 1 TILT 2 DEPTH TEMPERATURE PRESSURE
Pressure Sens Coefficients:
  c3 = +1.762294E-13
  c2 = +3.330826E-08
  c1 = +1.389532E-01
  Offset = -4.652679E+00

Temp Sens Offset: -0.13 degrees C

  CPU Firmware: 51.40 [0]
  Boot Code Ver: Required: 1.16 Actual: 1.16
  DEMOD #1 Ver: ad48, Type: 1f
  DEMOD #2 Ver: ad48, Type: 1f
  PWRTIMG Ver: 85d3, Type: 5

Board Serial Number Data:
E4 00 00 02 00 20 C0 09 DSP727-2001-03F
OD 00 00 02 48 A7 98 09 REC727-1000-03A
7E 00 00 02 00 4D 0B 09 PI0727-3000-03C
97 00 00 02 00 3F BB 09 CPU727-2000-00H
>tg20220722,23:59:59ERR: TF date/time is more than a year!
  ERR: Bad command parameters!Out of range!
>tf ERR: Bad command parameters!Out of range!
>TF?
TF **/**/**,**:**:** --- Time of First Ping (yr/mon/day,hour:min:sec)
>TG?
TG ****/**/**,**:**:** - Time of First Ping (CCYY/MM/DD,hh:mm:ss)
>T?
Available Commands:

TB 00:00:00.00 ----- Time per Burst (hrs:min:sec.sec/100)
TC 00000 ----- Ensembles Per Burst (0-65535)
TE 00:10:00.00 ----- Time per Ensemble (hrs:min:sec.sec/100)
TF **/**/**,**:**:** --- Time of First Ping (yr/mon/day,hour:min:sec)
TG ****/**/**,**:**:** - Time of First Ping (CCYY/MM/DD,hh:mm:ss)
TP 00:02.00 ----- Time per Ping (min:sec.sec/100)
TS 60/07/22,22:57:03 --- Time Set (yr/mon/day,hour:min:sec)
TT 2060/07/22,22:57:03 - Time Set (CCYY/MM/DD,hh:mm:ss)
TX 00:00:00 ----- Buffer Output Period: (hh:mm:ss)
T? ----- Display Time Help

>TS ERR: Bad command parameters!Out of range!
>
>ts 22/07/22,22:58:00
>tg2022/07/22,23:59:59
>ck?

```

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```

CK ----- Keep Parameters as USER Defaults
>ck
[Parameters saved as USER defaults]
>ps0
  Instrument S/N: 1825
    Frequency: 614400 HZ
  Configuration: 4 BEAM, JANUS
    Match Layer: 10
    Beam Angle: 20 DEGREES
  Beam Pattern: CONVEX
  Orientation: UP
  Sensor(s): HEADING TILT 1 TILT 2 DEPTH TEMPERATURE PRESSURE
Pressure Sens Coefficients:
  c3 = +1.762294E-13
  c2 = +3.330826E-08
  c1 = +1.389532E-01
  Offset = -4.652679E+00

Temp Sens Offset: -0.13 degrees C

  CPU Firmware: 51.40 [0]
  Boot Code Ver: Required: 1.16 Actual: 1.16
  DEMOD #1 Ver: ad48, Type: 1f
  DEMOD #2 Ver: ad48, Type: 1f
  PWRTIMG Ver: 85d3, Type: 5

Board Serial Number Data:
  E4 00 00 02 00 20 C0 09 DSP727-2001-03F
  OD 00 00 02 48 A7 98 09 REC727-1000-03A
  7E 00 00 02 00 4D 0B 09 PI0727-3000-03C
  97 00 00 02 00 3F BB 09 CPU727-2000-00H
>
=====

[BREAK Wakeup A]
WorkHorse Broadband ADCP Version 51.40
Teledyne RD Instruments (c) 1996-2010
All Rights Reserved.
>ps0
  Instrument S/N: 1825
    Frequency: 614400 HZ
  Configuration: 4 BEAM, JANUS
    Match Layer: 10
    Beam Angle: 20 DEGREES
  Beam Pattern: CONVEX
  Orientation: UP
  Sensor(s): HEADING TILT 1 TILT 2 DEPTH TEMPERATURE PRESSURE
Pressure Sens Coefficients:
  c3 = +1.762294E-13
  c2 = +3.330826E-08
  c1 = +1.389532E-01
  Offset = -4.652679E+00

Temp Sens Offset: -0.13 degrees C

  CPU Firmware: 51.40 [0]

```

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```

Boot Code Ver: Required: 1.16 Actual: 1.16
  DEMOD #1 Ver: ad48, Type: 1f
  DEMOD #2 Ver: ad48, Type: 1f
  PWRTIMG Ver: 85d3, Type: 5

```

Board Serial Number Data:

```

E4 00 00 02 00 20 C0 09 DSP727-2001-03F
OD 00 00 02 48 A7 98 09 REC727-1000-03A
7E 00 00 02 00 4D 0B 09 PI0727-3000-03C
97 00 00 02 00 3F BB 09 CPU727-2000-00H

```

>t?

Available Commands:

```

TB 00:00:00.00 ----- Time per Burst (hrs:min:sec.sec/100)
TC 00000 ----- Ensembles Per Burst (0-65535)
TE 00:10:00.00 ----- Time per Ensemble (hrs:min:sec.sec/100)
TF **/**/**,**:**:** --- Time of First Ping (yr/mon/day,hour:min:sec)
TG ****/**/**,**:**:** - Time of First Ping (CCYY/MM/DD,hh:mm:ss)
TP 00:02.00 ----- Time per Ping (min:sec.sec/100)
TS 22/07/23,00:28:13 --- Time Set (yr/mon/day,hour:min:sec)
TT 2022/07/23,00:28:13 - Time Set (CCYY/MM/DD,hh:mm:ss)
TX 00:00:00 ----- Buffer Output Period: (hh:mm:ss)
T? ----- Display Time Help

```

>ts220723,00:29:10

>t?

Available Commands:

```

TB 00:00:00.00 ----- Time per Burst (hrs:min:sec.sec/100)
TC 00000 ----- Ensembles Per Burst (0-65535)
TE 00:10:00.00 ----- Time per Ensemble (hrs:min:sec.sec/100)
TF **/**/**,**:**:** --- Time of First Ping (yr/mon/day,hour:min:sec)
TG ****/**/**,**:**:** - Time of First Ping (CCYY/MM/DD,hh:mm:ss)
TP 00:02.00 ----- Time per Ping (min:sec.sec/100)
TS 22/07/23,00:29:13 --- Time Set (yr/mon/day,hour:min:sec)
TT 2022/07/23,00:29:13 - Time Set (CCYY/MM/DD,hh:mm:ss)
TX 00:00:00 ----- Buffer Output Period: (hh:mm:ss)
T? ----- Display Time Help

```

>tg 2022/07/23,00:40:00

>t?

Available Commands:

```

TB 00:00:00.00 ----- Time per Burst (hrs:min:sec.sec/100)
TC 00000 ----- Ensembles Per Burst (0-65535)
TE 00:10:00.00 ----- Time per Ensemble (hrs:min:sec.sec/100)
TF 22/07/23,00:40:00 --- Time of First Ping (yr/mon/day,hour:min:sec)
TG 2022/07/23,00:40:00 - Time of First Ping (CCYY/MM/DD,hh:mm:ss)
TP 00:02.00 ----- Time per Ping (min:sec.sec/100)
TS 22/07/23,00:29:55 --- Time Set (yr/mon/day,hour:min:sec)
TT 2022/07/23,00:29:55 - Time Set (CCYY/MM/DD,hh:mm:ss)
TX 00:00:00 ----- Buffer Output Period: (hh:mm:ss)
T? ----- Display Time Help

```

>ck

[Parameters saved as USER defaults]

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```

>deploy?
Deployment Commands:
BP = 000 ----- Bottom Track Pings per Ensemble

CF = 11101 ----- Flow Ctrl (EnsCyc;PngCyc;Binry;Ser;Rec)
CK ----- Keep Parameters as USER Defaults
CR # ----- Retrieve Parameters (0 = USER, 1 = FACTORY)
CS ----- Start Deployment

EA = +00000 ----- Heading Alignment (1/100 deg)
EB = +00954 ----- Heading Bias (1/100 deg)
ED = 00475 ----- Transducer Depth (0 - 65535 dm)
ES = 35 ----- Salinity (0-40 pp thousand)
EX = 11111 ----- Coord Transform (Xform: Type,Tilts,3 Bm,Map)
EZ = 1111101 ----- Sensor Source (C,D,H,P,R,S,T)

RE ----- Recorder ErAsE
RN ----- Set Deployment Name

TE = 00:10:00.00 ----- Time per Ensemble (hrs:min:sec.sec/100)
TF = 22/07/23,00:40:00 --- Time of First Ping (yr/mon/day,hour:min:sec)
TP = 00:02.00 ----- Time per Ping (min:sec.sec/100)
TS = 22/07/23,00:30:06 --- Time Set (yr/mon/day,hour:min:sec)

WD = 111 100 000 ----- Data Out (Vel,Cor,Amp; PG,St,P0; P1,P2,P3)
WF = 0088 ----- Blank After Transmit (cm)
WN = 025 ----- Number of depth cells (1-128)
WP = 00080 ----- Pings per Ensemble (0-16384)
WS = 0200 ----- Depth Cell Size (cm)
WV = 175 ----- Mode 1 Ambiguity Vel (cm/s radial)

>cs

```

7.3 WHOTS-18 MicroCAT - Headers

```

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 6411
* <?xml version="1.0"?>
* <!--DeviceManager-->
* <SBEDataUploadFile>
* <ApplicationData>
* <DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* <SoftwareVersion>1.8.2</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>25-Jul-2018 07:49:42 UTC</BuildDate>
* </DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606411'>
*   <DateTime>2023-06-21T20:10:47</DateTime>
*   <DelayedStart>2000-01-01T00:00:00</DelayedStart>
*   <EventSummary numEvents='0' />
*   <Power>
*     <MainSupplyVoltage>3.63</MainSupplyVoltage>
*   </Power>
* <ADCRatio>

```

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```

*      <Ratio>11209069</Ratio>
*      </ADCRatio>
*      <Battery>
*      <Installed>2000-01-01T00:00:00</Installed>
*      <Samples>480731</Samples>
*      </Battery>
*      <MemorySummary>
*      <Samples>480731</Samples>
*      <Bytes>2001408</Bytes>
*      <BytesFree>64583168</BytesFree>
*      </MemorySummary>
*      </StatusData>
*
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606411'>
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc</Manufacturer>
*   <FirmwareVersion>SBE56 V0.96</FirmwareVersion>
*   <FirmwareDate>Feb 25 2011</FirmwareDate>
*   <PCBAsembly PCBID='101833' AssemblyNum='41688F' />
*   <MfgDate>Feb 25 2011</MfgDate>
*   <PCBType>0</PCBType>
*   <InternalSensors>
*     <Sensor id='Water Temperature'>
*       <type>TEMP0</type>
*       <SerialNumber>05606411</SerialNumber>
*     </Sensor>
*   </InternalSensors>
* </HardwareData>
*
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606411'>
*   <Settings
*     samplePeriod='60' format='1' />
*   </ConfigurationData>
*
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606411'>
*   <Calibration format='TEMP0' id='Water Temperature'>
*     <CalDate>2016-03-11</CalDate>
*     <a0>-1.251684E-03</a0>
*     <a1>3.519107E-04</a1>
*     <a2>-7.014985E-06</a2>
*     <a3>2.081770E-07</a3>
*     <OFFSET>0.000000E+00</OFFSET>
*   </Calibration>
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
*
* <EventSummary DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05606411'>
*   <EventList numEvents='0' maxStack='-2'>
*   </EventList>
* </EventSummary>
*
* </InstrumentState>
# nquan = 4
# nvalues = 480731
# units = specified
# name 0 = scan: Scan Count
# name 1 = timeJ: Julian Days
# name 2 = t090C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C

```

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```

# name 3 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = 1, 480731
# span 1 = 203.999306, 537.839572
# span 2 = -0.0022, 46.7334
# span 3 = 0.000e+00, 0.000e+00
# interval = seconds: 60
# start_time = Jul 22 2022 23:59:00
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# sensor 0 = RRatio temperature, 05606411
# datcnv_date = Jun 21 2023 20:34:29, SeatermUSB v 1.8.2
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W18\DATA\SUBSURFACE\SBE56_6411.
→xml
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 7213
* <?xml version="1.0"?>
* <!--DeviceManager-->
* <SBEDataUploadFile>
* <ApplicationData>
* <DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* <SoftwareVersion>1.8.2</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>25-Jul-2018 07:49:42 UTC</BuildDate>
* </DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607213'>
* <DateTime>2023-06-21T20:21:02</DateTime>
* <DelayedStart>2000-01-01T00:00:00</DelayedStart>
* <EventSummary numEvents='0' />
* <Power>
* <MainSupplyVoltage>3.65</MainSupplyVoltage>
* </Power>
* <ADCRatio>
* <Ratio>9651696</Ratio>
* </ADCRatio>
* <Battery>
* <Installed>2000-01-01T00:00:00</Installed>
* <Samples>480741</Samples>
* </Battery>
* <MemorySummary>
* <Samples>480741</Samples>
* <Bytes>2001408</Bytes>
* <BytesFree>64583168</BytesFree>
* </MemorySummary>
* </StatusData>
*
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607213'>
* <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc</Manufacturer>
* <FirmwareVersion>SBE56 V0.96</FirmwareVersion>
* <FirmwareDate>Feb 25 2011</FirmwareDate>
* <PCBAAssembly PCBAID='112208' AssemblyNum='41688F' />
* <MfgDate>Feb 25 2011</MfgDate>
* <PCBType>0</PCBType>
* <InternalSensors>

```

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```

*      <Sensor id='Water Temperature'>
*          <type>TEMPO</type>
*          <SerialNumber>05607213</SerialNumber>
*      </Sensor>
*  </InternalSensors>
* </HardwareData>
*
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607213'>
*   <Settings
*     samplePeriod='60' format='1' />
* </ConfigurationData>
*
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607213'>
*   <Calibration format='TEMPO' id='Water Temperature'>
*     <CalDate>2016-12-06</CalDate>
*     <a0>-1.412968E-03</a0>
*     <a1>3.625611E-04</a1>
*     <a2>-7.149116E-06</a2>
*     <a3>2.145689E-07</a3>
*     <OFFSET>0.000000E+00</OFFSET>
*   </Calibration>
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
*
* <EventSummary DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607213'>
*   <EventList numEvents='0' maxStack='-2'>
*     </EventList>
* </EventSummary>
*
* </InstrumentState>
# nquan = 4
# nvalues = 480741
# units = specified
# name 0 = scan: Scan Count
# name 1 = timeJ: Julian Days
# name 2 = t090C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C
# name 3 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = 1, 480741
# span 1 = 203.999306, 537.846516
# span 2 = -0.0016, 49.6870
# span 3 = 0.000e+00, 0.000e+00
# interval = seconds: 60
# start_time = Jul 22 2022 23:59:00
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# sensor 0 = RRatio temperature, 05607213
# datcnv_date = Jun 21 2023 20:35:06, SeatermUSB v 1.8.2
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W18\DATA\SUBSURFACE\SBE56_7213.
→xml
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 7214
* <?xml version="1.0"?>
* <!--DeviceManager-->
* <SBEDataUploadFile>
* <ApplicationData>

```

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(continued from previous page)

```

* <DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* <SoftwareVersion>1.8.2</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>25-Jul-2018 07:49:42 UTC</BuildDate>
* </DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607214'>
*   <DateTime>2023-06-21T20:26:25</DateTime>
*   <DelayedStart>2000-01-01T00:00:00</DelayedStart>
*   <EventSummary numEvents='0' />
*   <Power>
*     <MainSupplyVoltage>3.65</MainSupplyVoltage>
*   </Power>
*   <ADCRatio>
*     <Ratio>8790379</Ratio>
*   </ADCRatio>
*   <Battery>
*     <Installed>2000-01-01T00:00:00</Installed>
*     <Samples>480747</Samples>
*   </Battery>
*   <MemorySummary>
*     <Samples>480747</Samples>
*     <Bytes>2001408</Bytes>
*     <BytesFree>64583168</BytesFree>
*   </MemorySummary>
* </StatusData>
*
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607214'>
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc</Manufacturer>
*   <FirmwareVersion>SBE56 V0.96</FirmwareVersion>
*   <FirmwareDate>Feb 25 2011</FirmwareDate>
*   <PCBAssembly PCBID='112199' AssemblyNum='41688F' />
*   <MfgDate>Feb 25 2011</MfgDate>
*   <PCBType>0</PCBType>
*   <InternalSensors>
*     <Sensor id='Water Temperature'>
*       <type>TEMP0</type>
*       <SerialNumber>05607214</SerialNumber>
*     </Sensor>
*   </InternalSensors>
* </HardwareData>
*
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607214'>
*   <Settings
*     samplePeriod='60' format='1' />
* </ConfigurationData>
*
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607214'>
*   <Calibration format='TEMP0' id='Water Temperature'>
*     <CalDate>2022-02-22</CalDate>
*     <a0>-1.404439E-03</a0>
*     <a1>3.594089E-04</a1>
*     <a2>-6.928444E-06</a2>
*     <a3>2.100205E-07</a3>
*     <OFFSET>0.000000E+00</OFFSET>
*   </Calibration>

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*   </CalibrationCoefficients>
*
* <EventSummary DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607214'>
*   <EventList numEvents='0' maxStack='-2'>
*     </EventList>
*   </EventSummary>
*
* </InstrumentState>
# nquan = 4
# nvalues = 480747
# units = specified
# name 0 = scan: Scan Count
# name 1 = timeJ: Julian Days
# name 2 = t090C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C
# name 3 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = 1, 480747
# span 1 = 203.999306, 537.850683
# span 2 = -0.0040, 44.2721
# span 3 = 0.000e+00, 0.000e+00
# interval = seconds: 60
# start_time = Jul 22 2022 23:59:00
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# sensor 0 = RRatio temperature, 05607214
# datcnv_date = Jun 21 2023 20:35:19, SeatermUSB v 1.8.2
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W18\DATA\SUBSURFACE\SBE56_7214.
→xml
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

```

```

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 7215
* <?xml version="1.0"?>
* <!--DeviceManager-->
* <SBEDataUploadFile>
* <ApplicationData>
* <DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* <SoftwareVersion>1.8.2</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>25-Jul-2018 07:49:42 UTC</BuildDate>
* </DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607215'>
*   <DateTime>2023-06-21T20:29:55</DateTime>
*   <DelayedStart>2000-01-01T00:00:00</DelayedStart>
*   <EventSummary numEvents='0' />
*   <Power>
*     <MainSupplyVoltage>3.63</MainSupplyVoltage>
*   </Power>
*   <ADCRatio>
*     <Ratio>8856121</Ratio>
*   </ADCRatio>
*   <Battery>
*     <Installed>2000-01-01T00:00:00</Installed>
*     <Samples>480750</Samples>
*   </Battery>

```

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```

* <MemorySummary>
*   <Samples>480750</Samples>
*   <Bytes>2001408</Bytes>
*   <BytesFree>64583168</BytesFree>
*   </MemorySummary>
* </StatusData>
*
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607215'>
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc</Manufacturer>
*   <FirmwareVersion>SBE56 V0.96</FirmwareVersion>
*   <FirmwareDate>Feb 25 2011</FirmwareDate>
*   <PCBAssembly PCBID='112209' AssemblyNum='41688F' />
*   <MfgDate>Feb 25 2011</MfgDate>
*   <PCBType>0</PCBType>
*   <InternalSensors>
*     <Sensor id='Water Temperature'>
*       <type>TEMP0</type>
*       <SerialNumber>05607215</SerialNumber>
*     </Sensor>
*   </InternalSensors>
* </HardwareData>
*
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607215'>
*   <Settings
*     samplePeriod='60' format='1' />
*   </ConfigurationData>
*
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607215'>
*   <Calibration format='TEMP0' id='Water Temperature'>
*     <CalDate>2022-02-18</CalDate>
*     <a0>-1.447522E-03</a0>
*     <a1>3.705846E-04</a1>
*     <a2>-7.702980E-06</a2>
*     <a3>2.256575E-07</a3>
*     <OFFSET>0.000000E+00</OFFSET>
*   </Calibration>
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
*
* <EventSummary DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607215'>
*   <EventList numEvents='0' maxStack='-2'>
*   </EventList>
* </EventSummary>
*
* </InstrumentState>
# nquan = 4
# nvalues = 480750
# units = specified
# name 0 = scan: Scan Count
# name 1 = timeJ: Julian Days
# name 2 = t090C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C
# name 3 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = 1, 480750
# span 1 = 203.999306, 537.852766
# span 2 = -0.0023, 45.8691
# span 3 = 0.000e+00, 0.000e+00
# interval = seconds: 60

```

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```

# start_time = Jul 22 2022 23:59:00
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# sensor 0 = RRatio temperature, 05607215
# datcnv_date = Jun 21 2023 20:35:30, SeatermUSB v 1.8.2
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W18\DATA\SUBSURFACE\SBE56_7215.
↪xml
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 7212
* <?xml version="1.0"?>
* <!--DeviceManager-->
* <SBEDataUploadFile>
* <ApplicationData>
* <DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* <SoftwareVersion>1.8.2</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>25-Jul-2018 07:49:42 UTC</BuildDate>
* </DeviceInterfaceAppData>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607212'>
*   <DateTime>2023-06-21T20:16:15</DateTime>
*   <DelayedStart>2000-01-01T00:00:00</DelayedStart>
*   <EventSummary numEvents='255' />
*   <Power>
*     <MainSupplyVoltage>3.65</MainSupplyVoltage>
*   </Power>
*   <ADCRatio>
*     <Ratio>1003343</Ratio>
*   </ADCRatio>
*   <Battery>
*     <Installed>2000-01-01T00:00:00</Installed>
*     <Samples>480736</Samples>
*   </Battery>
*   <MemorySummary>
*     <Samples>480736</Samples>
*     <Bytes>2001408</Bytes>
*     <BytesFree>64583168</BytesFree>
*   </MemorySummary>
* </StatusData>
*
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607212'>
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc</Manufacturer>
*   <FirmwareVersion>SBE56 V0.96</FirmwareVersion>
*   <FirmwareDate>Feb 25 2011</FirmwareDate>
*   <PCBAAssembly PCBID='112207' AssemblyNum='41688F' />
*   <MfgDate>Feb 25 2011</MfgDate>
*   <PCBType>0</PCBType>
*   <InternalSensors>
*     <Sensor id='Water Temperature'>
*       <type>TEMPO</type>
*       <SerialNumber>05607212</SerialNumber>
*     </Sensor>
*   </InternalSensors>
* </HardwareData>

```

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```

*
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607212'>
*   <Settings
*     samplePeriod='60' format='1' />
*   </ConfigurationData>
*
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607212'>
*   <Calibration format='TEMPO' id='Water Temperature'>
*     <CalDate>2022-02-18</CalDate>
*     <a0>-1.418179E-03</a0>
*     <a1>3.633361E-04</a1>
*     <a2>-7.201988E-06</a2>
*     <a3>2.156908E-07</a3>
*     <OFFSET>0.000000E+00</OFFSET>
*   </Calibration>
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
*
* <EventSummary DeviceType='SBE56' SerialNumber='05607212'>
*   <EventList numEvents='255' maxStack='-2'>
*     <Event type='Error11' count='255' />
*   </EventList>
* </EventSummary>
*
* </InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
* <![CDATA[
* ** BROKEN PROBE/GUARD
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 4
# nvalues = 480736
# units = specified
# name 0 = scan: Scan Count
# name 1 = timeJ: Julian Days
# name 2 = t090C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C
# name 3 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = 1, 480736
# span 1 = 203.999306, 537.843044
# span 2 = -0.0029, 42.5076
# span 3 = 0.000e+00, 0.000e+00
# interval = seconds: 60
# start_time = Jul 22 2022 23:59:00
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# sensor 0 = RRatio temperature, 05607212
# datcnv_date = Jun 21 2023 20:34:54, SeatermUSB v 1.8.2
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W18\DATA\SUBSURFACE\SBE56_7212.
→xml
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 1834
* Sea-Bird SBE37 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W18\DATA\SURFACE\SBE37_SST_1834.
→asc
* Software Version 1.59

```

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```
* Temperature SN = 1834
* Conductivity SN = 1834
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 21 2023 02:56:46
** WHOTS 18 SYSTEM 1 SST SN1834
* ds
* 1ds
* SBE37-SM 485 V 2.3b SERIAL NO. 1834    21 Jun 2023  02:55:47
* not logging: received stop command
* sample interval = 300 seconds
* samplenumber = 96600, free = 136416
* store time with each sample
* do not output salinity with each sample
* do not output sound velocity with each sample
* reference pressure = 0.0 db
* do not output density with each sample
* do not output depth with each sample
* A/D cycles to average = 4
* internal pump not installed
* temperature = 23.41 deg C
```

```
* S>
* 1dc
* SBE37-SM 485 V 2.3b 1834
* temperature: 04-mar-22
*   TAO = 9.598777e-06
*   TA1 = 2.755003e-04
*   TA2 = -2.262447e-06
*   TA3 = 1.566359e-07
* conductivity: 04-mar-22
*   G = -1.011899e+00
*   H = 1.395489e-01
*   I = -1.084226e-04
*   J = 3.021298e-05
*   CPCOR = -9.570000e-08
*   CTCOR = 3.250000e-06
*   WBOTC = -6.124698e-06
* rtc: 04-mar-22
*   RTCA0 = 1.000004e+00
*   RTCA1 = 1.583139e-06
*   RTCA2 = -3.071189e-08
```

```
* S>
*END*
```

```
# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 3617
* Sea-Bird SBE37 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Jefrey\Documents\WHOTS-19\w19_07m_3617_data_2ndtry.asc
* Software Version 1.59
* Temperature SN = 3617
* Conductivity SN = 3617
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 26 2023 20:16:43
** WHOTS-18
** 7m
```

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```
* ds
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b SERIAL NO. 3617 06-26-2023 20:15:22
* not logging: received stop command
* sample interval = 180 seconds
* samplenum = 160144, free = 72872
* do not transmit real-time data
* output salinity with each sample
* do not output sound velocity with each sample
* store time with each sample
* number of samples to average = 4
* reference pressure = 7.0 db
* serial sync mode disabled
* wait time after serial sync sampling = 30 seconds
* internal pump not installed
* temperature = 21.56 deg C

* S>
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b 3617
* temperature: 17-nov-21
*   TAO = -2.196350e-04
*   TA1 = 3.113773e-04
*   TA2 = -4.679920e-06
*   TA3 = 2.107474e-07
* conductivity: 17-nov-21
*   G = -1.022418e+00
*   H = 1.462615e-01
*   I = -8.351268e-05
*   J = 3.152163e-05
*   CPCOR = -9.570000e-08
*   CTCOR = 3.250000e-06
*   WBOTC = -1.710719e-05
* rtc: 17-nov-21
*   RTCA0 = 9.999822e-01
*   RTCA1 = 1.686235e-06
*   RTCA2 = -3.276656e-08

* S>
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 6893
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = D:\WHOTS-18_mcat_recovery\w18_15m_6893_data.hex
* Software version SeatermV2 2.8.0.119
* Temperature SN = 6893
* Conductivity SN = 6893
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 21 2023 19:25:35
* sample interval = 60 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>2.8.0.119</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>07-Nov-2018</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
```

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```
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706893'>
*
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.</Manufacturer>
*
*   <FirmwareVersion>3.1</FirmwareVersion>
*
*   <FirmwareDate>Jan 20 2012 17:33:01</FirmwareDate>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41647</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41624A</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41611D</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <MfgDate>17 Mar 2009</MfgDate>
*
*   <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
*
*   <InternalSensors>
*
*     <Sensor id='Temperature'>
*
*       <type>temperature-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03706893</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*     <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*
*       <type>conductivity-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03706893</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*   </InternalSensors>
*
* </HardwareData>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706893'>
*
*   <DateTime>2023-06-21T18:38:28</DateTime>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='7' />
*
*   <Power>
*
*     <vMain> 6.93</vMain>
*
*     <vLith> 3.18</vLith>
*
*   </Power>
*
*   <MemorySummary>
*
*     <Bytes>4806370</Bytes>
```

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```
*
*   <Samples>480637</Samples>
*
*   <SamplesFree>358223</SamplesFree>
*
*   <SampleLength>10</SampleLength>
*
* </MemorySummary>
*
*   <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
*
* </StatusData>
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706893'>
*
*   <PressureInstalled>no</PressureInstalled>
*
*   <ReferencePressure>1.500000e+01</ReferencePressure>
*
*   <PumpInstalled>no</PumpInstalled>
*
*   <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering alternate</SampleDataFormat>
*
*   <OutputSalinity>yes</OutputSalinity>
*
*   <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*
*   <TxRealTime>no</TxRealTime>
*
*   <SampleInterval>60</SampleInterval>
*
*   <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
*
* </ConfigurationData>
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706893'>
*
*   <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>
*
*     <SerialNum>03706893</SerialNum>
*
*     <CalDate>13-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*     <A0>7.877624e-05</A0>
*
*     <A1>2.703790e-04</A1>
*
*     <A2>-2.165396e-06</A2>
*
*     <A3>1.442060e-07</A3>
*
*   </Calibration>
*
*   <Calibration format='WBCOND0' id='Conductivity'>
*
*     <SerialNum>03706893</SerialNum>
*
*     <CalDate>13-Nov-21</CalDate>
```

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```

*
*   <G>-1.028597e+00</G>
*
*   <H>1.583802e-01</H>
*
*   <I>-3.384380e-04</I>
*
*   <J>5.093549e-05</J>
*
*   <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*
*   <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*
*   <WBOTC>2.611541e-07</WBOTC>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
* <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706893'>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='7' />
*
*   <Event type='PON reset' count='7' />
*
* </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
* <![CDATA[
** WHOTS-18
** 15m
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 5
# nvalues = 480637
# units = specified
# name 0 = condOS/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 2 = prM: Pressure [db]
# name 3 = timeJV2: Time, Instrument [julian days]
# name 4 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = -0.000011, 5.609118
# span 1 = 0.0273, 31.9968
# span 2 = 15.000, 15.000
# span 3 = 204.000000, 537.775000
# span 4 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = seconds: 60
# start_time = Jul 23 2022 00:00:00 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="2" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>6893</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>13-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <A0>7.87762400e-005</A0>
#       <A1>2.70379000e-004</A1>
#       <A2>-2.16539600e-006</A2>

```

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```

#       <A3>1.44206000e-007</A3>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </TemperatureSensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="2" >
#     <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
#     <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
#       <SerialNumber>6893</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>13-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
#       <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
#       <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
#       <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
#       <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
#       <Coefficients equation="0" >
#         <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
#         <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
#         <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
#         <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
#         <M>0.0</M>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Coefficients equation="1" >
#         <G>-1.02859700e+000</G>
#         <H>1.58380200e-001</H>
#         <I>-3.38438000e-004</I>
#         <J>5.09354900e-005</J>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#         <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
#         <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
#         <WBOTC>2.61154100e-007</WBOTC>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </ConductivitySensor>
#   </sensor>
# </Sensors>
# datchv_date = Jun 22 2023 14:25:14, 7.26.7.129 [datchv_vars = 4]
# datchv_in = C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_15m_6893_data.
→ hex C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_15m_6893_data.xmlcon
# datchv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 6894
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Jefrey\Documents\WHOTS-18_mcat_recovery\w18_25m_6894_data.hex
* Software version SeatermV2 2.8.0.119
* Temperature SN = 6894
* Conductivity SN = 6894
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 21 2023 20:39:31
* sample interval = 60 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>2.8.0.119</SoftwareVersion>

```

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```
* <BuildDate>07-Nov-2018</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706894'>
*
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.</Manufacturer>
*
*   <FirmwareVersion>3.1</FirmwareVersion>
*
*   <FirmwareDate>Jan 20 2012 17:33:01</FirmwareDate>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41647</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41624A</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41611D</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <MfgDate>17 Mar 2009</MfgDate>
*
*   <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
*
*   <InternalSensors>
*
*     <Sensor id='Temperature'>
*
*       <type>temperature-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03706894</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*     <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*
*       <type>conductivity-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03706894</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*   </InternalSensors>
*
* </HardwareData>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706894'>
*
*   <DateTime>2023-06-21T19:19:43</DateTime>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='5' />
*
*   <Power>
*
*     <vMain> 6.99</vMain>
*
*     <vLith> 3.18</vLith>
*
*   </Power>
```

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```

*
* <MemorySummary>
*
*   <Bytes>4806790</Bytes>
*
*   <Samples>480679</Samples>
*
*   <SamplesFree>358181</SamplesFree>
*
*   <SampleLength>10</SampleLength>
*
* </MemorySummary>
*
* <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
*
* </StatusData>
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706894'>
*
*   <PressureInstalled>no</PressureInstalled>
*
*   <ReferencePressure>2.500000e+01</ReferencePressure>
*
*   <PumpInstalled>no</PumpInstalled>
*
*   <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering</SampleDataFormat>
*
*   <OutputSalinity>yes</OutputSalinity>
*
*   <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*
*   <TxRealTime>no</TxRealTime>
*
*   <SampleInterval>60</SampleInterval>
*
*   <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
*
* </ConfigurationData>
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706894'>
*
*   <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>
*
*     <SerialNum>03706894</SerialNum>
*
*     <CalDate>04-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*     <A0>4.355702e-05</A0>
*
*     <A1>2.764020e-04</A1>
*
*     <A2>-2.643107e-06</A2>
*
*     <A3>1.560671e-07</A3>
*
*   </Calibration>
*
*   <Calibration format='WBCOND0' id='Conductivity'>

```

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```

*
*   <SerialNum>03706894</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>04-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*   <G>-1.002938e+00</G>
*
*   <H>1.441178e-01</H>
*
*   <I>-4.697682e-04</I>
*
*   <J>5.762839e-05</J>
*
*   <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*
*   <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*
*   <WBOTC>-3.464574e-07</WBOTC>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
* <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706894'>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='5' />
*
*   <Event type='PON reset' count='5' />
*
* </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
* <![CDATA[
** WHOTS18 WHOTS18
** 55m 25m
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 5
# nvalues = 480679
# units = specified
# name 0 = condOS/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 2 = prM: Pressure [db]
# name 3 = timeJV2: Time, Instrument [julian days]
# name 4 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = -0.000031, 5.612718
# span 1 = 0.0847, 32.2924
# span 2 = 25.000, 25.000
# span 3 = 204.000000, 537.804167
# span 4 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = seconds: 60
# start_time = Jul 23 2022 00:00:00 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="2" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>6894</SerialNumber>

```

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```

#       <CalibrationDate>04-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <A0>4.35570200e-005</A0>
#       <A1>2.76402000e-004</A1>
#       <A2>-2.64310700e-006</A2>
#       <A3>1.56067100e-007</A3>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </TemperatureSensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="2" >
#     <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
#     <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
#       <SerialNumber>6894</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>04-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
#       <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
#       <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
#       <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
#       <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
#       <Coefficients equation="0" >
#         <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
#         <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
#         <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
#         <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
#         <M>0.0</M>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Coefficients equation="1" >
#         <G>-1.00293800e+000</G>
#         <H>1.44117800e-001</H>
#         <I>-4.69768200e-004</I>
#         <J>5.76283900e-005</J>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#         <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
#         <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
#         <WBOTC>-3.46457400e-007</WBOTC>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </ConductivitySensor>
#   </sensor>
# </Sensors>
# datchv_date = Jun 22 2023 14:30:17, 7.26.7.129 [datchv_vars = 4]
# datchv_in = C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_25m_6894_data.
→ hex C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_25m_6894_data.xmlcon
# datchv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

```

```

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 6896
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Jefrey\Documents\WHOTS-18_mcat_recovery\w18_40m_6896_data.hex
* Software version SeatermV2 2.8.0.119
* Temperature SN = 6896
* Conductivity SN = 6896

```

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```
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 21 2023 22:13:54
* sample interval = 60 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>2.8.0.119</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>07-Nov-2018</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706896'>
*
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.</Manufacturer>
*
*   <FirmwareVersion>3.1</FirmwareVersion>
*
*   <FirmwareDate>Jan 20 2012 17:33:01</FirmwareDate>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41647</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41624A</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41611D</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <MfgDate>18 Mar 2009</MfgDate>
*
*   <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
*
*   <InternalSensors>
*
*     <Sensor id='Temperature'>
*
*       <type>temperature-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03706896</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*     <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*
*       <type>conductivity-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03706896</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*   </InternalSensors>
*
* </HardwareData>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706896'>
*
*   <DateTime>2023-06-21T20:54:19</DateTime>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='2' />
*
*   <Power>
```

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```

*      <vMain> 6.98</vMain>
*
*      <vLith> 3.14</vLith>
*
* </Power>
*
* <MemorySummary>
*
*      <Bytes>4807730</Bytes>
*
*      <Samples>480773</Samples>
*
*      <SamplesFree>358087</SamplesFree>
*
*      <SampleLength>10</SampleLength>
*
* </MemorySummary>
*
* <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
*
* </StatusData>
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706896'>
*
*      <PressureInstalled>no</PressureInstalled>
*
*      <ReferencePressure>4.000000e+01</ReferencePressure>
*
*      <PumpInstalled>no</PumpInstalled>
*
*      <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering</SampleDataFormat>
*
*      <OutputSalinity>yes</OutputSalinity>
*
*      <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*
*      <TxRealTime>no</TxRealTime>
*
*      <SampleInterval>60</SampleInterval>
*
*      <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
*
* </ConfigurationData>
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706896'>
*
*      <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>
*
*          <SerialNum>03706896</SerialNum>
*
*          <CalDate>24-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*          <A0>6.567388e-05</A0>
*
*          <A1>2.670875e-04</A1>
*
*          <A2>-1.883997e-06</A2>
*

```

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```

*      <A3>1.378615e-07</A3>
*
*    </Calibration>
*
*    <Calibration format='WBCONDO' id='Conductivity'>
*
*      <SerialNum>03706896</SerialNum>
*
*      <CalDate>24-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*      <G>-1.004139e+00</G>
*
*      <H>1.542972e-01</H>
*
*      <I>-1.626669e-04</I>
*
*      <J>3.604198e-05</J>
*
*      <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*
*      <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*
*      <WBOTC>4.897022e-07</WBOTC>
*
*    </Calibration>
*
*  </CalibrationCoefficients>
*  <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706896'>
*
*    <EventSummary numEvents='2' />
*
*    <Event type='PON reset' count='1' />
*
*    <Event type='alarm long' count='1' />
*
*  </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
*  <UserHeaderInsert>
*  <![CDATA[
** WHOTS18 WHOTS18
** 55m 40m
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 5
# nvalues = 480773
# units = specified
# name 0 = condOS/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 2 = prM: Pressure [db]
# name 3 = timeJV2: Time, Instrument [julian days]
# name 4 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = -0.000035, 5.612707
# span 1 = 0.2936, 31.9805
# span 2 = 40.000, 40.000
# span 3 = 204.000000, 537.869444
# span 4 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = seconds: 60

```

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```

# start_time = Jul 23 2022 00:00:00 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="2" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>6896</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>24-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <A0>6.56738800e-005</A0>
#       <A1>2.67087500e-004</A1>
#       <A2>-1.88399700e-006</A2>
#       <A3>1.37861500e-007</A3>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </TemperatureSensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="2" >
#     <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
#     <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
#       <SerialNumber>6896</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>24-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
#       <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
#       <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
#       <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
#       <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
#       <Coefficients equation="0" >
#         <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
#         <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
#         <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
#         <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
#         <M>0.0</M>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Coefficients equation="1" >
#         <G>-1.00413900e+000</G>
#         <H>1.54297200e-001</H>
#         <I>-1.62666900e-004</I>
#         <J>3.60419800e-005</J>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#         <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
#         <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
#         <WBOTC>4.89702200e-007</WBOTC>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </ConductivitySensor>
#   </sensor>
# </Sensors>
# datchv_date = Jun 22 2023 14:28:11, 7.26.7.129 [datchv_vars = 4]
# datchv_in = C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_40m_6896_data.
→hex C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_40m_6896_data.xmlcon
# datchv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

```

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```
# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 6887
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = D:\WHOTS-18_mcat_recovery\w18_45m_6887_data.hex
* Software version SeatermV2 2.8.0.119
* Temperature SN = 6887
* Conductivity SN = 6887
* System Upload Time = Jun 21 2023 21:05:25
* sample interval = 75 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>2.8.0.119</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>07-Nov-2018</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706887'>
*
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.</Manufacturer>
*
*   <FirmwareVersion>3.1</FirmwareVersion>
*
*   <FirmwareDate>Jan 20 2012 17:33:01</FirmwareDate>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41647</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41610B</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41611D</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <MfgDate>12 Mar 2009</MfgDate>
*
*   <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
*
*   <InternalSensors>
*
*     <Sensor id='Temperature'>
*
*       <type>temperature-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03706887</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*     <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*
*       <type>conductivity-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03706887</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*     <Sensor id='Pressure'>
*
*       <type>strain-0</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>2651319</SerialNumber>
```

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```
*
*   </Sensor>
*
* </InternalSensors>
*
* </HardwareData>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706887'>
*
*   <DateTime>2023-06-21T20:35:52</DateTime>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1'/>
*
*   <Power>
*
*     <vMain> 7.03</vMain>
*
*     <vLith> 3.21</vLith>
*
*   </Power>
*
*   <MemorySummary>
*
*     <Bytes>5769030</Bytes>
*
*     <Samples>384602</Samples>
*
*     <SamplesFree>174638</SamplesFree>
*
*     <SampleLength>15</SampleLength>
*
*   </MemorySummary>
*
*   <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
*
* </StatusData>
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706887'>
*
*   <PressureInstalled>yes</PressureInstalled>
*
*   <PumpInstalled>no</PumpInstalled>
*
*   <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering</SampleDataFormat>
*
*   <OutputSalinity>yes</OutputSalinity>
*
*   <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*
*   <TxRealTime>no</TxRealTime>
*
*   <SampleInterval>75</SampleInterval>
*
*   <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
*
* </ConfigurationData>
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706887'>
*
```

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```
* <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>
*
*   <SerialNum>03706887</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>19-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*   <A0>7.349799e-05</A0>
*
*   <A1>2.755167e-04</A1>
*
*   <A2>-2.572488e-06</A2>
*
*   <A3>1.557271e-07</A3>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* <Calibration format='WBCONDO' id='Conductivity'>
*
*   <SerialNum>03706887</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>19-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*   <G>-1.014648e+00</G>
*
*   <H>1.501699e-01</H>
*
*   <I>-2.489897e-04</I>
*
*   <J>4.121820e-05</J>
*
*   <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*
*   <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*
*   <WBOTC>4.802827e-07</WBOTC>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* <Calibration format='STRAIN0' id='Pressure'>
*
*   <SerialNum>2651319</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>02-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*   <PA0>-2.039715e-01</PA0>
*
*   <PA1>4.893293e-03</PA1>
*
*   <PA2>-2.294833e-11</PA2>
*
*   <PTCA0>5.248083e+05</PTCA0>
*
*   <PTCA1>1.930555e+00</PTCA1>
*
*   <PTCA2>-1.506502e-01</PTCA2>
*
```

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```

*      <PTCB0>2.626762e+01</PTCB0>
*
*      <PTCB1>1.250000e-04</PTCB1>
*
*      <PTCB2>0.000000e+00</PTCB2>
*
*      <PTempa0>-7.196676e+01</PTempa0>
*
*      <PTempa1>5.039060e-02</PTempa1>
*
*      <PTempa2>-5.759730e-07</PTempa2>
*
*      <POFFSET>6.000000e-02</POFFSET>
*
*      <PRANGE>1.450000e+03</PRANGE>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
* <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706887'>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*
*   <Event type='PON reset' count='1' />
*
* </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
* <![CDATA[
** WHOTS-18
** 45m
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 5
# nvalues = 384602
# units = specified
# name 0 = condOS/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 2 = prdM: Pressure, Strain Gauge [db]
# name 3 = timeJV2: Time, Instrument [julian days]
# name 4 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = -0.000014, 5.609808
# span 1 = 4.0690, 31.9483
# span 2 = -0.331, 48.792
# span 3 = 204.000000, 537.855035
# span 4 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = seconds: 75
# start_time = Jul 23 2022 00:00:00 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="3" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>6887</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>19-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <A0>7.34979900e-005</A0>
#       <A1>2.75516700e-004</A1>

```

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```

#      <A2>-2.57248800e-006</A2>
#      <A3>1.55727100e-007</A3>
#      <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#      <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#    </TemperatureSensor>
#  </sensor>
#  <sensor Channel="2" >
#    <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
#    <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
#      <SerialNumber>6887</SerialNumber>
#      <CalibrationDate>19-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#      <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
#      <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
#      <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
#      <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
#      <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
#      <Coefficients equation="0" >
#        <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
#        <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
#        <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
#        <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
#        <M>0.0</M>
#        <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#      </Coefficients>
#      <Coefficients equation="1" >
#        <G>-1.01464800e+000</G>
#        <H>1.50169900e-001</H>
#        <I>-2.48989700e-004</I>
#        <J>4.12182000e-005</J>
#        <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#        <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
#        <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
#        <WBOTC>4.80282700e-007</WBOTC>
#      </Coefficients>
#      <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#      <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#    </ConductivitySensor>
#  </sensor>
#  <sensor Channel="3" >
#    <!-- Count, Pressure, Strain Gauge -->
#    <PressureSensor SensorID="46" >
#      <SerialNumber>2651319</SerialNumber>
#      <CalibrationDate>02-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#      <PA0>-2.03971500e-001</PA0>
#      <PA1>4.89329300e-003</PA1>
#      <PA2>-2.29483300e-011</PA2>
#      <PTempa0>-7.19667600e+001</PTempa0>
#      <PTempa1>5.03906000e-002</PTempa1>
#      <PTempa2>-5.75973000e-007</PTempa2>
#      <PTCA0>5.24808300e+005</PTCA0>
#      <PTCA1>1.93055500e+000</PTCA1>
#      <PTCA2>-1.50650200e-001</PTCA2>
#      <PTCB0>2.62676200e+001</PTCB0>
#      <PTCB1>1.25000000e-004</PTCB1>
#      <PTCB2>0.00000000e+000</PTCB2>
#      <Offset>0.000000</Offset>

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```

#     </PressureSensor>
#   </sensor>
# </Sensors>
# datcnv_date = Jun 22 2023 14:29:28, 7.26.7.129 [datcnv_vars = 4]
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_45m_6887_data.
hex C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_45m_6887_data.xml con
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 6897
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Jefrey\Documents\WHOTS-18_mcat_recovery\w18_50m_6897_data.hex
* Software version SeatermV2 2.8.0.119
* Temperature SN = 6897
* Conductivity SN = 6897
* System Upload Time = Jun 21 2023 18:42:43
* sample interval = 60 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>2.8.0.119</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>07-Nov-2018</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706897'>
*
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.</Manufacturer>
*
*   <FirmwareVersion>3.1</FirmwareVersion>
*
*   <FirmwareDate>Jan 20 2012 17:33:01</FirmwareDate>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41647</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41624A</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41611D</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <MfgDate>18 Mar 2009</MfgDate>
*
*   <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
*
*   <InternalSensors>
*
*     <Sensor id='Temperature'>
*
*       <type>temperature-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03706897</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*     <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*
*       <type>conductivity-1</type>

```

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```
*
*       <SerialNumber>03706897</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*   </InternalSensors>
*
* </HardwareData>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706897'>
*
*   <DateTime>2023-06-21T16:35:45</DateTime>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*
*   <Power>
*
*     <vMain> 6.99</vMain>
*
*     <vLith> 3.12</vLith>
*
*   </Power>
*
*   <MemorySummary>
*
*     <Bytes>4805140</Bytes>
*
*     <Samples>480514</Samples>
*
*     <SamplesFree>358346</SamplesFree>
*
*     <SampleLength>10</SampleLength>
*
*   </MemorySummary>
*
*   <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
*
* </StatusData>
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706897'>
*
*   <PressureInstalled>no</PressureInstalled>
*
*   <ReferencePressure>5.000000e+01</ReferencePressure>
*
*   <PumpInstalled>no</PumpInstalled>
*
*   <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering</SampleDataFormat>
*
*   <OutputSalinity>yes</OutputSalinity>
*
*   <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*
*   <TxRealTime>no</TxRealTime>
*
*   <SampleInterval>60</SampleInterval>
*
*   <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
```

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```

*
* </ConfigurationData>
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706897'>
*
*   <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>
*
*     <SerialNum>03706897</SerialNum>
*
*     <CalDate>04-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*     <A0>3.893372e-05</A0>
*
*     <A1>2.741949e-04</A1>
*
*     <A2>-2.497047e-06</A2>
*
*     <A3>1.508359e-07</A3>
*
*   </Calibration>
*
*   <Calibration format='WBCOND0' id='Conductivity'>
*
*     <SerialNum>03706897</SerialNum>
*
*     <CalDate>04-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*     <G>-1.005567e+00</G>
*
*     <H>1.526919e-01</H>
*
*     <I>-3.267329e-04</I>
*
*     <J>4.847325e-05</J>
*
*     <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*
*     <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*
*     <WBOTC>1.296675e-07</WBOTC>
*
*   </Calibration>
*
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
* <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706897'>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*
*   <Event type='PON reset' count='1' />
*
* </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
* <![CDATA[
** WHOTS18 WHOTS18
** 55m 50m
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>

```

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```

# nquan = 5
# nvalues = 480514
# units = specified
# name 0 = condOS/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 2 = prM: Pressure [db]
# name 3 = timeJV2: Time, Instrument [julian days]
# name 4 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = 0.000023, 5.618516
# span 1 = 0.2104, 27.4332
# span 2 = 50.000, 50.000
# span 3 = 204.000000, 537.689583
# span 4 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = seconds: 60
# start_time = Jul 23 2022 00:00:00 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="2" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>6897</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>04-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <A0>3.89337200e-005</A0>
#       <A1>2.74194900e-004</A1>
#       <A2>-2.49704700e-006</A2>
#       <A3>1.50835900e-007</A3>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </TemperatureSensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="2" >
#     <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
#     <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
#       <SerialNumber>6897</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>04-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
#       <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
#       <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
#       <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
#       <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
#       <Coefficients equation="0" >
#         <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
#         <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
#         <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
#         <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
#         <M>0.0</M>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Coefficients equation="1" >
#         <G>-1.00556700e+000</G>
#         <H>1.52691900e-001</H>
#         <I>-3.26732900e-004</I>
#         <J>4.84732500e-005</J>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#         <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
#       <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->

```

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```

#       <WBOTC>1.29667500e-007</WBOTC>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.00000</Offset>
#       </ConductivitySensor>
#     </sensor>
# </Sensors>
# datcnv_date = Jun 22 2023 14:33:23, 7.26.7.129 [datcnv_vars = 4]
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_50m_6897_data.
hex C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_50m_6897_data.xmlcon
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

```

```

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 6898
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Jefrey\Documents\WHOTS-18_mcat_recovery\w18_55m_6898_data.hex
* Software version SeatermV2 2.8.0.119
* Temperature SN = 6898
* Conductivity SN = 6898
* System Upload Time = Jun 20 2023 22:42:39
* sample interval = 60 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>2.8.0.119</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>07-Nov-2018</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706898'>
*
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.</Manufacturer>
*
*   <FirmwareVersion>3.1</FirmwareVersion>
*
*   <FirmwareDate>Jan 20 2012 17:33:01</FirmwareDate>
*
*   <PCBAAssembly>41647</PCBAAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAAssembly>41624A</PCBAAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAAssembly>41611D</PCBAAssembly>
*
*   <MfgDate>18 Mar 2009</MfgDate>
*
*   <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
*
*   <InternalSensors>
*
*     <Sensor id='Temperature'>
*
*       <type>temperature-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03706898</SerialNumber>
*

```

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```

*     </Sensor>
*
*     <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*
*         <type>conductivity-1</type>
*
*         <SerialNumber>03706898</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
* </InternalSensors>
*
* </HardwareData>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706898'>
*
*     <DateTime>2023-06-20T18:58:00</DateTime>
*
*     <EventSummary numEvents='13' />
*
*     <Power>
*
*         <vMain> 7.11</vMain>
*
*         <vLith> 3.10</vLith>
*
*     </Power>
*
*     <MemorySummary>
*
*         <Bytes>4792080</Bytes>
*
*         <Samples>479208</Samples>
*
*         <SamplesFree>359652</SamplesFree>
*
*         <SampleLength>10</SampleLength>
*
*     </MemorySummary>
*
*     <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
*
* </StatusData>
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706898'>
*
*     <PressureInstalled>no</PressureInstalled>
*
*     <ReferencePressure>5.500000e+01</ReferencePressure>
*
*     <PumpInstalled>no</PumpInstalled>
*
*     <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering</SampleDataFormat>
*
*     <OutputSalinity>yes</OutputSalinity>
*
*     <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*

```

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```
* <TxRealTime>yes</TxRealTime>
*
* <SampleInterval>60</SampleInterval>
*
* <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
*
* </ConfigurationData>
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706898'>
*
* <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>
*
* <SerialNum>03706898</SerialNum>
*
* <CalDate>02-Dec-21</CalDate>
*
* <A0>9.450561e-05</A0>
*
* <A1>2.642366e-04</A1>
*
* <A2>-1.702430e-06</A2>
*
* <A3>1.318726e-07</A3>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* <Calibration format='WBCOND0' id='Conductivity'>
*
* <SerialNum>03706898</SerialNum>
*
* <CalDate>02-Dec-21</CalDate>
*
* <G>-1.019711e+00</G>
*
* <H>1.534926e-01</H>
*
* <I>-1.896768e-04</I>
*
* <J>3.825842e-05</J>
*
* <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*
* <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*
* <WBOTC>2.261411e-07</WBOTC>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
* <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706898'>
*
* <EventSummary numEvents='13' />
*
* <Event type='PON reset' count='13' />
*
* </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
```

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```

* <![CDATA[
** WHOTS18
** 55m
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 5
# nvalues = 479208
# units = specified
# name 0 = condOS/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 2 = prM: Pressure [db]
# name 3 = timeJV2: Time, Instrument [julian days]
# name 4 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = 5.9090e-07, 5.608256
# span 1 = 0.2780, 27.4126
# span 2 = 55.000, 55.000
# span 3 = 204.000000, 536.782639
# span 4 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = seconds: 60
# start_time = Jul 23 2022 00:00:00 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="2" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>6898</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>02-Dec-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <A0>9.45056100e-005</A0>
#       <A1>2.64236600e-004</A1>
#       <A2>-1.70243000e-006</A2>
#       <A3>1.31872600e-007</A3>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </TemperatureSensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="2" >
#     <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
#     <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
#       <SerialNumber>6898</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>02-Dec-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
#       <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
#       <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
#       <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
#       <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
#       <Coefficients equation="0" >
#         <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
#         <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
#         <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
#         <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
#         <M>0.0</M>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Coefficients equation="1" >
#         <G>-1.01971100e+000</G>
#         <H>1.53492600e-001</H>

```

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```

#      <I>-1.89676800e-004</I>
#      <J>3.82584200e-005</J>
#      <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#      <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
#      <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
#      <WBOTC>2.26141100e-007</WBOTC>
#      </Coefficients>
#      <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#      <Offset>0.00000</Offset>
#      </ConductivitySensor>
#    </sensor>
#  </Sensors>
# datcnv_date = Jun 22 2023 14:37:38, 7.26.7.129 [datcnv_vars = 4]
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_55m_6898_data.
→hex C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_55m_6898_data.xmlcon
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 6899
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Jefrey\Documents\WHOTS-18_mcat_recovery\w18_65m_6899_data.hex
* Software version SeatermV2 2.8.0.119
* Temperature SN = 6899
* Conductivity SN = 6899
* System Upload Time = Jun 21 2023 16:23:52
* sample interval = 60 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>2.8.0.119</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>07-Nov-2018</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706899'>
*
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.</Manufacturer>
*
*   <FirmwareVersion>3.1</FirmwareVersion>
*
*   <FirmwareDate>Jan 20 2012 17:33:01</FirmwareDate>
*
*   <PCBAAssembly>41647</PCBAAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAAssembly>41624A</PCBAAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAAssembly>41611D</PCBAAssembly>
*
*   <MfgDate>18 Mar 2009</MfgDate>
*
*   <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
*
*   <InternalSensors>
*
*     <Sensor id='Temperature'>

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```

*      <type>temperature-1</type>
*
*      <SerialNumber>03706899</SerialNumber>
*
*    </Sensor>
*
*    <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*
*      <type>conductivity-1</type>
*
*      <SerialNumber>03706899</SerialNumber>
*
*    </Sensor>
*
*  </InternalSensors>
*
* </HardwareData>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706899'>
*
*   <DateTime>2023-06-21T15:04:33</DateTime>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*
*   <Power>
*
*     <vMain> 6.92</vMain>
*
*     <vLith> 3.08</vLith>
*
*   </Power>
*
*   <MemorySummary>
*
*     <Bytes>4804240</Bytes>
*
*     <Samples>480424</Samples>
*
*     <SamplesFree>358436</SamplesFree>
*
*     <SampleLength>10</SampleLength>
*
*   </MemorySummary>
*
*   <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
*
* </StatusData>
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706899'>
*
*   <PressureInstalled>no</PressureInstalled>
*
*   <ReferencePressure>6.500000e+01</ReferencePressure>
*
*   <PumpInstalled>no</PumpInstalled>
*
*   <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering</SampleDataFormat>
*

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```

* <OutputSalinity>no</OutputSalinity>
*
* <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*
* <TxRealTime>no</TxRealTime>
*
* <SampleInterval>60</SampleInterval>
*
* <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
*
* </ConfigurationData>
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706899'>
*
*   <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>
*
*     <SerialNum>03706899</SerialNum>
*
*     <CalDate>13-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*     <A0>5.929491e-05</A0>
*
*     <A1>2.752034e-04</A1>
*
*     <A2>-2.505302e-06</A2>
*
*     <A3>1.544594e-07</A3>
*
*   </Calibration>
*
*   <Calibration format='WBCOND0' id='Conductivity'>
*
*     <SerialNum>03706899</SerialNum>
*
*     <CalDate>13-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*     <G>-1.021210e+00</G>
*
*     <H>1.508593e-01</H>
*
*     <I>-2.971312e-04</I>
*
*     <J>4.524669e-05</J>
*
*     <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*
*     <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*
*     <WBOTC>3.837484e-07</WBOTC>
*
*   </Calibration>
*
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
* <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706899'>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*

```

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```

*   <Event type='PON reset' count='1' />
*
* </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
* <![CDATA[
** WHOTS18 WHOTS18
** 55m 65m
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 5
# nvalues = 480424
# units = specified
# name 0 = condOS/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 2 = prM: Pressure [db]
# name 3 = timeJV2: Time, Instrument [julian days]
# name 4 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = -0.000019, 5.593476
# span 1 = 0.1927, 27.3415
# span 2 = 65.000, 65.000
# span 3 = 204.000000, 537.627083
# span 4 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = seconds: 60
# start_time = Jul 23 2022 00:00:00 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="2" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>6899</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>13-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <A0>5.92949100e-005</A0>
#       <A1>2.75203400e-004</A1>
#       <A2>-2.50530200e-006</A2>
#       <A3>1.54459400e-007</A3>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </TemperatureSensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="2" >
#     <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
#     <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
#       <SerialNumber>6899</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>13-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
#       <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
#       <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
#       <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
#       <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
#       <Coefficients equation="0" >
#         <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
#         <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
#         <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
#         <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
#         <M>0.0</M>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>

```

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```

#      </Coefficients>
#      <Coefficients equation="1" >
#      <G>-1.02121000e+000</G>
#      <H>1.50859300e-001</H>
#      <I>-2.97131200e-004</I>
#      <J>4.52466900e-005</J>
#      <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#      <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
#      <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
#      <WBOTC>3.83748400e-007</WBOTC>
#      </Coefficients>
#      <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#      <Offset>0.00000</Offset>
#      </ConductivitySensor>
#    </sensor>
#  </Sensors>
# datcnv_date = Jun 22 2023 14:34:00, 7.26.7.129 [datcnv_vars = 4]
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_65m_6899_data.
→hex C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_65m_6899_data.xmlcon
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 3618
* Sea-Bird SBE37 Data File:
* FileName = D:\WHOTS-18_mcat_recovery\w18_75m_3618_data.asc
* Software Version 1.59
* Temperature SN = 3618
* Conductivity SN = 3618
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 20 2023 22:32:39
** WHOTS-18
** 75m
* ds
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b SERIAL NO. 3618    20 Jun 2023  22:31:26
* not logging: received stop command
* sample interval = 180 seconds
* samplenummer = 159809, free = 73207
* do not transmit real-time data
* output salinity with each sample
* do not output sound velocity with each sample
* store time with each sample
* number of samples to average = 4
* reference pressure = 75.0 db
* serial sync mode disabled
* wait time after serial sync sampling = 30 seconds
* internal pump not installed
* temperature = 19.07 deg C

* S>
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b 3618
* temperature: 04-nov-21
*   TAO = -7.245919e-05
*   TA1 = 2.883522e-04
*   TA2 = -3.225646e-06
*   TA3 = 1.790927e-07

```

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```
* conductivity: 04-nov-21
*   G = -1.007241e+00
*   H = 1.387097e-01
*   I = 2.797664e-04
*   J = 1.572639e-05
*   CPCOR = -9.570000e-08
*   CTCOR = 3.250000e-06
*   WBOTC = -1.110161e-05
* rtc: 04-nov-21
*   RTCA0 = 9.999764e-01
*   RTCA1 = 1.754173e-06
*   RTCA2 = -3.347873e-08

* S>
*END*
```

```
# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 3634
* Sea-Bird SBE37 Data File:
* FileName = D:\WHOTS-18_mcat_recovery\w18__85m_3634_data.asc
* Software Version 1.59
* Temperature SN = 3634
* Conductivity SN = 3634
* System Upload Time = Jun 21 2023 05:37:43
** WHOTS-18
** 85m
* ds
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b SERIAL NO. 3634 06-21-2023 05:36:24
* not logging: received stop command
* sample interval = 180 seconds
* samplenum = 159951, free = 73065
* do not transmit real-time data
* output salinity with each sample
* do not output sound velocity with each sample
* store time with each sample
* number of samples to average = 4
* reference pressure = 85.0 db
* serial sync mode disabled
* wait time after serial sync sampling = 30 seconds
* internal pump not installed
* temperature = 19.98 deg C

* S>
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b 3634
* temperature: 13-nov-21
*   TAO = -4.900056e-05
*   TA1 = 2.811162e-04
*   TA2 = -2.863184e-06
*   TA3 = 1.640679e-07
* conductivity: 13-nov-21
*   G = -1.019645e+00
*   H = 1.467542e-01
*   I = -1.326342e-04
*   J = 3.543132e-05
```

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```
*   CPCOR = -9.570000e-08
*   CTCOR = 3.250000e-06
*   WBOTC = -1.225817e-05
* rtc: 13-nov-21
*   RTCA0 = 9.999831e-01
*   RTCA1 = 1.739713e-06
*   RTCA2 = -3.278574e-08

* S>
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 3670
* Sea-Bird SBE37 Data File:
* FileName = D:\WHOTS-18_mcat_recovery\w18_95m_3870_data.asc
* Software Version 1.59
* Temperature SN = 3670
* Conductivity SN = 3670
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 20 2023 19:34:55
** WHOTS-18
** 95m
* ds
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b SERIAL NO. 3670    20 Jun 2023  19:33:36
* not logging: received stop command
* sample interval = 240 seconds
* samplenum = 119813, free = 70837
* do not transmit real-time data
* do not output salinity with each sample
* do not output sound velocity with each sample
* store time with each sample
* number of samples to average = 4
* serial sync mode disabled
* wait time after serial sync sampling = 30 seconds
* internal pump not installed
* temperature = 18.83 deg C

* S>
* SBE37-SM V 2.6b 3670
* temperature: 19-nov-21
*   TAO = -2.217529e-04
*   TA1 = 3.125302e-04
*   TA2 = -4.715840e-06
*   TA3 = 2.118395e-07
* conductivity: 19-nov-21
*   G = -1.012115e+00
*   H = 1.231429e-01
*   I = -9.476538e-05
*   J = 2.603631e-05
*   CPCOR = -9.570000e-08
*   CTCOR = 3.250000e-06
*   WBOTC = -8.688073e-06
* pressure S/N 5701, range = 1450 psia: 03-nov-21
*   PA0 = -5.344184e-02
*   PA1 = 6.860336e-02
*   PA2 = -4.245815e-09
```

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```

*   PTCA0 = -2.001202e+02
*   PTCA1 = -6.639637e-02
*   PTCA2 = 1.408200e-03
*   PTCSB0 = 2.491775e+01
*   PTCSB1 = -6.500000e-04
*   PTCSB2 = 0.000000e+00
*   POFFSET = -1.230000e+00
* rtc: 19-nov-21
*   RTCA0 = 9.999888e-01
*   RTCA1 = 1.835673e-06
*   RTCA2 = -3.505132e-08

* S>
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 6889
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Jefrey\Documents\WHOTS-18_mcat_recovery\w18_105m_6889_data.hex
* Software version SeatermV2 2.8.0.119
* Temperature SN = 6889
* Conductivity SN = 6889
* System Upload Time = Jun 21 2023 06:28:47
* sample interval = 75 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>2.8.0.119</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>07-Nov-2018</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706889'>
*
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.</Manufacturer>
*
*   <FirmwareVersion>3.1</FirmwareVersion>
*
*   <FirmwareDate>Jan 20 2012 17:33:01</FirmwareDate>
*
*   <PCBAsembly>41647</PCBAsembly>
*
*   <PCBAsembly>41610B</PCBAsembly>
*
*   <PCBAsembly>41611D</PCBAsembly>
*
*   <MfgDate>13 Mar 2009</MfgDate>
*
*   <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
*
*   <InternalSensors>
*
*     <Sensor id='Temperature'>
*
*       <type>temperature-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03706889</SerialNumber>

```

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```
*
*   </Sensor>
*
*   <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*
*     <type>conductivity-1</type>
*
*     <SerialNumber>03706889</SerialNumber>
*
*   </Sensor>
*
*   <Sensor id='Pressure'>
*
*     <type>strain-0</type>
*
*     <SerialNumber>2651321</SerialNumber>
*
*   </Sensor>
*
* </InternalSensors>
*
* </HardwareData>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706889'>
*
*   <DateTime>2023-06-21T03:56:07</DateTime>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*
*   <Power>
*
*     <vMain> 6.85</vMain>
*
*     <vLith> 3.14</vLith>
*
*   </Power>
*
*   <MemorySummary>
*
*     <Bytes>5756400</Bytes>
*
*     <Samples>383760</Samples>
*
*     <SamplesFree>175480</SamplesFree>
*
*     <SampleLength>15</SampleLength>
*
*   </MemorySummary>
*
*   <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
*
* </StatusData>
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706889'>
*
*   <PressureInstalled>yes</PressureInstalled>
*
*   <PumpInstalled>no</PumpInstalled>
```

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```
*
* <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering</SampleDataFormat>
*
* <OutputSalinity>yes</OutputSalinity>
*
* <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*
* <TxRealTime>no</TxRealTime>
*
* <SampleInterval>75</SampleInterval>
*
* <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
*
* </ConfigurationData>
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706889'>
*
*   <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>
*
*     <SerialNum>03706889</SerialNum>
*
*     <CalDate>10-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*     <A0>1.016718e-04</A0>
*
*     <A1>2.610141e-04</A1>
*
*     <A2>-1.424935e-06</A2>
*
*     <A3>1.246406e-07</A3>
*
*   </Calibration>
*
*   <Calibration format='WBCOND0' id='Conductivity'>
*
*     <SerialNum>03706889</SerialNum>
*
*     <CalDate>10-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*     <G>-9.999722e-01</G>
*
*     <H>1.501833e-01</H>
*
*     <I>-2.695119e-04</I>
*
*     <J>4.302018e-05</J>
*
*     <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*
*     <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*
*     <WBOTC>1.290011e-07</WBOTC>
*
*   </Calibration>
*
*   <Calibration format='STRAIN0' id='Pressure'>
```

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```

*      <SerialNum>2651321</SerialNum>
*
*      <CalDate>02-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*      <PA0>3.430363e-01</PA0>
*
*      <PA1>5.078449e-03</PA1>
*
*      <PA2>-1.305139e-11</PA2>
*
*      <PTCA0>5.247892e+05</PTCA0>
*
*      <PTCA1>2.344197e+00</PTCA1>
*
*      <PTCA2>3.608461e-03</PTCA2>
*
*      <PTCB0>2.627775e+01</PTCB0>
*
*      <PTCB1>-1.250000e-03</PTCB1>
*
*      <PTCB2>0.000000e+00</PTCB2>
*
*      <PTempa0>-6.960694e+01</PTempa0>
*
*      <PTempa1>5.057417e-02</PTempa1>
*
*      <PTempa2>-4.275673e-07</PTempa2>
*
*      <POFFSET>7.999999e-02</POFFSET>
*
*      <PRANGE>1.450000e+03</PRANGE>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
* <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706889'>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*
*   <Event type='PON reset' count='1' />
*
* </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
* <![CDATA[
** WHOTS18 WHOTS18
** 55m 105m
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 5
# nvalues = 383760
# units = specified
# name 0 = condOS/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 2 = prdM: Pressure, Strain Gauge [db]
# name 3 = timeJV2: Time, Instrument [julian days]
# name 4 = flag: 0.000e+00

```

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```

# span 0 = 0.000014, 5.459091
# span 1 = 0.9936, 26.4614
# span 2 = -0.594, 108.979
# span 3 = 204.000000, 537.124132
# span 4 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = seconds: 75
# start_time = Jul 23 2022 00:00:00 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="3" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>6889</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>10-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <A0>1.01671800e-004</A0>
#       <A1>2.61014100e-004</A1>
#       <A2>-1.42493500e-006</A2>
#       <A3>1.24640600e-007</A3>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </TemperatureSensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="2" >
#     <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
#     <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
#       <SerialNumber>6889</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>10-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
#       <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
#       <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
#       <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
#       <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
#       <Coefficients equation="0" >
#         <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
#         <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
#         <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
#         <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
#         <M>0.0</M>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Coefficients equation="1" >
#         <G>-9.99972200e-001</G>
#         <H>1.50183300e-001</H>
#         <I>-2.69511900e-004</I>
#         <J>4.30201800e-005</J>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#         <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
#         <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
#         <WBOTC>1.29001100e-007</WBOTC>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </ConductivitySensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="3" >
#     <!-- Count, Pressure, Strain Gauge -->

```

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```

#   <PressureSensor SensorID="46" >
#     <SerialNumber>2651321</SerialNumber>
#     <CalibrationDate>02-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#     <PA0>3.43036300e-001</PA0>
#     <PA1>5.07844900e-003</PA1>
#     <PA2>-1.30513900e-011</PA2>
#     <PTempa0>-6.96069400e+001</PTempa0>
#     <PTempa1>5.05741700e-002</PTempa1>
#     <PTempa2>-4.27567300e-007</PTempa2>
#     <PTCA0>5.24789200e+005</PTCA0>
#     <PTCA1>2.34419700e+000</PTCA1>
#     <PTCA2>3.60846100e-003</PTCA2>
#     <PTCB0>2.62777500e+001</PTCB0>
#     <PTCB1>-1.25000000e-003</PTCB1>
#     <PTCB2>0.00000000e+000</PTCB2>
#     <Offset>0.000000</Offset>
#   </PressureSensor>
# </sensor>
# </Sensors>
# datcnv_date = Jun 22 2023 14:36:18, 7.26.7.129 [datcnv_vars = 4]
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_105m_6889_
→data.hex C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_105m_6889_data.
→xmlcon
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

```

```

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 6890
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Jefrey\Documents\WHOTS-18_mcat_recovery\w18_120m_6890_data.hex
* Software version SeatermV2 2.8.0.119
* Temperature SN = 6890
* Conductivity SN = 6890
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 21 2023 01:35:59
* sample interval = 75 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>2.8.0.119</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>07-Nov-2018</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706890'>
*
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.</Manufacturer>
*
*   <FirmwareVersion>3.1</FirmwareVersion>
*
*   <FirmwareDate>Jan 20 2012 17:33:01</FirmwareDate>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41647</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41610B</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41611D</PCBAssembly>

```

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```
*
* <MfgDate>13 Mar 2009</MfgDate>
*
* <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
*
* <InternalSensors>
*
*   <Sensor id='Temperature'>
*
*     <type>temperature-1</type>
*
*     <SerialNumber>03706890</SerialNumber>
*
*   </Sensor>
*
*   <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*
*     <type>conductivity-1</type>
*
*     <SerialNumber>03706890</SerialNumber>
*
*   </Sensor>
*
*   <Sensor id='Pressure'>
*
*     <type>strain-0</type>
*
*     <SerialNumber>2651322</SerialNumber>
*
*   </Sensor>
*
* </InternalSensors>
*
* </HardwareData>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706890'>
*
*   <DateTime>2023-06-20T23:03:29</DateTime>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*
*   <Power>
*
*     <vMain> 6.88</vMain>
*
*     <vLith> 3.12</vLith>
*
*   </Power>
*
*   <MemorySummary>
*
*     <Bytes>5753505</Bytes>
*
*     <Samples>383567</Samples>
*
*     <SamplesFree>175673</SamplesFree>
*
*   </MemorySummary>
*
* </StatusData>
*
* </WHOTS-18>
```

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```
*      <SampleLength>15</SampleLength>
*
*    </MemorySummary>
*
*    <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
*
*  </StatusData>
*  <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706890'>
*
*    <PressureInstalled>yes</PressureInstalled>
*
*    <PumpInstalled>no</PumpInstalled>
*
*    <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering</SampleDataFormat>
*
*    <OutputSalinity>yes</OutputSalinity>
*
*    <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*
*    <TxRealTime>no</TxRealTime>
*
*    <SampleInterval>75</SampleInterval>
*
*    <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
*
*  </ConfigurationData>
*  <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706890'>
*
*    <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>
*
*      <SerialNum>03706890</SerialNum>
*
*      <CalDate>19-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*      <A0>4.151677e-05</A0>
*
*      <A1>2.718070e-04</A1>
*
*      <A2>-2.312460e-06</A2>
*
*      <A3>1.463529e-07</A3>
*
*    </Calibration>
*
*    <Calibration format='WBCONDO' id='Conductivity'>
*
*      <SerialNum>03706890</SerialNum>
*
*      <CalDate>19-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*      <G>-1.018172e+00</G>
*
*      <H>1.598801e-01</H>
*
*      <I>-2.824857e-04</I>
*
*
```

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```

*      <J>4.703804e-05</J>
*
*      <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*
*      <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*
*      <WBOTC>1.319142e-07</WBOTC>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* <Calibration format='STRAIN0' id='Pressure'>
*
*      <SerialNum>2651322</SerialNum>
*
*      <CalDate>03-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*      <PA0>-1.945177e-01</PA0>
*
*      <PA1>4.560412e-03</PA1>
*
*      <PA2>-1.846598e-11</PA2>
*
*      <PTCA0>5.247655e+05</PTCA0>
*
*      <PTCA1>1.259274e+00</PTCA1>
*
*      <PTCA2>-1.174853e-01</PTCA2>
*
*      <PTCB0>2.625275e+01</PTCB0>
*
*      <PTCB1>-2.500000e-04</PTCB1>
*
*      <PTCB2>0.000000e+00</PTCB2>
*
*      <PTEMPA0>-7.286258e+01</PTEMPA0>
*
*      <PTEMPA1>5.015612e-02</PTEMPA1>
*
*      <PTEMPA2>-4.160485e-07</PTEMPA2>
*
*      <POFFSET>4.000000e-02</POFFSET>
*
*      <PRANGE>1.450000e+03</PRANGE>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
* <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706890'>
*
*      <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*
*      <Event type='PON reset' count='1' />
*
* </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
* <![CDATA[

```

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```

** WHOTS18 WHOTS-18
** 55m 120m
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 5
# nvalues = 383567
# units = specified
# name 0 = condOS/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 2 = prdM: Pressure, Strain Gauge [db]
# name 3 = timeJV2: Time, Instrument [julian days]
# name 4 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = 0.000002, 5.415308
# span 1 = 1.0164, 27.9001
# span 2 = -0.259, 123.876
# span 3 = 204.000000, 536.956597
# span 4 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = seconds: 75
# start_time = Jul 23 2022 00:00:00 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="3" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>6890</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>19-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <A0>4.15167700e-005</A0>
#       <A1>2.71807000e-004</A1>
#       <A2>-2.31246000e-006</A2>
#       <A3>1.46352900e-007</A3>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </TemperatureSensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="2" >
#     <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
#     <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
#       <SerialNumber>6890</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>19-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
#       <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
#       <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
#       <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
#       <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
#       <Coefficients equation="0" >
#         <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
#         <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
#         <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
#         <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
#         <M>0.0</M>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Coefficients equation="1" >
#         <G>-1.01817200e+000</G>
#         <H>1.59880100e-001</H>
#         <I>-2.82485700e-004</I>

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```

#       <J>4.70380400e-005</J>
#       <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#       <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
#       <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
#       <WBOTC>1.31914200e-007</WBOTC>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.00000</Offset>
#     </ConductivitySensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="3" >
#     <!-- Count, Pressure, Strain Gauge -->
#     <PressureSensor SensorID="46" >
#       <SerialNumber>2651322</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>03-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <PA0>-1.94517700e-001</PA0>
#       <PA1>4.56041200e-003</PA1>
#       <PA2>-1.84659800e-011</PA2>
#       <TEMPA0>-7.28625800e+001</TEMPA0>
#       <TEMPA1>5.01561200e-002</TEMPA1>
#       <TEMPA2>-4.16048500e-007</TEMPA2>
#       <PTCA0>5.24765500e+005</PTCA0>
#       <PTCA1>1.25927400e+000</PTCA1>
#       <PTCA2>-1.17485300e-001</PTCA2>
#       <PTCB0>2.62527500e+001</PTCB0>
#       <PTCB1>-2.50000000e-004</PTCB1>
#       <PTCB2>0.00000000e+000</PTCB2>
#       <Offset>0.000000</Offset>
#     </PressureSensor>
#   </sensor>
# </Sensors>
# datcnv_date = Jun 22 2023 14:36:54, 7.26.7.129 [datcnv_vars = 4]
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_120m_6890_
→data.hex C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_120m_6890_data.
→xmlcon
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 6888
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Jefrey\Documents\WHOTS-18_mcat_recovery\w18_135m_6888_data.hex
* Software version SeatermV2 2.8.0.119
* Temperature SN = 6888
* Conductivity SN = 6888
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 21 2023 08:27:22
* sample interval = 75 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>2.8.0.119</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>07-Nov-2018</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706888'>
*

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```
* <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.</Manufacturer>
*
* <FirmwareVersion>3.1</FirmwareVersion>
*
* <FirmwareDate>Jan 20 2012 17:33:01</FirmwareDate>
*
* <PCBAssembly>41647</PCBAssembly>
*
* <PCBAssembly>41610B</PCBAssembly>
*
* <PCBAssembly>41611D</PCBAssembly>
*
* <MfgDate>13 Mar 2009</MfgDate>
*
* <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
*
* <InternalSensors>
*
*   <Sensor id='Temperature'>
*
*     <type>temperature-1</type>
*
*     <SerialNumber>03706888</SerialNumber>
*
*   </Sensor>
*
*   <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*
*     <type>conductivity-1</type>
*
*     <SerialNumber>03706888</SerialNumber>
*
*   </Sensor>
*
*   <Sensor id='Pressure'>
*
*     <type>strain-0</type>
*
*     <SerialNumber>3418742</SerialNumber>
*
*   </Sensor>
*
* </InternalSensors>
*
* </HardwareData>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706888'>
*
*   <DateTime>2023-06-21T06:52:10</DateTime>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*
*   <Power>
*
*     <vMain> 6.93</vMain>
*
*     <vLith> 3.14</vLith>
```

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```
*
* </Power>
*
* <MemorySummary>
*
*   <Bytes>5759175</Bytes>
*
*   <Samples>383945</Samples>
*
*   <SamplesFree>175295</SamplesFree>
*
*   <SampleLength>15</SampleLength>
*
* </MemorySummary>
*
* <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
*
* </StatusData>
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706888'>
*
*   <PressureInstalled>yes</PressureInstalled>
*
*   <PumpInstalled>no</PumpInstalled>
*
*   <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering alternate</SampleDataFormat>
*
*   <OutputSalinity>yes</OutputSalinity>
*
*   <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*
*   <TxRealTime>no</TxRealTime>
*
*   <SampleInterval>75</SampleInterval>
*
*   <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
*
* </ConfigurationData>
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706888'>
*
*   <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>
*
*     <SerialNum>03706888</SerialNum>
*
*     <CalDate>19-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*     <A0>7.421835e-05</A0>
*
*     <A1>2.727849e-04</A1>
*
*     <A2>-2.340633e-06</A2>
*
*     <A3>1.491767e-07</A3>
*
*   </Calibration>
*
*   <Calibration format='WBCOND0' id='Conductivity'>
```

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```
*
*   <SerialNum>03706888</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>19-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*   <G>-1.009682e+00</G>
*
*   <H>1.484617e-01</H>
*
*   <I>-2.695763e-04</I>
*
*   <J>4.233032e-05</J>
*
*   <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*
*   <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*
*   <WBOTC>3.829161e-07</WBOTC>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* <Calibration format='STRAIN0' id='Pressure'>
*
*   <SerialNum>3418742</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>02-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*   <PA0>1.014290e-01</PA0>
*
*   <PA1>4.977376e-03</PA1>
*
*   <PA2>-2.425301e-11</PA2>
*
*   <PTCA0>5.244692e+05</PTCA0>
*
*   <PTCA1>2.221365e+00</PTCA1>
*
*   <PTCA2>-5.610904e-02</PTCA2>
*
*   <PTCB0>2.523738e+01</PTCB0>
*
*   <PTCB1>4.750000e-04</PTCB1>
*
*   <PTCB2>0.000000e+00</PTCB2>
*
*   <PTEMPA0>-7.037432e+01</PTEMPA0>
*
*   <PTEMPA1>5.113173e-02</PTEMPA1>
*
*   <PTEMPA2>-6.041479e-07</PTEMPA2>
*
*   <POFFSET>0.000000e+00</POFFSET>
*
*   <PRANGE>1.450000e+03</PRANGE>
*
* </Calibration>
```

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```

*
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
* <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706888'>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*
*   <Event type='PON reset' count='1' />
*
* </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
* <UserHeaderInsert>
* <![CDATA[
** WHOTS18 WHOTS18
** 55m 135m
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 5
# nvalues = 383945
# units = specified
# name 0 = condOS/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 2 = prdM: Pressure, Strain Gauge [db]
# name 3 = timeJV2: Time, Instrument [julian days]
# name 4 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = -0.000154, 5.418553
# span 1 = 0.6243, 29.5186
# span 2 = -0.512, 138.892
# span 3 = 204.000000, 537.284722
# span 4 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = seconds: 75
# start_time = Jul 23 2022 00:00:00 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="3" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>6888</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>19-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <A0>7.42183500e-005</A0>
#       <A1>2.72784900e-004</A1>
#       <A2>-2.34063300e-006</A2>
#       <A3>1.49176700e-007</A3>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </TemperatureSensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="2" >
#     <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
#     <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
#       <SerialNumber>6888</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>19-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
#       <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
#       <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
#       <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
#       <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
#       <Coefficients equation="0" >

```

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```

# <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
# <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
# <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
# <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
# <M>0.0</M>
# <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
# </Coefficients>
# <Coefficients equation="1" >
# <G>-1.00968200e+000</G>
# <H>1.48461700e-001</H>
# <I>-2.69576300e-004</I>
# <J>4.23303200e-005</J>
# <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
# <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
# <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
# <WBOTC>3.82916100e-007</WBOTC>
# </Coefficients>
# <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
# <Offset>0.00000</Offset>
# </ConductivitySensor>
# </sensor>
# <sensor Channel="3" >
# <!-- Count, Pressure, Strain Gauge -->
# <PressureSensor SensorID="46" >
# <SerialNumber>3418742</SerialNumber>
# <CalibrationDate>02-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
# <PA0>1.01429000e-001</PA0>
# <PA1>4.97737600e-003</PA1>
# <PA2>-2.42530100e-011</PA2>
# <PTempa0>-7.03743200e+001</PTempa0>
# <PTempa1>5.11317300e-002</PTempa1>
# <PTempa2>-6.04147900e-007</PTempa2>
# <PTCA0>5.24469200e+005</PTCA0>
# <PTCA1>2.22136500e+000</PTCA1>
# <PTCA2>-5.61090400e-002</PTCA2>
# <PTCB0>2.52373800e+001</PTCB0>
# <PTCB1>4.75000000e-004</PTCB1>
# <PTCB2>0.00000000e+000</PTCB2>
# <Offset>0.000000</Offset>
# </PressureSensor>
# </sensor>
# </Sensors>
# datcnv_date = Jun 22 2023 14:35:39, 7.26.7.129 [datcnv_vars = 4]
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_135m_6888_
→data.hex C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_135m_6888_data.
→xmlcon
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 6891
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Jefrey\Documents\WHOTS-18_mcat_recovery\w18_155m_6891_data.hex
* Software version SeatermV2 2.8.0.119
* Temperature SN = 6891
* Conductivity SN = 6891

```

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```
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 21 2023 11:17:45
* sample interval = 75 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>2.8.0.119</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>07-Nov-2018</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706891'>
*
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.</Manufacturer>
*
*   <FirmwareVersion>3.1</FirmwareVersion>
*
*   <FirmwareDate>Jan 20 2012 17:33:01</FirmwareDate>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41647</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41610B</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAssembly>41611D</PCBAssembly>
*
*   <MfgDate>16 Mar 2009</MfgDate>
*
*   <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
*
*   <InternalSensors>
*
*     <Sensor id='Temperature'>
*
*       <type>temperature-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03706891</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*     <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*
*       <type>conductivity-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03706891</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*     <Sensor id='Pressure'>
*
*       <type>strain-0</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>2651323</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*   </InternalSensors>
*
* </HardwareData>
```

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```
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706891'>
*
*   <DateTime>2023-06-21T08:45:05</DateTime>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*
*   <Power>
*
*     <vMain> 6.94</vMain>
*
*     <vLith> 3.16</vLith>
*
*   </Power>
*
*   <MemorySummary>
*
*     <Bytes>5760540</Bytes>
*
*     <Samples>384036</Samples>
*
*     <SamplesFree>175204</SamplesFree>
*
*     <SampleLength>15</SampleLength>
*
*   </MemorySummary>
*
*   <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
*
* </StatusData>
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706891'>
*
*   <PressureInstalled>yes</PressureInstalled>
*
*   <PumpInstalled>no</PumpInstalled>
*
*   <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering alternate</SampleDataFormat>
*
*   <OutputSalinity>yes</OutputSalinity>
*
*   <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*
*   <TxRealTime>no</TxRealTime>
*
*   <SampleInterval>75</SampleInterval>
*
*   <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
*
* </ConfigurationData>
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706891'>
*
*   <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>
*
*     <SerialNum>03706891</SerialNum>
*
*     <CalDate>19-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*   </CalibrationCoefficients>
```

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```
*      <A0>5.630907e-05</A0>
*
*      <A1>2.748230e-04</A1>
*
*      <A2>-2.508233e-06</A2>
*
*      <A3>1.532169e-07</A3>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* <Calibration format='WBCONDO' id='Conductivity'>
*
*   <SerialNum>03706891</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>19-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*   <G>-1.009419e+00</G>
*
*   <H>1.496878e-01</H>
*
*   <I>-2.838778e-04</I>
*
*   <J>4.451645e-05</J>
*
*   <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*
*   <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*
*   <WBOTC>3.524720e-07</WBOTC>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* <Calibration format='STRAIN0' id='Pressure'>
*
*   <SerialNum>2651323</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>02-Nov-21</CalDate>
*
*   <PA0>2.339704e-01</PA0>
*
*   <PA1>5.063485e-03</PA1>
*
*   <PA2>-2.256721e-11</PA2>
*
*   <PTCA0>5.250761e+05</PTCA0>
*
*   <PTCA1>5.206896e+00</PTCA1>
*
*   <PTCA2>-1.317569e-01</PTCA2>
*
*   <PTCB0>2.632875e+01</PTCB0>
*
*   <PTCB1>9.500000e-04</PTCB1>
*
*   <PTCB2>0.000000e+00</PTCB2>
*
```

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```

*      <PTEMPA0>-7.163238e+01</PTEMPA0>
*
*      <PTEMPA1>4.963964e-02</PTEMPA1>
*
*      <PTEMPA2>-3.160714e-07</PTEMPA2>
*
*      <POFFSET>4.000000e-02</POFFSET>
*
*      <PRANGE>1.450000e+03</PRANGE>
*
*    </Calibration>
*
*  </CalibrationCoefficients>
*  <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03706891'>
*
*    <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*
*    <Event type='PON reset' count='1' />
*
*  </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
*  <UserHeaderInsert>
*  <![CDATA[
** WHOTS18 WHOTS18
** 55m 155m
* ]]>
* </UserHeaderInsert>
# nquan = 5
# nvalues = 384036
# units = specified
# name 0 = condOS/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 2 = prdM: Pressure, Strain Gauge [db]
# name 3 = timeJV2: Time, Instrument [julian days]
# name 4 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = -0.000025, 5.424074
# span 1 = 0.1399, 29.5262
# span 2 = -0.194, 158.681
# span 3 = 204.000000, 537.363715
# span 4 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = seconds: 75
# start_time = Jul 23 2022 00:00:00 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="3" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>6891</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>19-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#       <A0>5.63090700e-005</A0>
#       <A1>2.74823000e-004</A1>
#       <A2>-2.50823300e-006</A2>
#       <A3>1.53216900e-007</A3>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </TemperatureSensor>
#   </sensor>

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```

# <sensor Channel="2" >
#   <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
#   <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
#     <SerialNumber>6891</SerialNumber>
#     <CalibrationDate>19-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#     <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
#     <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
#     <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
#     <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
#     <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
#     <Coefficients equation="0" >
#       <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
#       <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
#       <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
#       <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
#       <M>0.0</M>
#       <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#     </Coefficients>
#     <Coefficients equation="1" >
#       <G>-1.00941900e+000</G>
#       <H>1.49687800e-001</H>
#       <I>-2.83877800e-004</I>
#       <J>4.45164500e-005</J>
#       <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#       <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
#       <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
#       <WBOTC>3.52472000e-007</WBOTC>
#     </Coefficients>
#     <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#     <Offset>0.00000</Offset>
#   </ConductivitySensor>
# </sensor>
# <sensor Channel="3" >
#   <!-- Count, Pressure, Strain Gauge -->
#   <PressureSensor SensorID="46" >
#     <SerialNumber>2651323</SerialNumber>
#     <CalibrationDate>02-Nov-21</CalibrationDate>
#     <PA0>2.33970400e-001</PA0>
#     <PA1>5.06348500e-003</PA1>
#     <PA2>-2.25672100e-011</PA2>
#     <PTempa0>-7.16323800e+001</PTempa0>
#     <PTempa1>4.96396400e-002</PTempa1>
#     <PTempa2>-3.16071400e-007</PTempa2>
#     <PTCA0>5.25076100e+005</PTCA0>
#     <PTCA1>5.20689600e+000</PTCA1>
#     <PTCA2>-1.31756900e-001</PTCA2>
#     <PTCB0>2.63287500e+001</PTCB0>
#     <PTCB1>9.50000000e-004</PTCB1>
#     <PTCB2>0.00000000e+000</PTCB2>
#     <Offset>0.000000</Offset>
#   </PressureSensor>
# </sensor>
# </Sensors>
# datchv_date = Jun 22 2023 14:35:00, 7.26.7.129 [datchv_vars = 4]
# datchv_in = C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_155m_6891_
→data.hex C:\Users\santi\Documents\Work\whots\whots18_mooring\mcat_data\w18_155m_6891_data.
→xmlcon

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```
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*
```

```
# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 11391
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W18\DATA\SUBSURFACE\SBE37_11391_
  DEEPTEMP.hex
* Software version SeatermV2 2.8.0.119
* Temperature SN = 11391
* Conductivity SN = 11391
* System UpLoad Time = Jun 21 2023 18:58:34
* sample interval = 300 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>2.8.0.119</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>07-Nov-2018</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03711391'>
*
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.</Manufacturer>
*
*   <FirmwareVersion>3.1</FirmwareVersion>
*
*   <FirmwareDate>Jan 20 2012 17:33:01</FirmwareDate>
*
*   <PCBAsembly>41647.1</PCBAsembly>
*
*   <PCBAsembly>41610B</PCBAsembly>
*
*   <PCBAsembly>41611D</PCBAsembly>
*
*   <MfgDate>14-Nov-2013</MfgDate>
*
*   <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
*
*   <InternalSensors>
*
*     <Sensor id='Temperature'>
*
*       <type>temperature-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03711391</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
*
*     <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*
*       <type>conductivity-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03711391</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>
```

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```

*
*   <Sensor id='Pressure'>
*
*       <type>strain-0</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>2146837</SerialNumber>
*
*   </Sensor>
*
* </InternalSensors>
*
* </HardwareData>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03711391'>
*
*   <DateTime>2023-06-21T18:34:35</DateTime>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*
*   <Power>
*
*       <vMain> 6.94</vMain>
*
*       <vLith> 3.25</vLith>
*
*   </Power>
*
*   <MemorySummary>
*
*       <Bytes>1441905</Bytes>
*
*       <Samples>96127</Samples>
*
*       <SamplesFree>463113</SamplesFree>
*
*       <SampleLength>15</SampleLength>
*
*   </MemorySummary>
*
*   <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
*
* </StatusData>
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03711391'>
*
*   <PressureInstalled>yes</PressureInstalled>
*
*   <PumpInstalled>no</PumpInstalled>
*
*   <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering</SampleDataFormat>
*
*   <OutputSalinity>no</OutputSalinity>
*
*   <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*
*   <TxRealTime>yes</TxRealTime>
*
*   <SampleInterval>300</SampleInterval>

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```
*
*   <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
*
* </ConfigurationData>
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03711391'>
*
*   <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>
*
*     <SerialNum>03711391</SerialNum>
*
*     <CalDate>10-Mar-22</CalDate>
*
*     <A0>-8.177573e-05</A0>
*
*     <A1>3.039413e-04</A1>
*
*     <A2>-4.298826e-06</A2>
*
*     <A3>1.961128e-07</A3>
*
*   </Calibration>
*
*   <Calibration format='WBCOND0' id='Conductivity'>
*
*     <SerialNum>03711391</SerialNum>
*
*     <CalDate>10-Mar-22</CalDate>
*
*     <G>-9.952020e-01</G>
*
*     <H>1.383237e-01</H>
*
*     <I>-1.641585e-04</I>
*
*     <J>3.163423e-05</J>
*
*     <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*
*     <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*
*     <WBOTC>1.459091e-06</WBOTC>
*
*   </Calibration>
*
*   <Calibration format='STRAIN0' id='Pressure'>
*
*     <SerialNum>2146837</SerialNum>
*
*     <CalDate>08-Mar-22</CalDate>
*
*     <PA0>-2.378486e+01</PA0>
*
*     <PA1>3.123519e-02</PA1>
*
*     <PA2>2.005387e-09</PA2>
*
*

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*      <PTCA0>5.227441e+05</PTCA0>
*
*      <PTCA1>-3.392557e+01</PTCA1>
*
*      <PTCA2>8.374315e-02</PTCA2>
*
*      <PTCBO>9.968137e+01</PTCBO>
*
*      <PTCB1>-8.810519e-03</PTCB1>
*
*      <PTCB2>0.000000e+00</PTCB2>
*
*      <PTEMPA0>-9.517107e+01</PTEMPA0>
*
*      <PTEMPA1>3.984701e-02</PTEMPA1>
*
*      <PTEMPA2>1.262323e-06</PTEMPA2>
*
*      <POFFSET>0.000000e+00</POFFSET>
*
*      <PRANGE>1.015300e+04</PRANGE>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* </CalibrationCoefficients>
* <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03711391'>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*
*   <Event type='PON reset' count='1' />
*
* </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
# nquan = 6
# nvalues = 96127
# units = specified
# name 0 = condOS/m: Conductivity [S/m]
# name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
# name 2 = timeJV2: Time, Instrument [julian days]
# name 3 = sal00: Salinity, Practical [PSU]
# name 4 = prdM: Pressure, Strain Gauge [db]
# name 5 = flag: 0.000e+00
# span 0 = 0.000043, 5.446433
# span 1 = 1.4674, 36.8171
# span 2 = 204.000000, 537.770833
# span 3 = 0.0088, 35.2750
# span 4 = -0.424, 4784.020
# span 5 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
# interval = seconds: 300
# start_time = Jul 23 2022 00:00:00 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="3" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>11391</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>10-Mar-22</CalibrationDate>

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```

# <A0>-8.17757300e-005</A0>
# <A1>3.03941300e-004</A1>
# <A2>-4.29882600e-006</A2>
# <A3>1.96112800e-007</A3>
# <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
# <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
# </TemperatureSensor>
# </sensor>
# <sensor Channel="2" >
# <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
# <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
# <SerialNumber>11391</SerialNumber>
# <CalibrationDate>10-Mar-22</CalibrationDate>
# <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
# <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
# <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
# <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
# <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
# <Coefficients equation="0" >
# <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
# <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
# <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
# <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
# <M>0.0</M>
# <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
# </Coefficients>
# <Coefficients equation="1" >
# <G>-9.95202000e-001</G>
# <H>1.38323700e-001</H>
# <I>-1.64158500e-004</I>
# <J>3.16342300e-005</J>
# <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
# <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
# <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
# <WBOTC>1.45909100e-006</WBOTC>
# </Coefficients>
# <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
# <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
# </ConductivitySensor>
# </sensor>
# <sensor Channel="3" >
# <!-- Count, Pressure, Strain Gauge -->
# <PressureSensor SensorID="46" >
# <SerialNumber>2146837</SerialNumber>
# <CalibrationDate>08-Mar-22</CalibrationDate>
# <PA0>-2.37848600e+001</PA0>
# <PA1>3.12351900e-002</PA1>
# <PA2>2.00538700e-009</PA2>
# <PTempa0>-9.51710700e+001</PTempa0>
# <PTempa1>3.98470100e-002</PTempa1>
# <PTempa2>1.26232300e-006</PTempa2>
# <PTCA0>5.22744100e+005</PTCA0>
# <PTCA1>-3.39255700e+001</PTCA1>
# <PTCA2>8.37431500e-002</PTCA2>
# <PTCB0>9.96813700e+001</PTCB0>
# <PTCB1>-8.81051900e-003</PTCB1>

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```

#       <PTCB2>0.0000000e+000</PTCB2>
#       <Offset>0.000000</Offset>
#       </PressureSensor>
#     </sensor>
# </Sensors>
# datcnv_date = Jun 21 2023 18:59:36, 7.26.7.129 [datcnv_vars = 5]
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W18\DATA\SUBSURFACE\sbe37_11391_
→deeptemp.hex C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W18\DATA\SUBSURFACE\sbe37_
→11391_deeptemp.XMLCON
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*

# Metadata for Sensor Serial Number: 12241
* Sea-Bird SBE37SM-RS232 Data File:
* FileName = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W18\DATA\SUBSURFACE\SBE37_12241_
→DEEPTEMP.hex
* Software version SeatermV2 2.8.0.119
* Temperature SN = 12241
* Conductivity SN = 12241
* System Upload Time = Jun 21 2023 19:07:23
* sample interval = 300 seconds
* <ApplicationData>
* <Seaterm232>
* <SoftwareVersion>2.8.0.119</SoftwareVersion>
* <BuildDate>07-Nov-2018</BuildDate>
* </Seaterm232>
* </ApplicationData>
* <InstrumentState>
* <HardwareData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03712241'>
*
*   <Manufacturer>Sea-Bird Electronics, Inc.</Manufacturer>
*
*   <FirmwareVersion>3.1</FirmwareVersion>
*
*   <FirmwareDate>Jan 20 2012 17:33:01</FirmwareDate>
*
*   <PCBAAssembly>41647.1</PCBAAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAAssembly>41610B</PCBAAssembly>
*
*   <PCBAAssembly>41611D</PCBAAssembly>
*
*   <MfgDate> 9 MAY 2014</MfgDate>
*
*   <FirmwareLoader>SBE 37 FirmwareLoader V 1.0</FirmwareLoader>
*
*   <InternalSensors>
*
*     <Sensor id='Temperature'>
*
*       <type>temperature-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03712241</SerialNumber>
*
*     </Sensor>

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```

*
*   <Sensor id='Conductivity'>
*
*       <type>conductivity-1</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>03712241</SerialNumber>
*
*   </Sensor>
*
*   <Sensor id='Pressure'>
*
*       <type>strain-0</type>
*
*       <SerialNumber>2153123</SerialNumber>
*
*   </Sensor>
*
* </InternalSensors>
*
* </HardwareData>
* <StatusData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03712241'>
*
*   <DateTime>2023-06-21T18:43:23</DateTime>
*
*   <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*
*   <Power>
*
*       <vMain> 6.98</vMain>
*
*       <vLith> 3.24</vLith>
*
*   </Power>
*
*   <MemorySummary>
*
*       <Bytes>1441935</Bytes>
*
*       <Samples>96129</Samples>
*
*       <SamplesFree>463111</SamplesFree>
*
*       <SampleLength>15</SampleLength>
*
*   </MemorySummary>
*
*   <AutonomousSampling>no, stop command</AutonomousSampling>
*
* </StatusData>
* <ConfigurationData DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03712241'>
*
*   <PressureInstalled>yes</PressureInstalled>
*
*   <PumpInstalled>no</PumpInstalled>
*
*   <SampleDataFormat>converted engineering</SampleDataFormat>

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```
*
* <OutputSalinity>no</OutputSalinity>
*
* <OutputSV>no</OutputSV>
*
* <TxRealTime>no</TxRealTime>
*
* <SampleInterval>300</SampleInterval>
*
* <SyncMode>no</SyncMode>
*
* </ConfigurationData>
* <CalibrationCoefficients DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03712241'>
*
* <Calibration format='TEMP1' id='Temperature'>
*
*   <SerialNum>03712241</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>25-Feb-22</CalDate>
*
*   <A0>-1.173750e-04</A0>
*
*   <A1>3.062532e-04</A1>
*
*   <A2>-4.331589e-06</A2>
*
*   <A3>1.981291e-07</A3>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* <Calibration format='WBCOND0' id='Conductivity'>
*
*   <SerialNum>03712241</SerialNum>
*
*   <CalDate>25-Feb-22</CalDate>
*
*   <G>-9.871401e-01</G>
*
*   <H>1.724485e-01</H>
*
*   <I>-2.191593e-04</I>
*
*   <J>4.628980e-05</J>
*
*   <PCOR>-9.570000e-08</PCOR>
*
*   <TCOR>3.250000e-06</TCOR>
*
*   <WBOTC>1.392140e-07</WBOTC>
*
* </Calibration>
*
* <Calibration format='STRAIN0' id='Pressure'>
*
*   <SerialNum>2153123</SerialNum>
*
```

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```

*      <CalDate>16-Feb-22</CalDate>
*
*      <PA0>-1.777185e+00</PA0>
*
*      <PA1>3.015012e-02</PA1>
*
*      <PA2>1.884953e-09</PA2>
*
*      <PTCA0>5.252472e+05</PTCA0>
*
*      <PTCA1>-8.637300e+00</PTCA1>
*
*      <PTCA2>2.466118e-01</PTCA2>
*
*      <PTCB0>1.031030e+02</PTCB0>
*
*      <PTCB1>-9.453885e-03</PTCB1>
*
*      <PTCB2>0.000000e+00</PTCB2>
*
*      <PTEMPA0>-9.679022e+01</PTEMPA0>
*
*      <PTEMPA1>4.040292e-02</PTEMPA1>
*
*      <PTEMPA2>1.142765e-06</PTEMPA2>
*
*      <POFFSET>0.000000e+00</POFFSET>
*
*      <PRANGE>1.015300e+04</PRANGE>
*
*    </Calibration>
*
*  </CalibrationCoefficients>
*  <EventCounters DeviceType='SBE37SM-RS232' SerialNumber='03712241'>
*
*    <EventSummary numEvents='1' />
*
*    <Event type='PON reset' count='1' />
*
*  </EventCounters></InstrumentState>
*  # nquan = 6
*  # nvalues = 96129
*  # units = specified
*  # name 0 = cond0S/m: Conductivity [S/m]
*  # name 1 = tv290C: Temperature [ITS-90, deg C]
*  # name 2 = timeJV2: Time, Instrument [julian days]
*  # name 3 = sal00: Salinity, Practical [PSU]
*  # name 4 = prdM: Pressure, Strain Gauge [db]
*  # name 5 = flag: 0.000e+00
*  # span 0 = 7.8785e-07, 5.444069
*  # span 1 = 1.4674, 38.2886
*  # span 2 = 204.000000, 537.777778
*  # span 3 = 0.0057, 35.2606
*  # span 4 = -2.056, 4791.746
*  # span 5 = 0.0000e+00, 0.0000e+00
*  # interval = seconds: 300

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```

# start_time = Jul 23 2022 00:00:00 [Instrument's time stamp, first data scan]
# bad_flag = -9.990e-29
# <Sensors count="3" >
#   <sensor Channel="1" >
#     <!-- Count, Temperature -->
#     <TemperatureSensor SensorID="58" >
#       <SerialNumber>12241</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>25-Feb-22</CalibrationDate>
#       <A0>-1.17375000e-004</A0>
#       <A1>3.06253200e-004</A1>
#       <A2>-4.33158900e-006</A2>
#       <A3>1.98129100e-007</A3>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </TemperatureSensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="2" >
#     <!-- Frequency 0, Conductivity -->
#     <ConductivitySensor SensorID="3" >
#       <SerialNumber>12241</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>25-Feb-22</CalibrationDate>
#       <UseG_J>1</UseG_J>
#       <!-- Cell const and series R are applicable only for wide range sensors. -->
#       <SeriesR>0.0000</SeriesR>
#       <CellConst>2000.0000</CellConst>
#       <ConductivityType>1</ConductivityType>
#       <Coefficients equation="0" >
#         <A>0.00000000e+000</A>
#         <B>0.00000000e+000</B>
#         <C>0.00000000e+000</C>
#         <D>0.00000000e+000</D>
#         <M>0.0</M>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Coefficients equation="1" >
#         <G>-9.87140100e-001</G>
#         <H>1.72448500e-001</H>
#         <I>-2.19159300e-004</I>
#         <J>4.62898000e-005</J>
#         <CPcor>-9.57000000e-008</CPcor>
#         <CTcor>3.2500e-006</CTcor>
#         <!-- WBOTC not applicable unless ConductivityType = 1. -->
#         <WBOTC>1.39214000e-007</WBOTC>
#       </Coefficients>
#       <Slope>1.00000000</Slope>
#       <Offset>0.0000</Offset>
#     </ConductivitySensor>
#   </sensor>
#   <sensor Channel="3" >
#     <!-- Count, Pressure, Strain Gauge -->
#     <PressureSensor SensorID="46" >
#       <SerialNumber>2153123</SerialNumber>
#       <CalibrationDate>16-Feb-22</CalibrationDate>
#       <PA0>-1.77718500e+000</PA0>
#       <PA1>3.01501200e-002</PA1>
#       <PA2>1.88495300e-009</PA2>

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```
# <PTempa0>-9.67902200e+001</PTempa0>
# <PTempa1>4.04029200e-002</PTempa1>
# <PTempa2>1.14276500e-006</PTempa2>
# <PTCA0>5.25247200e+005</PTCA0>
# <PTCA1>-8.63730000e+000</PTCA1>
# <PTCA2>2.46611800e-001</PTCA2>
# <PTCB0>1.03103000e+002</PTCB0>
# <PTCB1>-9.45388500e-003</PTCB1>
# <PTCB2>0.00000000e+000</PTCB2>
# <Offset>0.000000</Offset>
# </PressureSensor>
# </sensor>
# </Sensors>
# datcnv_date = Jun 21 2023 19:07:27, 7.26.7.129 [datcnv_vars = 5]
# datcnv_in = C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W18\DATA\SUBSURFACE\sbe37_12241_
→deeptemp.hex C:\Users\Rtgra\Documents\Buoy Systems\ORS\WHOTS\W18\DATA\SUBSURFACE\sbe37_
→12241_deeptemp.XMLCON
# datcnv_skipover = 0
# file_type = ascii
*END*
```

References

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- Sean P. Whelan, Robert A. Weller, Roger Lukas, Frank Bradley, Jeffrey Lord, Jason C. Smith, Frank B. Bahr, Paul Lethaby, and Jeffrey Snyder. Whoi hawaii ocean timeseries station (whots) : whots-3 mooring turnaround cruise report. Technical Report, Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, 2007. URL: <https://hdl.handle.net/1912/1825>, doi:10.1575/1912/1825.
- Sean P. Whelan, Albert J. Plueddemann, Roger Lukas, Jeffrey Lord, Paul Lethaby, Jason C. Smith, Frank B. Bahr, Nancy R. Galbraith, and Christopher L. Sabine. Whoi hawaii ocean timeseries station (whots): whots-4 2007 mooring turnaround cruise report. Technical Report, Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, 1 2008. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1575/1912/2504>.
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